

**AGENT-BASED
SUPPORT TOOL FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURE POLICIES**

D1.3 Characterisation of EU and other supranational statistics datasets

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the methodology defined within the AGRICORE project to characterise socio-economic statistical data sources useful for performing agricultural research analysis. This methodology has been developed as part of the first of the work packages defined in the AGRICORE project. AGRICORE is a research project proposing an innovative way to apply agent-based modelling to improve the capacities of policymakers to evaluate the impact of agricultural-related measurements under and outside the framework of the Common Agricultural Policy. This project was funded by the European Commission as a result of the RUR-04-2018 call, part of the H2020 programme.

In the introduction, the basis on which the methodology has been developed is presented, i.e., the ARDIT tool and the AGRICORE DCAT-AP 2.0 ontology. Then, the proposed methodology is detailed including also the definition of all the fields to be filled while characterising a dataset in ARDIT. As part of this methodology, also all the main challenges encountered during the characterisation of the datasets have been explained, illustrating the proposed solutions. After that, also the methodology proposed to guarantee that the tool ARDIT remains efficiently working is described, relying on a continuous upgrade and maintenance of the data. Finally, some conclusions regarding the characterisation process and the need for a governance strategy to ensure the survival of the ARDIT after the project are provided.

It is important to remark that although this deliverable has been developed in the framework of the AGRICORE project, the participating partners have aimed for broader usage of the proposed methodology. As the final goal of this work package, the proposed EU Index Tool (now renamed as Agricultural Research Data Index Tool (ARDIT)) aims to serve as a central entry point for locating useful datasets useful for agricultural research.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
AC(s)	Agricultural Census(es)
AP	Application Profile
API	Application Programming Interface
ARDIT	Agricultural Research Data Index Tool
CSV	comma-separated values
DCAT	Data Catalogue
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Application Profile
DG-AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
EC	European commission
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
ESS	European Statistical System
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GUI	Graphic User Interface
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
MSs	Member States
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RDF	Resource Description Framework
TB	Table
UoA	Unit of Analysis
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VOCAB-DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

The objective of ARDIT is to support agricultural researchers to identify the most suitable datasets based on model requirements and research questions without having to retrieve them. ARDIT will represent a great help if considering that generally also just obtaining preliminary access to the dataset can result in expending a significant effort of the researcher which could have been in vain especially in case the data was, upon retrieval and inspection, inadequate (e.g., due to an undesired unit of analysis of the dataset or the lack of one or more key variables). In addition, the amount of data necessary to use large-scale models, or combinations of multiple models, is likely to be significant. Therefore, properly organising the relevant datasets to be ready for use, by selecting or manipulating parts of them, could be a limiting factor for (some) researchers. Specifically, this activity has relied on having access to good and complete descriptions (i.e., metadata) of the contents of the dataset, especially on the characteristics of the variables contained in them. The methodology presented in the following sections has been developed to collect all the relevant information on datasets, such that this knowledge could be stored, manipulated and displayed employing the AGRICORE ontology. Lastly, this information will be gathered and hosted in the ARDIT, which will be then used to allow researchers to identify useful data sources for them.

The proposed methodology to characterise agricultural datasets is described through the three main elements that it is composed of:

1. The proposed ontology: The AGRICORE DCAT-AP 2.0 Extension
2. The ARDIT tool
3. The data governance process

This process has been applied within the project to characterise an extensive set of data sources covering EU-wide and local datasets (especially those relevant to the three use cases foreseen in the AGRICORE project). Moreover, this methodology also describes the process that should be followed after the project to add contents in ARDIT.

As already said, one of the goals of the AGRICORE project is to provide the ARDIT as a tool for agricultural researchers to facilitate the task of identifying relevant and useful data for performing agricultural policy analysis. To do so, the AGRICORE partners devised a characterisation methodology (detailed in the next sections) for describing the available data sources and their content to enable proper mapping and searching capabilities over the gathered information. To design such a methodology, one of the key elements is the definition and the adoption of an ontology (or a set of them), which allows:

- To share a **common understanding** of the structure of information among people or software agents.
- To enable the **reuse** of domain knowledge.
- To make domain **assumptions explicit**.
- To **separate domain** knowledge from the **operational** knowledge
- To **analyse** domain knowledge
- To secure the interoperability of datasets

All these motivations are present in the AGRICORE project. Indeed, to ensure the long-term usefulness of the ARDIT platform well beyond the scope of the AGRICORE project, it has been critical to develop it in a way that it is easy to upgrade and maintain as well as user-friendly for the research community as a whole. Accordingly, during the first months of the project,

consortium partners performed an analysis of existing ontologies that could be used for developing the ARDIT.

In order to build the ontology used for characterising the datasets on the ARDIT, Protégé 5¹ was selected due to the large community deeming it a reliable and flexible collaborative tool available as an open-source product both in a desktop and web version. As reported by previous studies, it has a suite of tools to construct domain models and knowledge-based applications with ontologies. It implements a rich set of knowledge-modelling structures and actions that support the creation, visualisation and manipulation of ontologies in various representation formats. It can be customised to provide domain-friendly support to creating knowledge models and entering data. Also, it can be extended by a plug-in architecture and Java-based API for building knowledge-base tools and applications. Protégé allows the definition of classes, class hierarchy's variables, variable-value restrictions, and the relationships between classes and the properties of these relationships.

Within the next phases of the AGRICORE project, the ontology will allow the application of semantic queries in ARDIT for searching datasets information and characterisations. Likewise, it will allow a continuous enrichment of the number and quality of datasets characterisations through the ARDIT Graphic User Interface (GUI) tailored to fit the data model structure described by the ontology.

¹ <http://protegeproject.github.io/protege/getting-started>

2 EU and other supranational statistical datasets

A dataset is a collection of one or more tables, schemas, points, and/or objects that are grouped together either because they are stored in the same location or because they are related to the same subject.

An EU statistical dataset is a collection of data related to European socio-economic conditions. The variables within these datasets may therefore be economic or social. The economic variables are measures that describe economic units, like the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inflation or interest rates of/recorded in a country; on the other hand, social variables are those concerning the characteristics of a relevant population such as - among others - age, gender, culture, religion.

The typical variables of EU socio-economic datasets are those defined by the EU as Euro indicators which provide general economic information on the European area, EU and individual Member States (MSs). Most Euro indicators are produced by Eurostat. They are complemented by selected monetary and financial indicators produced by the European Central Bank and by data from economic tendencies surveys produced by the Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs of the EC².

The main topics covered by these indicators are:

- Balance of payments (e.g., foreign direct investments)
- Business and consumer surveys
- Industry and services (e.g., industrial production, retail trade, turnover in services)
- International trade
- Labour market (e.g., unemployment, labour cost, job vacancies)
- Monetary and financial indicators (e.g., interest rates, exchange rates)
- National accounts (e.g., GDP, debt and deficit, investments, savings, consumption)
- Prices (e.g., inflation rate, house prices)

Most of the European socio-economic datasets are available from Eurostat, the statistical office of the EU. Eurostat produces European statistics in partnership with National Statistical Institutes and other national authorities in the EU MSs³. This partnership is known as the European Statistical System (ESS) and also includes the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) countries. The EU MSs and EFTA countries collect data and compile statistics for national and EU purposes. The ESS functions as a network in which Eurostat leads the way in the harmonisation of statistics, in close cooperation with the national statistical authorities.

Collecting statistical data sets is aimed at developing ex-post or ex-ante analyses of the different policies that the EU MSs governments and the EU itself define in their government action. In this regard, it is necessary to distinguish databases that are made public to citizens and stakeholders and databases that, on the other hand, have been developed for a specific purpose or policy. An example is given by the economic, social and structural databases developed by Eurostat and those specific for the agricultural sector coordinated by DG-AGRI for the agricultural sector such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN).

Public databases refer to structural or business-cycle information of a general nature, reporting data that describe social and economic phenomena in an aggregate way or by type (e.g., production, consumption). On the other hand, databases that refer to specific sectors and which

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/euro-indicators>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/about/who-we-are>

report sensitive information, as they may refer specifically to individual production units, are reserved only for policymakers as well as selected and authorised researchers.

For the purposes of the AGRICORE project, the most relevant datasets are those concerning the Agriculture, Forestry and Fishery sector, whose data are collected by countries through surveys and from administrative data sources.

Countries collect data through two kinds of surveys:

- an agricultural census (AC) every 10 years
- several sample-based surveys in the intervening time between two ACs.

The sampling rate depends upon the country and the survey year. It varies between 2.5% and 100% of the total population of agricultural holdings.

The use of administrative sources has been established in Regulation (EC) No 1166/2008. According to Article 4 of Regulation (EC) No 1166/2008, provided that the information from the administrative source is of at least equal quality to information obtained from statistical surveys, countries are allowed to use information from:

- The Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) established in Council Regulation (EC) No 1782/2003,
- The System for the Identification and Registration of Bovine Animals established in Regulation (EC) No 1760/2000,
- The Organic Farming Registers set up pursuant to Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007,
- Administrative sources associated with the cultivation of genetically modified crops and the specific rural development measures referred to in Annex III of the Regulation (EC) No 1166/2008.

Moreover, in case of countries decide to use any administrative source other than those specified above, they can do so on condition that the EC will be informed in advance and will be provided with a description of the used methods and quality of the data from this administrative source.

Only data and metadata having been entirely validated can be disseminated.

Besides Eurostat, the FADN is an EU data source aimed at exploring, mainly, the economic situation of the EU agriculture and it is an important informative source for understanding the impact of the measures taken under the common agricultural policy as well as in planning and monitoring it. The FADN monitors farms' income and business activities⁴. FADN is the only source of microeconomic data based on harmonised bookkeeping principles. It is based on national surveys and only covers EU agricultural holdings which, due to their size, can be considered commercial. FADN basically serves two objectives: on one hand, it serves as a basis for agricultural sector analyses whereby the profitability of agricultural holdings is in the focus. On the other hand, it is an instrument for agricultural policy analyses. In the Member States, the data are collected according to EU-wide standardised guidelines. However, there are national distinctions concerning data availability. The FADN databases refer to two organisational types of data distinguishing between databases relating to individual information and referring to individual farms and databases that report average and aggregate information. The first type of database is not public, while the second is public.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/farming/facts-and-figures/farms-farming-and-innovation/structures-and-economics/economics/fadn_en

3 Methodology for the selection and characterisation

3.1 Selected datasets

In Task 1.3, we focused on the characterisation of EU statistics datasets. During Task 1.1, a preliminary selection of EU statistics datasets was done and taken as starting point, but due to the large number of datasets that might provide relevant information for the analysis of the impact of policy (reforms) on agriculture, a further selection has been made in order to identify a general but representative methodology and to provide an extensive overview on how to characterise this kind of datasets.

In the context of the AGRICORE project, 72 Tables of the Eurostat database, 34 tables of the OECD, 48 tables of FAOstat and the FADN have been characterised.

OECD and Eurostat have a unique entry point to dataset access. For Eurostat, it has been decided to characterise the “Tables by themes”, as the “Database by themes” are mostly dynamic data views. However, for “Environmental and Energy” datasets it has been decided to characterise using Database by themes because only in these sections the various sectors (NACE activities) can be differentiated, and the AGRICORE scope focuses on agricultural activities.

In the OECD case, we still have a subdivision by themes; for our project, we decided to characterise the tables under the themes:

- Agriculture and Fisheries: where we find tables concerning Agricultural Outlook, Agricultural Policy Indicators and Environmental Indicators for Agriculture.
- Environment: where we find tables concerning Air and Climate, Water, Material Resources, Forest, Biodiversity, Land Resources, Innovation in environment-related technologies, Environmental policy, Agri-Environmental indicators and Green Growth.

We have also characterised a table on Labour Force Statistics and one on Non-Medical Determinants of Health as they could be useful for the purpose of the project.

Unlike Eurostat and OECD, the FAO database does not provide predefined tables, but it offers the possibility for the user to build his own with the desired data. A division by themes is however possible and we have characterised tables on Production, Trade, Food Balance, Prices, Inputs, Population, Investment, Agri-Environmental Indicators, Climate Change and Forestry.

For the EU FADN, an interactive online portal is available where the user can build a table containing all the desired variables, therefore it has been decided to make a single characterisation by treating the portal as a single interactive table with a complete list of socio-economic variables.

The dataset characterisation effort in Task 1.3 was mostly carried out by UNIPR, while for Task 1.4 to Task 1.6 effort was distributed among partners.

Table 1 below contains all the datasets that have been identified and characterised in the context of Task 1.3, depicting the provider and the location of the dataset in the institutional repository, in terms of the folder and sub-folder.

Table 1: List of datasets characterised within AGRICORE Task 1.3

Dataset Provider	Folder	Sub-Folder/Dataset Name
FAO	Production	Crops and livestock products
FAO	Production	Production Indices
FAO	Production	Value of Agricultural Production
FAO	Trade	Crops and livestock products
FAO	Trade	Detailed trade matrix
FAO	Trade	Trade Indices
FAO	Food Balance	Food balances
FAO	Food Balance	Supply Utilization Accounts
FAO	Food Security	Suite of Food Security Indicators
FAO	Prices	Producer Prices
FAO	Prices	Consumer Price Indices
FAO	Prices	Deflators
FAO	Prices	Exchange rates - Annual
FAO	Inputs	Fertilizers by Nutrient
FAO	Inputs	Fertilizers by Product
FAO	Inputs	Pesticides Use
FAO	Inputs	Pesticides Trade
FAO	Inputs	Land Use
FAO	Population	Employment Indicators
FAO	Investment	Government Expenditure
FAO	Investment	Credit to Agriculture
FAO	Investment	Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)
FAO	Investment	Country Investment Statistics Profile
FAO	Macro-Statistics	Capital Stock
FAO	Macro-Statistics	Macro Indicators
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Fertilisers indicators
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Land use indicators
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Land Cover
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Livestock Patterns
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Livestock Manure
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Pesticides indicators
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Emissions intensities
FAO	Agri-Environmental Indicators	Temperature change
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	emissions Total
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Enteric Fermentation
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Manure Management
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Rice Cultivation
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Synthetic Fertilizers
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Manure applied to Soils

FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Manure left on Pasture
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Crop Residues
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Burning - Crop Residues
FAO	Climate Change - Emissions - Agriculture	Energy Use
FAO	Forestry	Forestry Production and Trade
FAO	Forestry	Forestry Trade Flows
FAO	ASTI R&D Indicators	ASTI-Researchers
FAO	ASTI R&D Indicators	ASTI-Expenditures
OECD	Agriculture and Fisheries	OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 1990-2020
OECD	Agriculture and Fisheries	Monitoring and evaluation : Reference Tables
OECD	Agriculture and Fisheries	Monitoring and evaluation : Single commodity indicators
OECD	Agriculture and Fisheries	Agri-Environmental indicators: Nutrients balance
OECD	Environment	Greenhouse gas emissions by source
OECD	Environment	Air emissions by source
OECD	Environment	Air Emission Accounts
OECD	Environment	Generation and discharge of wastewater
OECD	Environment	Freshwater abstractions
OECD	Environment	Water made available for use
OECD	Environment	Wastewater treatment
OECD	Environment	Treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants
OECD	Environment	Food Waste
OECD	Environment	Material Resources
OECD	Environment	Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
OECD	Environment	Threatened species
OECD	Environment	Land cover in countries
OECD	Environment	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
OECD	Environment	Loss and gain of natural and semi-natural vegetated land
OECD	Environment	Surface water
OECD	Environment	Land use
OECD	Environment	Technology development
OECD	Environment	Environmental Policy Stringency Index
OECD	Environment	Environmentally related tax revenue accounts
OECD	Environment	Agri-Environmental indicators: Nutrients balance
OECD	Environment	Agri-Environmental others indicators
OECD	Environment	All indicators
OECD	Environment	Mineral and Energy Resources
OECD	Environment	Embodied Materials in Trade
OECD	Environment	Nutrient Balance of Exports
OECD	Environment	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
OECD	Health	Non-Medical Determinants of Health - Key Indicators
OECD	Labour	Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Regional statistics (t_reg)	Animal populations by NUTS 2 regions (tgs00045)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Regional statistics (t_reg)	Production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions (tgs00046)

Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings by agricultural area (tag00001)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings by economic size of the farm (Standard Output in Euro) (tag00123)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings by crops (tag00007)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings with livestock (tag00124)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Farm labour force (tag00020)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings by age of holder (tag00029)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Agricultural holdings by age of manager (tag00125)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Livestock density index (tai09)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Crop output - basic and producer prices (tag00054)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Animal output - basic and producer prices (tag00055)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Output of the agricultural industry - basic and producer prices (tag00102)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Gross value added of the agricultural industry - basic and producer prices (tag00056)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Indicator A of the income from agricultural activity (tag00057)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of oats (tag00061)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of barley (tag00060)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of soft wheat (tag00059)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of maize (tag00062)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of main crop potatoes (tag00063)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of sugar beet (unit value) (tag00064)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of calves (tag00065)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of pigs (light) (tag00066)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of piglets (tag00067)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of sheep (tag00069)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of chickens (live 1st choice) (tag00068)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of fresh eggs (tag00071)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Selling prices of raw cow's milk (tag00070)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Producer price indices, total agricultural production (tag00046)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Producer price indices, crop products (tag00048)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Producer price indices, animals and animal products (tag00050)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Purchase price indices, total means of agricultural production (tag00052)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Utilised agricultural area by categories (tag00025)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Cereals for the production of grain (including seed) by area, production and humidity (tag00027)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Wheat and spelt by area, production and humidity (tag00047)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Rye and winter cereal mixtures by area, production and humidity (tag00049)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Barley by area, production and humidity (tag00051)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Oats and spring cereal mixtures by area, production and humidity (tag00053)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Grain maize and corn-cob-mix by area, production and humidity (tag00093)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain (including seed and mixtures of cereals and pulses) by area, production and humidity (tag00094)

Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Rape, turnip rape, sunflower seeds and soya by area (tag00100)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Green maize by area, production and humidity (tag00101)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Root crops and plants harvested green from arable land by area (tag00103)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Fresh vegetables and strawberries by area (tag00115)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Permanent crops for human consumption by area (tag00120)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Grapes by production (tag00121)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Olives by production (tag00122)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Collection of cow's milk (tag00037)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of butter (tag00038)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of milk powder (tag00039)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of cheese (tag00040)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of milk on farms (tag00041)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions (tgs00046)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of meat: pigs (tag00042)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of meat: cattle (tag00044)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of meat: sheep and goats (tag00045)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Production of meat: poultry (tag00043)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Number of dairy cows (tag00014)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Number of bovine animals (tag00016)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Number of sheep (tag00017)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Number of pigs (tag00018)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Animal populations by NUTS 2 regions (tgs00045)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Area under organic farming (sdg_02_40)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Agriculture (agr)	Organic crop area (fully converted area) (tag00098)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Forestry (for)	Gross value added of the forestry industry, at basic prices (tag00058)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Forestry (for)	Roundwood production (tag00072)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Forestry (for)	Total sawnwood production (tag00073)
Eurostat (TB by themes)	Forestry (for)	Total paper and paperboard production (tag00074)
database by themes	Environment	Air emissions accounts by NACE Rev. 2 activity
database by themes	Environment	Air emissions intensities by NACE Rev. 2 activity
database by themes	Environment	Environmental taxes by economic activity (NACE Rev. 2)
database by themes	Environment	Generation and discharge of wastewater by pollutant

3.2 Characterisation within the project duration

During Task 1.1, project partners performed an initial characterisation of a number of datasets (listed in the table in Selection of Datasets Characterised so Far of D1.1) to identify the information that had to be captured by the ARDIT ontology and defined the necessary information required for further characterisation in ARDIT.

Consequently, the ARDIT back end has been organised in 7 sections:

1. One **GENERAL** section where information such as the name of the table, the description, the type of dataset, the producer, issue date and last update, etc., are captured. In this category, the user can indicate the catalogue to which the dataset belongs (Eurostat, FAO, OECD, etc ...). Spatial resolution is a characteristic dedicated to geo-referenced datasets to depict the minimum spatial separation resolvable in a dataset, measured in meters, while temporal

resolution is intended to provide a summary indication of the temporal resolution of the data distribution as a single value. More complex descriptions of various aspects of temporal precision, accuracy, resolution and other statistics can be provided using the Data Quality Vocabulary [VOCAB-DQV]⁵. In these sections, we can also find the activities that generated or provided the business context for the creation of the dataset ("Was generated by"). An activity is something that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities; it may include consuming, processing, transforming, modifying, relocating, using, or generating entities. The activity associated with the generation of a dataset will typically be an initiative, project, mission, survey, ongoing activity ("business as usual") etc.

Ultimately, if the dataset is cited in the literature, or on other datasets or used by some other related resources, such as publications, etc., this information can be depicted in the field "Is referenced by".

2. The second section is dedicated to the **PURPOSE** of the dataset and defines what kind of analysis the dataset was created for. The purpose property has been added in the AGRICORE ontology and it identifies the purpose of the dataset, i.e., for what kind of analysis that dataset has been created: there is an internal vocabulary of terms that will be enriched over time. In this section, we find information on the temporal extent of the data collection period, on the object of the dataset (i.e., the type of data that has been analysed and represented), on the purposes of the dataset and the data, and on the theme covered (derived from DCAT-AP).
3. The **GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE** section depicts the geographic features of a dataset. It's a spatial property. It's a list of spatial regions or named places. It can be represented using a controlled vocabulary or with geographic coordinates.
4. The **DISTRIBUTION** of a data set is the format in which the data can be retrieved. A dataset might be available in multiple formats, such as spreadsheet, pdf, CSV, etc. This section, besides information on the title, issue date and description, collects all data on access rights, byte size, procedures to access the data, URL and format.
5. The **UNIT OF ANALYSIS** (UoA) is the object to which the variables are referred. Every dataset has at least one UoA, but in one dataset there could be more than one UoA. The UoA is generally something spatially defined, such as the holdings, a region or a country, but it can also be something different such as a commodity. While defining a new Unit of Analysis, the following information will be captured: the temporal extent (that could have a different value from one of the datasets), the aggregation level, unit or scale, whether the dataset is a census, the population coverage if not a census, the statistical representativeness, the number of UoA in the sample (if known) and the downscaling strategy (if any).
6. Once the UoA has been created, the related variables are characterised through: unit of measurement, temporal extent, mathematical representation, data frequency, aggregation level and UoA to which the variable refers. In the case of price variables, currency, price type and size unit will be displayed as well.
7. In ARDIT there is also a section to list the **KEYWORDS** describing or representing the dataset.

Table 2 below depicts the list of fields to be filled while characterising a dataset in ARDIT.

⁵ https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/#Property:dataset_temporal_resolution

Table 2: Template for the ARDIT Dataset Characterisation (Methodological Grid)

Characteristic captured and presented in ARDIT	Explanation/Example
GENERAL	This section regards general information and characteristics about the dataset.
Title	Name or identifier of the dataset.
Description	Short description of the dataset, its purpose or the type of data collected.
Issued	Indicates the date of the first formal issuance or publication of the specific dataset.
Last update	Indicates the most recent date on which the dataset was changed, updated or modified.
Dataset type	A dataset can be either geo-referenced or socioeconomic. The dataset type is usually determined by the type of its Units of Analysis or the type of its variables.
Producer	Indicates the institution/organisation which generated, published or maintains the dataset.
Link	Provides an URL to the landing page of the described dataset.
Language	Indicates the original language in which the data and metadata are available
Periodicity of the publication	Indicates the frequency with which the data (variables) is updated (between one issue and the following one).
Catalogues	Indicates the catalogue to which the dataset belongs (if any).
Temporal resolution	Indicates the shortest period of time between two consecutive samples of any of the variables contained within the dataset.
Spatial resolution	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the smallest resolvable spatial separation (measured in metres) between neighbouring Units of Analysis, and thus between their corresponding geo-referenced variables.
Resource type	Indicates the nature or genre of the resource (e.g. collection, interactive resource)
Was generated by	Indicates the activities that generated or provided the business context for the creation of the dataset.
Is referenced by	Indicates other datasets or scientific publications that cite or (re)use data contained in the dataset being described.
PURPOSE	This section depicts what kind of analysis the dataset was created for.
Temporal extent	Indicates the time period for which data are available.
Subjects	Indicates the topics covered by the dataset.
Useful for the analysis of (purpose)	Indicates which types of analysis could be performed using the data contained in the dataset's variables.
Theme covered	Indicates the themes covered by the dataset.
GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE	This section describes the geographical scope of the dataset. It is therefore a property describing a particular physical or administrative spatial entity. It is possible to describe the geographical coverage using several alternatives (but only one of them at a time): list with 1+ physical continents <i>OR</i> list with 1+ countries <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS1 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS2 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS3 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ ADM1 geo-entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ ADM2 geo-entities. In future releases, it will be also possible to use a coordinates box for this.
DISTRIBUTIONS	The distributions of a dataset are the set of different formats/shapes in which the data can be retrieved. (e.g. pdf, CSV)
License	Indicates the legal framework under which the distribution is made available
Access right	Indicates a declaration on the rights that concerns how the distribution is accessed. (e.g. public, restricted)
Byte size	Indicates the memory size required to store the data contained in the dataset.
Procedures to access the data	Describes the guidelines and procedures required for accessing private datasets.
Access URL	Indicates the URL from where the data contained in the dataset can be accessed.
Download URL	Indicates the URL of the downloadable file in a given format (if exists).
Format	Indicates the file format of the raw data file (e.g. xls, csv, html, pc).
Compress format	Indicate the compression format (if any) of the downloadable file in which the data is contained.
Packaging format	Indicates the packaging format of the distribution when several data files are grouped together.

Data service	Indicates the data service that gives access to the distribution of the dataset.
Publisher	The entity responsible for making the data service available.
Creator	The entity responsible for producing the data service.
UNIT OF ANALYSIS	It's the object to which the variables refer. Every dataset has at least one UoA.
Area size	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the spatial magnitude of the unit of analysis.
Area size unit	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the physical unit corresponding to the magnitude of area size of the UoA.
Aggregation Level	Number of Units of Analysis for which the data is aggregated / Area size for which the Units of Analysis are aggregated.
Aggregation Level Unit	Political-Administrative or physical unit of the aggregation level (e.g. the Unit of Analysis can be the Agricultural Holdings, whose results are aggregated at a national (country) level).
Census	Boolean property that indicates whether the dataset is a census (100% of Units of Analysis were polled to gather the data).
Population coverage	Indicates (when known) the proportion of Units of Analysis sampled with respect to the size of the total population of Units of Analysis. Could be either a float between 0 and 1 or a percentage between 0 and 100.
Unit of analysis number	Indicates the total number of Units of Analysis that form the sample.
Statistical representativeness	Provides information on how the sample was built. It is a value between 0 and 1 that refers to what percentage of the total real population of units of analysis is represented by the sample used to generate the dataset.
Available stratification criteria & suggested downscaling methodologies	Indicates which additional stratification levels are resolvable within the dataset (i.e. the criteria to filter among Units of Analysis and their possible values). Additionally, for data available at higher (geographical or administrative) scale levels, methodologies can be suggested to generate data at smaller scales.
VARIABLES INCLUDED	It lists all the variables contained within the dataset. Those variables can be geo-referenced or socioeconomic, depending on the dataset and Unit of Analysis types.
Name	Identifier of the variable.
Unit of Measurement	Physical unit in which the variable is displayed.
Temporal extent	Indicates the time period for which data are available. Normally it has the same value as the dataset's temporal extent, but it might be also different (shorter) for some variables.
Mathematical representation	Indicates whether the value of the variable is an instantaneous value, or an extreme value (maximum, minimum), or the average of several values, etc.
Data frequency	To indicate the frequency with which data are collected and processed during the "temporal extent". (e.g.: dataset with two variables for temperature, one is the monthly average, another one is the maximum annual temperature)
Aggregation level	To indicate the spatial units of the data (e. g., NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3 or other administrative regions/units, 50000 (e.g., 1:50000 scale map), 0.25 degrees). It refers to the level of detail of the data set/ analysis. It shall be expressed as a set of zero to many resolution distances (typically for gridded data and imagery-derived products) or equivalent scales (typically for maps or map-derived products).
Data origin	Indicates whether the values of the variable have been obtained by actual physical measurements or surveys (measured), <i>OR</i> by qualitative observation (observed), <i>OR</i> by calculations on other raw variables (calculated), <i>OR</i> are predictions obtained using models or other forecasting techniques (forecast).
Reference Values	Sometimes variables are coded (or modified) using value identifiers generated by the dataset producers themselves. This property may include such codes and their meaning (or their modifying value) in natural language.
Unit of analysis	Indicates the UoA the variable is related to.
KEYWORDS	This section is to indicate the keywords regarding the dataset.

In this framework, STAM took care of keeping updated the ontology, while IDENER of communicating the required changes and adaptations both to the ARDIT developers and to the data providers (people performing the characterisations). UNIPR was in charge of the characterisation of the socioeconomic datasets, STAM was in charge of the characterisation of the geo-referenced datasets and IDENER took the role of supervisor and reviewer of the work done.

The list of datasets, characterised in the context of this deliverable, will be continuously updated throughout the project period to address any additional need, identified by the project modelers.

An iterative approach will allow maturing the governance structure aiming for its maintenance after the project finalisation. In the current stage, the AGRICORE partners have established that for each dataset to be included in the platform, a reviewer of the quality of its characterisation is defined.

During the project, an extensive list of characterization of the required datasets has been already produced. Nonetheless, as coordinator of the project, IDENER will be in charge of monitoring any additional data characterisation need identifying within the execution of the UCs. Any additional need will be notified by the UC responsible to the coordinator and the actions required to tackle it.

Finally, a special committee formed by representatives of STAM, UNIPR and IDENER will be formed. This Committee will be tasked with the continuous monitoring of the characterisation process, identifying the relevant aspects that may require a modification of the current ontology.

3.3 Characterisation challenges

One of the main challenges was to develop ARDIT as we went along with the characterisations so that it could adapt to the peculiarities of each dataset. On the other hand, this parallel effort allowed to exploit the possibilities provided by the tool for a more accurate characterisation for each dataset.

The first step in the characterisation exercise was to select a representative number of datasets. This selection was also a challenge in itself, as there are an extremely large number of datasets available that could be characterised, but the identification of the most appropriate ones was not immediate, as the development of the AGRICORE agent-based model is not yet completed and consequently the necessary inputs are not rigorously defined.

During the characterisation of the socio-economic dataset, another big challenge has been to identify the unit of analysis and the respective variables.

This issue has been seldom encountered while characterising the **Eurostat** datasets, where tables are static and there are no doubts on choosing which parameter. Furthermore, the information required for complete characterisation was available in a single page of each dataset.

In the **OECD** database, the major problem was finding the needed data, it is not a very intuitive database. Tables are dynamic and more difficult to characterise. It was not clear how to define the unit of analysis (e.g: doubts rose whether choosing countries or other parameters). Sometimes units of analysis and variables were mixed up, in other cases the number of units of analysis and variables was very large, making the characterisation process long and tedious. For some datasets, there were different parameters to visualize the table, and it was difficult to define which was the best characterisation option.

The **FAO** database is huge and full of data, but not complicated. The only problem encountered was that, in some datasets, there were not available data for some countries, variables, or units of analysis. The parameters selected for the visualization had to be constantly changed because FAO tables are dynamic and depend on the option chosen.

3.4 Characterisation after the project

Upon completing the activities of the AGRICORE project and having published the ARDIT on the public internet, researchers interested in using and contributing to the tool with the characterisation of new datasets will be able to do so by means of the same functionality employed by project partners in the lifetime of the project. It is obvious that for ensuring the survival of the developed portal, a continuous upgrade and maintenance of the data included should be promoted. To do so, a clear governance structure should be defined.

Although the final version of such governance will be established later in the project (as this relies on the activities pertaining to other WPs and tasks, such as WP8, Exploitation, clustering and open sourcing, and WP9 with the PEDR and DMP), an initial potential governance structure is already under discussion.

The ARDIT tool will be developed to include a Datasource life cycle management system. This system, among other things, will establish a set of roles within the platform which will be linked to specific responsibilities. The corresponding roles will be defined within the project by both AAT and IDENER and the people assigned with them will be identified; initially within the personnel of such companies. However, project activities already include efforts to increase the adoption and interest in the project tools (including ARDIT) and external requests from potential contributors are expected.

4 Conclusion

Agricultural research and agricultural policy impact assessment is normally supported by the analysis of several datasets with different characteristics and their own complexity. Some datasets are statistically oriented (such as Eurostat), following the evolution of statistical macroeconomics phenomena by giving a structural or cognitive overview. They might be used to make a forecast analysis (ex-ante analysis) or a policy evaluation (ex-post). Some other datasets are policy-oriented (such as FADN), providing specific information for policymakers and for specific policy sectors (fisheries, environment, agriculture etc.). Such datasets can be implemented by governments or international organisations oriented towards specific objectives, such as the fight against world hunger, rural development, etc. Therefore, datasets are created for a specific purpose and follow specific generation methodologies. A dataset must allow researchers to obtain information in the most efficient way, timely and functionally. To that end, it should contain those variables that are most common or most widely used, using appropriate units of analysis and standardised units of measurement. But it should also ensure that the information on these and other characteristics (the dataset metadata) is publicly available and easily interpretable by researchers during the phase of identifying and searching for relevant data. The tools to reach this objective are the ontologies, which allow a common way of conceptualising the characteristics of datasets, allowing easy extraction of metadata and grouping of datasets with similar properties. The quality and usefulness of these datasets descriptions depend on the quality and efficiency of the ontologies used by researchers as a basis to characterise them.

In the scope of the AGRICORE project, a new dedicated ontology (AGRICORE DCAT 2.0) was designed to capture the information needed down to the level of the variables. This ontology constitutes the base for the structural design of the Agricultural Research Data Index Tool (ARDIT), a web-based tool that allows the characterisation of agricultural datasets and their subsequent search and query.

In task 1.3, 71 Tables of the Eurostat database, 34 tables of the OECD, 48 tables of FAOstat and the FADN have been characterised. These characterisations have been included as an ANNEX to this deliverable. Additionally, the [JSON file](#) containing all the characterisations corresponding to tasks T1.3, T1.4, T1.5 and T1.6 of the AGRICORE Project has been uploaded to ZENODO⁶.

Characterisations of datasets are the result of human-made decision processes based on human-designed ontologies. Therefore, every characterisation is a dynamic outcome subject to modifications, either because someone else suggests a better way of describing some of its properties using the ontology, or because the ontology itself undergoes modifications to improve the way of describing certain characteristic(s). Therefore, there must be an overall process management approach to ensure the quality of the resulting products (the characterisations), i.e. the ability to keep useful and accurate information about the datasets and to access it easily and quickly. The former will be included as part of the ARDIT design to be submitted in M31. Furthermore, a governance structure for the ARDIT itself is important to guarantee the quality of the characterisation procedures during the project phase, but also to ensure proper management, information provisioning and tool maintenance in the future post-project stage.

⁶ [Zenodo](#) is a general purpose open access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and operated by CERN.

5 References

For preparing this report, the following deliverables have been taken into consideration:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due date
D1.1	Standardised Methodology and Set of Ontologies for the Characterisation of Data Sources	UNIPR	Report	Public	M09
D1.4	Geo-referenced datasets	STAM	Report	Public	M29
D1.5	National and Regional datasets	UNIPR	Report	Public	M29
D1.6	Previous research results as information sources	UNIPR	Report	Public	M29

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FAO - ASTI-Expenditures

General information

Description: ASTI collects primary time-series data on agricultural research capacity and spending levels through national survey rounds in over 80 low-and middle-income countries.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AE>

Languages: English

Catalogue: ASTI R&D Indicators

Subjects: agricultural research, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: ASTI (www.asti.cgiar.org/data)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Argentina, Antigua and Barbuda, Burundi, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Belize, Brazil, Barbados, Botswana, Central African Republic, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Congo, Colombia, Cabo Verde, Costa Rica, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Grenada, Guatemala, Honduras, Indonesia, India, Iran, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Cambodia, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Saint Lucia, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Morocco, Madagascar, Mexico, Mali, Mozambique, Mauritania, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Namibia, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Nepal, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Philippines, Papua New Guinea, Paraguay, Rwanda, Sudan, Senegal, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, Eswatini, Chad, Togo, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Tanzania, Uganda, Uruguay, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Democratic Republic of Vietnam, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 11, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1981 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AE	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AE	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Share of Value Added (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	January, 1981 - December, 2016	Country	95	
Spending, total	January, 1981 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agriculture research spending	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage/million PPP (constant 2011 prices)	January, 1981 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of Value Added (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing), Spending, total

FAO - ASTI-Researchers

General information

Description: ASTI collects primary time-series data on agricultural research capacity and spending levels through national survey rounds in over 80 low-and middle-income countries.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AF>

Languages: English

Catalogue: ASTI R&D Indicators

Subjects: agricultural research, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: ASTI (www.asti.cgiar.org/data)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Argentina, Antigua and Barbuda, Burundi, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Belize, Brazil, Barbados, Botswana, Central African Republic, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Congo, Colombia, Cabo Verde, Costa Rica, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Grenada, Guatemala, Honduras, Indonesia, India, Iran, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Cambodia, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Saint Lucia, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Morocco, Madagascar, Mexico, Mali, Myanmar/Burma, Mozambique, Mauritania, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Namibia, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Nepal, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Philippines, Papua New Guinea, Paraguay, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, South Sudan, Eswatini, Chad, Togo, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Tanzania, Uganda, Uruguay, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Democratic Republic of Vietnam, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 11, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1981 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AF	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/AF	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Per 100,000 farmers	January, 1981 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Researchers, total	January, 1981 - December, 2016	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agricultural researchers	Socioeconomic variable	FTE	January, 1981 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Researchers, total, Per 100,000 farmers

EUROSTAT - Animal populations by NUTS 2 regions

General information

Description: This dataset shows the animal populations in different countries and regions.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, slaughter of animals, population census, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: YEARS

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
csv	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
tsv	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
sdmx	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Live animals	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis

[A4200] Live goats	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2000] Live bovine animals	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2230_2330] Female bovine animals, 2 years old or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2230_2330] Female bovine animals, 2 years old or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2220] Heifers, 1 to less than 2 years old	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2220B] Heifers, 1 year old, for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2220C] Heifers, 1 year old, not for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2230] Heifers, 2 years old or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2230B] Heifers, 2 years old or over, for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2230C] Heifers, 2 years	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals

old or over, not for slaughter						
[A2300] Cows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4210KB] Goats having already kidded	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4220] Other goats	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2300F] Dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2300G] Non dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2400] Buffaloes	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2410] Breeding female buffaloes	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2420] Other buffaloes	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3100] Live swine, domestic species	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3110] Piglets, live weight of under 20 kg	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3120_3133] Breeding pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3120] Breeding sows,	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals

live weight 50 kg or over						
[A3120K] Covered sows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3120KA] Sows covered for the first time	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3120L] Sows, not covered	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3120LA] Gilts not yet covered	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3131] Pigs, from 20 kg to less than 50 kg	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3132] Fattening pigs, live weight 50 kg or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3132X] Fattening pigs, from 50 kg to less than 80 kg	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3132Y] Fattening pigs, from 80 kg to less than 110 kg	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A3132Z] Fattening pigs, live weight 110 kg or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals

[A3133] Breeding boars	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4100] Live sheep	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4110K] Ewes and ewe-lambs put to the ram	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4110KC] Milk ewes and ewe- lambs put to the ram	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4110KD] Non milk ewes and ewe-lambs put to the ram	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4120] Other sheep	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4210K] Goats mated and having already kidded	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A4210KA] Goats mated for the first time	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2010] Bovine animals, less than 1 year old	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2010B] Bovine animals, less than 1 year old, for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals

[A2010C] Bovine animals, less than 1 year old, not for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2020] Bovine animals, 1 to less than 2 years old	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2030] Bovine animals, 2 years old or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2110C] Male calves, less than 1 year old, not for slaughter	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals
[A2120] Male bovine animals, 1 to less than 2 years old	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live animals

FAO - Crop Residues

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT domain Crop Residues contains estimates of nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from the decomposition of nitrogen in crop residues left on managed soils.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GA>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Climate Change

Subjects: crop production, soil pollution, atmospheric pollution, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Air emissions intensities

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Excel (xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GA	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Beans, dry	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Maize	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Millet	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Wheat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Barley	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Rye	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Soybeans	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Oats	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Sorghum	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Potatoes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Rice, paddy	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Residues (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg of nutrients	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Barley, Beans, dry, Maize, Millet, Oats, Potatoes, Rice, paddy, Rye, Sorghum, Soybeans, Wheat
Direct emissions (N ₂ O)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Barley, Beans, dry, Maize, Millet, Oats, Potatoes, Rice, paddy, Rye, Sorghum, Soybeans, Wheat
Indirect emissions (N ₂ O)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Barley, Beans, dry, Maize, Millet, Oats, Potatoes, Rice, paddy, Rye, Sorghum, Soybeans, Wheat
Emissions (N ₂ O)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Barley, Beans, dry, Maize, Millet, Oats, Potatoes, Rice, paddy, Rye, Sorghum, Soybeans, Wheat

FAO - Livestock Patterns

General information

Description: The Livestock Patterns domain of the FAOSTAT Agri-Environmental Indicators contains data on livestock numbers, shares of major livestock species and livestock densities in the agricultural land area. Values are calculated using Livestock Units (LSU), which facilitate aggregating information for different livestock types. Data are available by country, with global coverage, for the period 1961 to present, with annual updates. This methodology applies the LSU coefficients reported in the "Guidelines for the preparation of livestock sector reviews" (FAO, 2011). From this publication, LSU coefficients are computed by livestock type and by country. The reference unit used for the calculation of livestock units (=1 LSU) is the grazing equivalent of one adult dairy cow producing 3000 kg of milk annually, fed without additional concentrated foodstuffs. FAOSTAT agri-environmental indicators on livestock patterns closely follow the structure of the indicators in EUROSTAT.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EK/metadata>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords: farm work

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EK/metadata	CSV	False
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EK/metadata	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Camels	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Asses	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	

Chickens	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Mules	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Cattle	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	
Pigs	January, 1961 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Livestock per agricultural land area	Socioeconomic variable	LSU/ha	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Asses, Camels, Cattle, Chickens, Goats, Buffaloes, Horses, Mules, Pigs, Sheep
Share in total livestock	Socioeconomic variable	% of total LSU	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Asses, Camels, Cattle, Chickens, Goats, Buffaloes, Horses, Mules, Pigs, Sheep
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units (LSU)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Asses, Camels, Cattle, Chickens, Goats, Buffaloes, Horses, Mules, Pigs, Sheep

FAO - Manure left on Pasture

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT domain Manure left on pasture consists of nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from nitrogen of manure left by grazing livestock on pasture.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Emissions

Subjects: emission trading, greenhouse gas, Environment, Soil, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT domains Production/Live animals

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 17, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Ducks	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, broilers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, breeding	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Turkeys	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Camels	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, market	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Asses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, non-dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, layers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Llamas	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Mules	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Manure (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses

Emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Indirect emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Direct emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses

FAO - Trade - Crops and livestock products

General information

Description: Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Primary, Cereals, Coarse Grain, Citrus Fruit, Fruit, Jute Jute-like Fibres, Oilcakes Equivalent, Oil crops Primary, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts and Vegetables and Melons. Data are expressed in terms of area harvested, production quantity and yield. The objective is to comprehensively cover production of all primary crops for all countries and regions in the world.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TCL>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Trade

Subjects: trade balance, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Price policy, Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: January 10, 2022

Issued:

Last update: December 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet (XLS)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TCL	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TCL	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Crops and livestock products	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Live Animals	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Crops and livestock products, Live Animals
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Crops and livestock products, Live Animals
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live Animals, Crops and livestock products

Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Live Animals, Crops and livestock products
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OECD - Monitoring and evaluation : Reference Tables

General information

Description: This dataset and predefined summary tables are a complement to the report Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation 2021, which monitors agricultural policy developments.

The OECD uses a comprehensive system for measuring and classifying support to agriculture - the Producer and Consumer Support Estimates (PSEs and CSEs) and related indicators. They provide insight into the increasingly complex nature of agricultural policy and serve as a basis for OECD's work on agricultural policies.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_REFERENCE_TABLE#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: agricultural policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: collected from agricultural and other relevant ministries of participating countries,

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 23, 2021

Issued:
Last update: June 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1986 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_REFERENCE_TABLE#	XML	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_REFERENCE_TABLE#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_REFERENCE_TABLE#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_REFERENCE_TABLE#	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country policies	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Proportion of support with input constraints	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Agricultural employment	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Most distorting support as % of PSE	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Contribution to change in PSE by country	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Total Support Estimate (share of all country TSE)	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
General Services Support Estimate (share of all country GSSE)	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Producer Support Estimate (share of all country TSE)	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies

Contribution to change in PSE by country	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
% change PSE from the current year to last year	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Contribution to change in PSE of Market price support	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Contribution of change in PSE of budgetary payments	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Share of agriculture in GDP	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Gross Farm Receipts (GFR)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
GDP deflator	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Producer Single Commodity Transfers	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
General Services Support Estimate (GSSE)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Producer Nominal Assistance Coefficient (coeff.)	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies

Producer Nominal Protection Coefficient (coeff.)	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Consumer Support Estimate (CSE)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Consumer NAC (coeff.)	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Consumer NPC (coeff.)	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Total Support Estimate (TSE)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Excess feed cost	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Proportion of support not requiring production	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Total value of production (at farm gate)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Total value of consumption (at farm gate)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Producer Support Estimate (PSE)	Socioeconomic variable	USD millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies
Proportion of support with	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country policies

output and payment limits						
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OECD - Environmental Policy Stringency Index

General information

Description: The OECD Environmental Policy Stringency Index (EPS) is a country-specific and internationally-comparable measure of the stringency of environmental policy. Stringency is defined as the degree to which environmental policies put an explicit or implicit price on polluting or environmentally harmful behaviour. The index ranges from 0 (not stringent) to 6 (highest degree of stringency). The index covers 28 OECD and 6 BRIICS countries for the period 1990-2012. The index is based on the degree of stringency of 14 environmental policy instruments, primarily related to climate and air pollution.

Producer: OECD

Link: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EPS>

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: environmental policy, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: The dedicated website: <http://oe.cd/OQ>

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, China, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States, South Africa

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 2, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 2, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2015

Keywords: environment, index

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EPS	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EPS	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EPS	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=EPS	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Environmental policy stringency	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Market EPS	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Taxes	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Tax CO2	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Tax Diesel	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Tax NOx	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Tax SOx	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Trading schemes	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Feed-in Tariffs	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Non-market EPS	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Standards	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
Emission limit values	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
R&D subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index

Renewable energy public RD&D budget	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Countries' Environmental Policy Stringency Index
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FAO - Manure applied to Soils

General information

Description: GHG emissions from manure applied to soils consist of direct and indirect nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from nitrogen (N) of manure added to agricultural soils.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Emissions

Subjects: emission trading, greenhouse gas, Environment, Soil, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT domains Production/Live animals

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GU	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Ducks	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, broilers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, breeding	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Turkeys	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Camels	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, market	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Asses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, non-dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, layers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Llamas	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Mules	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Manure (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses

Emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Indirect emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses
Direct emissions (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/kg/kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Turkeys , Swine, market, Swine, breeding, Sheep, Mules, Llamas, Horses, Goats, Ducks, Chickens, layers, Chickens, broilers, Cattle, non-dairy, Cattle, dairy, Camels, Buffaloes, Asses

FAO - Livestock Manure

General information

Description: The Livestock Manure domain under the FAOSTAT section of Agri-Environmental Indicators contains estimates of nitrogen (N) inputs to agricultural soils from livestock manure. Data on the N losses to air and water are also disseminated. These estimates are compiled using official FAOSTAT statistics of animal stocks and by applying the internationally approved Guidelines of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Data are available by country, with global coverage and relative to the period 1961–2018, with annual updates.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EMN/metadata>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: livestock farming, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: livestock farming value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords: manure, livestock

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EMN/metadata	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EMN/metadata	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, diary	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, non-diary	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, broilers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chickens, layers	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Ducks	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, breeding	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Amount excreted in manure (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Head	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure left on pasture (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure left on pasture that volatilises (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure treated (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding

Manure left on pasture that leaches (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Losses from manure treated (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure applied to soils (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure applied to soils that volatilises (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding
Manure applied to soils that leaches (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Cattle, diary, Cattle, non-diary, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Sheep, Swine, breeding

OECD - Greenhouse gas emissions

General information

Description: This dataset presents trends in man-made emissions of major greenhouse gases and emissions by gas.

Data refer to total emissions of CO₂, CH₄ (methane), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃). Datas' table also contains percentages of values.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AIR_GHG#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: greenhouse gas, Environment, Atmospheric conditions

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions, Pollutant Gases

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Inventory Submissions 2021 to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, CRF tables), OECD State of the Environment Questionnaire.

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:
Last update: September 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AIR_GHG#	SDMX	False
pc-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AIR_GHG#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (csv)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AIR_GHG#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AIR_GHG#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Greenhouse gases	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Carbon dioxide	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Methane	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Nitrous oxide	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Unspecified mix of HFCs and PFCs	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Hydrofluorocarbons	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Perfluorocarbons	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Sulphur hexafluoride	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	
Nitrogen trifluoride	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Energy industries	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Manufacturing industries and construction	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Transport	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Residential and other sectors	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Energy-other	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Fugitive Emissions from Fuels	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases

CO2 from Transport and Storage	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Industrial processes and product use	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Waste	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Other	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total emissions including LULUCF	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total GHG excl. LULUCF per capita	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total GHG excl. LULUCF per unit of GDP	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total GHG incl. LULUCF per capita	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total GHG incl. LULUCF per	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases

unit of GDP Unit						
Total GHG excl. LULUCF, Index 2000=100	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases
Total GHG excl. LULUCF, Index 1990=100	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Greenhouse gases

EUROSTAT - Livestock density index

General information

Description: The livestock density index provides the number of livestock units (LSU) per hectare of utilised agricultural area. The LSU is a reference unit which facilitates the aggregation of livestock from various species and ages. The Eurofarm LSU coefficients, which are at the basis of this indicator, are established by convention (originally, they were related to the animals' feed requirements, the reference being a dairy cow with an annual yield of 3000 kg milk, without additional concentrated feedingstuffs). In the interpretation of the livestock density index, the limits of this theoretical unit are to be taken into account. The livestock species aggregated in the LSU total, for the purpose of this indicator, are: equidae, cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, poultry and rabbits.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tai09/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock farming, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 22, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tai09/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tai09/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tai09/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2005 - December, 2016	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Livestock density index	Socioeconomic variable	number of livestock units (LSU) per hectare of utilised agricultural area	January, 2005 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

FAO - Government Expenditure

General information

Description: The FAO dataset consists of a time series, from 2001 onwards, of Total Government Expenditure and expenditure in: Economic affairs; Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing and Hunting, along with its three disaggregated subsectors of Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing; and Environmental Protection.

Producer: FAO - IMF

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/IG>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Investment

Subjects: investment, EU expenditure, agricultural expenditure, Economy and finance, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Government Expenditure, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: Questionnaire developed in partnership with the International Monetary Fund (IMF)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 30, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2001 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/IG	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/IG	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Central Government	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Country		
General Government	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Fishing, Recurrent	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Fishing, Capital	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
R&D Agriculture, forestry, fishing	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government

Environmental protection	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Total Expenditure	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture, forestry, fishing Expenditure	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture, forestry, fishing, Recurrent	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture, forestry, fishing, Capital	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture Expenditure	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture, Recurrent	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Agriculture, Capital	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Forestry Expenditure	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Forestry, Recurrent	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Forestry, Capital	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government
Fishing Expenditure	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 2001 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Central Government, General Government

FAO - Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

General information

Description: FDI is an investment which aims to acquire a lasting management influence (10 percent or more of the voting stock) in an enterprise operating in a foreign economy. FDI may be undertaken by individuals, as well as business entities. The foreign direct investor most often is aiming to gain access to natural resources, to markets, to labour supply, to technology, to ensure security of supplies or to control the quality of a certain product. FDI can be decomposed into two types of investments: mergers and acquisitions (MA) and greenfield investments.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FDI>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Investment

Subjects: foreign investment, investment policy, Economy and finance, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:
Last update: December 18, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1991 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FDI	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FDI	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
FDI inflows to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
FDI inflows to Food, Beverages and Tobacco	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

Total FDI inflows	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
FDI outflows to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
FDI outflows to Food, Beverages and Tobacco	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Total FDI outflows	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

EUROSTAT - Gross value added of the agricultural industry - basic and producer prices

General information

Description: Gross value added at basic prices corresponds to the value of output (at basic prices) less the value of intermediate consumption. The basic price is defined as the price received by the producer, after deduction of all taxes on products but including all subsidies on products. The definition of the agricultural industry is based on Division 01 of NACE Rev. 1.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00056/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agro-industry, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, production value, agro-industry value added

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00056/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00056/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00056/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production value at producer price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production value at basic price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

FAO - Deflators

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT Deflators database provides the following selection of implicit price deflator series by country and at regional level: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) deflator, Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) deflator, Agriculture, Forestry, Fishery Value-Added (VA_AFF) deflator, and Manufacturing Valued-Added (VA_MAN) deflator. A deflator is a figure expressing the change in prices over a period of time for a product or a basket of products by comparing a reference period to a base period. It is obtained by dividing a current price value of a given aggregate by its real counterpart. When calculated from the major national accounting aggregates such as GDP or agriculture VA, implicit price deflators pertains to wider ranges of goods and services in the economy than that represented by any of the individual price indexes (such as CPIs, PPIs).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PD>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Prices

Subjects: economic statistics, economic indicator, Economy and finance, Business, statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 27, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PD	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PD	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
GDP Deflator	Socioeconomic variable	Value Local Currency, 2015 prices	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added Deflator (Manufacturing)	Socioeconomic variable	Value Local Currency, 2015 prices	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

Value Added Deflator (Agriculture, forestry and fishery)	Socioeconomic variable	Value Local Currency, 2015 prices	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Gross Fixed Capital Formation Deflator	Socioeconomic variable	Value Local Currency, 2015 prices	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

EUROSTAT - Utilised agricultural area by categories

General information

Description: The Utilised agricultural area (abbreviated as UAA) describes the area used for farming. It includes the following land categories: •arable land; •permanent grassland; •permanent crops; •other agricultural land such as kitchen gardens (even if they only represent small areas of total UAA). The term does not include unused agricultural land, woodland and land occupied by buildings, farmyards, tracks, ponds, etc. This indicator uses the concept of "main area" that means the area of the land parcel: •in case of annual crops, the main area correspond to the sown area; •in the case of permanent crops, to the total planted area; •in the case of successive crops, to the main crop that occupied the parcel during that year; •and in the case of simultaneous crops, to the corresponding area of the different crops.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00025/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: land use, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00025/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00025/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00025/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Utilised agricultural area	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Permanent grassland	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Kitchen gardens	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area

EUROSTAT - Collection of cow's milk

General information

Description: Data covers cow's milk collected in farms by approved dairies. A distinction should be made between "milk collected by dairies" and "milk production on the farm". Milk collection is only a part of the total use of milk production on the farm. The other part of the use of milk produced on the farm generally includes domestic consumption, direct sale and cattle feed.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00037/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: milk, milk product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Collection

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00037/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00037/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00037/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Collection of milk	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

EUROSTAT - Fresh vegetables and strawberries by area

General information

Description: This table includes the areas of all brassicas, leafy and stalked vegetables, vegetables cultivated for fruit, root, tuber and bulb vegetables, fresh pulses, other vegetables harvested fresh (not dry), including melons, and strawberries grown on arable land outdoor in rotation with other agricultural or horticultural crops and under glass or high accessible cover. This indicator uses the concepts of "harvested area". The "harvested area" corresponds to the total sown area for the production of a specific crop during the same year (i.e. the sum of the areas sown and harvested more than once in the same year) excluding the non-harvested area. For instance, radishes have a cropping time of between 4 and 6 weeks. If 1 ha is sown and harvested four times, within the same year, and all the sown area is harvested except the last one, where only 80% of the field is harvested, then the harvested area will be 3,8 hectares (4 hectares minus non harvested area 0,2 hectares).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00115/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: vegetable, land use, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Agriculture policy, land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00115/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00115/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00115/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land with Fresh vegetables (including melons) and strawberries	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with Tomatoes	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with Cucumbers	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with Carrots	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with Onions	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area

OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 1990-2030

General information

Description: This tool dataset is a limited version of the database presented in the OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2021-2030. For most of the commodity markets analysed in the Outlook, detailed supply and use balances are available, as well as domestic and international commodity prices.

For OECD countries, the data is accompanied by detailed metadata. In most cases the data is going back to 1990 and extended to the latest year in the projections (currently 2030).

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=HIGH_AGLINK_2021

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: agricultural product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: October 4, 2021

Issued: July 1, 2021

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2030

Keywords: agricultural outlook

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Ethanol	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
White sugar	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Poultry meat	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Eggs	December, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Milk	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fresh dairy products	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Butter	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		

Cheese	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Skim milk powder	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Whey powder	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Pulses	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country	100	
Fertilizer	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country	100	
Wheat	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country	100	
Casein	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Biodiesel	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fish	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fish from capture	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fish from aquaculture	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fish meal	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Whole milk powder	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Fish oil	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Oil	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		

Soybean	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Agricultural sector	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Total	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
High fructose corn syrup	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Sugar beet	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Sugar cane	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Molasses	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Beef and veal	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Pigmeat	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Cotton	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Roots and tuberes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Maize	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Other coarse grains	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Rice	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Distiller's dry grains	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		

Other oilseeds	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Protein meals	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Vegetable oils	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Sugar	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Raw sugar	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country		
Sheepmeat	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, vegetables oils, Sugar, Raw sugar, Molasses, White sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, beef and veal, Pigmeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Milk, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol, Biodiesel, Fish, Fish from aquaculture, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pules
Ethanol production from commodity	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains

Biodiesel production from commodity	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Vegetables oils
Imports	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetables oils, Sugar, Raw sugar, White sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol , Biodiesel, Fish, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Whole milk powder
Consumption	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetables oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol , Biodiesel, Fish, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
Exports	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetables oils, Sugar, Raw sugar, White sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol , Biodiesel, Fish, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Whole milk powder

Ending stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetables oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Ethanol , Biodiesel
Trade balance	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	White sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol , Biodiesel, Fish, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Whole milk powder, Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetables oils, Sugar, Raw sugar
Area harvested	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
Cow inventory	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Beef and veal, Milk
Crush	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Soybean, Other oilseeds, Fish
Food	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetable oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Beef and veal, Piguemeat, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder,

						Whey powder, Casein, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
Biofuel use	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains, Vegetable oils, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, Molasses, Roots and tuberes
Feed	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Molasses, Skim milk powder, Whey powder, Fish meal, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
Other use	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand of tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, Roots and tuberes, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Vegetable oils, Sugar, Molasses, Eggs, Whey powder, Fish, Pulses
Yeld	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes per hectare	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, Beef and veal, Milk, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
World Price	Price variable	USD per tonne	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Distiller's dry grains, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Protein meals, Vegetable oils, Raw sugar, White sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Molasses, Beef and veal, Pigmear, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Ethanol , Biodiesel, Fish, Fish from capture, Fish from acquaculture, Fish meal, Fish oil, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Fertilizer, Oil

Human consumption per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Kilograms per capita	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Vegetable oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Beef and veal, Piguement, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Fish, Roots and tuberes, Pulses
Direct GHG emission	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, maize, Others coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Sugar beet, Sugar cane, Beef and veal, Piguement, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Milk, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Casein, Cotton, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Agricultural sector
Total calorie availability	Socioeconomic variable	Kcal/person/day	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Vegetable oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Beef and veal, Piguement, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Fish, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Total
Food protein availability	Socioeconomic variable	g/person/day	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Vegetable oils, Sugar, High fructose corn syrup, Beef and veal, Piguement, Poultry meat, Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Whey powder, Fish, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Total
Food fat availability	Socioeconomic variable	g/person/day	January, 1990 - December, 2030	Instant value	Annual	Wheat, Maize, Other coarse grains, Rice, Soybean, Other oilseeds, Vegetable oils, Beef and veal, Piguement, Poultry meat,

						Sheepmeat, Eggs, Fresh dairy products, Butter, Cheese, Skim milk powder, Whole milk powder, Fish, Roots and tuberes, Pulses, Total
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FAO - Exchange rates - Annual

General information

Description: Exchange rates are defined as the price of one country's currency in relation to another, and can be: i) a market rate in which the rate floats and is determined largely by market forces; ii) an official rate, as determined or announced by national authorities (typically the central bank); and iii) the principal, secondary, or tertiary rate, for countries maintaining multiple exchange arrangements. In this domain, exchange rates are provided in terms of Standard Local Currency (SLC) per US dollar, where SLC refers to the currency used in the most recent reference year of the statistical reference period covered. For example, the "euro" is the SLC for Italy from 1970 to 2016, as it was the currency used by Italy in the 2019 reference year, though the Lire was the actual currency used, or local currency unit (LCU), for 1970 to 1998, while the euro was the LCU for Italy from 1999 to the present.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PE>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Prices

Subjects: economic indicator, economic statistics, Business, statistics, Economy and finance, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 14, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	http://www.fao.org/docrep/019/i3664e/i3664e.pdf	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	http://www.fao.org/docrep/019/i3664e/i3664e.pdf	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1970 - December, 2020	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Exchange rates	Socioeconomic variable	Standard local currency units per USD	January, 1970 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Country
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FAO - Forestry production and trade

General information

Description: The database contains data on the production and trade in roundwood and in primary wood and paper products for all countries and territories in the world. The main types of primary forest products included in this database are roundwood, sawnwood, wood-based panels, pulp, and paper and paperboard.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FO>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: forestry statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Forestry output

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: August 12, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2020

Keywords: exports, production, imports

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/FO	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/FO	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Roundwood	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Wood pulp	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Paper and paperboard	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production)	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Forest products (export/import)	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Fibreboard	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		

Other industrial roundwood	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Roundwood, non-coniferous	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Wood fuel	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Industrial roundwood	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Roundwood, coniferous	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Wood-based panels	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Pulp for paper	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Industrial roundwood, coniferous	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997)	January, 1961 - December, 1997	Country		
Wood chips, particles and residues	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Wood pellets and other agglomerates	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Sawlogs and veneer logs	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Sawnwood	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Total fibre furnish	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		

Graphic papers	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		
Packaging paper and paperboard	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood, Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production), Other industrial roundwood, Wood pulp, Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp, Paper and paperboard, Forest products (export/import), Fibreboard, Roundwood, coniferous, Roundwood, non-coniferous, Wood fuel, Industrial roundwood, Wood-based panels, Pulp for paper, Industrial roundwood, coniferous , Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous, Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997) , Wood chips, particles and residues , Wood pellets and other agglomerates, Sawlogs and veneer logs, Sawnwood, Total fibre furnish , Graphic papers, Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint , Packaging paper and paperboard
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Pulp for paper, Industrial roundwood, coniferous , Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous, Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997) , Wood chips, particles and residues , Wood pellets and other agglomerates, Sawlogs and veneer logs, Sawnwood, Total fibre furnish , Graphic papers, Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint ,

						Packaging paper and paperboard , Roundwood, Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production), Other industrial roundwood, Wood pulp, Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp, Paper and paperboard, Forest products (export/import), Fibreboard, Roundwood, coniferous, Roundwood, non-coniferous, Wood fuel, Industrial roundwood, Wood-based panels
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood, Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production), Other industrial roundwood, Wood pulp, Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp, Paper and paperboard, Forest products (export/import), Fibreboard, Roundwood, coniferous, Roundwood, non-coniferous, Wood fuel, Industrial roundwood, Wood-based panels, Pulp for paper, Industrial roundwood, coniferous , Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous, Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997) , Wood chips, particles and residues , Wood pellets and other agglomerates, Sawlogs and veneer logs, Sawnwood, Total fibre furnish , Graphic papers, Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint , Packaging paper and paperboard
Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood, Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production), Other industrial roundwood, Wood pulp, Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp, Paper and paperboard, Forest products (export/import), Fibreboard, Roundwood, coniferous, Roundwood, non-coniferous, Wood fuel, Industrial roundwood, Wood-

						based panels, Pulp for paper, Industrial roundwood, coniferous , Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous, Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997) , Wood chips, particles and residues , Wood pellets and other agglomerates, Sawlogs and veneer logs, Sawnwood, Total fibre furnish , Graphic papers, Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint , Packaging paper and paperboard
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood, Pulpwood, round and split, all species (production), Other industrial roundwood, Wood pulp, Wood pulp, excluding mechanical wood pulp, Paper and paperboard, Forest products (export/import), Fibreboard, Roundwood, coniferous, Roundwood, non-coniferous, Wood fuel, Industrial roundwood, Wood-based panels, Pulp for paper, Industrial roundwood, coniferous , Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous, Pulpwood and particles (1961-1997) , Wood chips, particles and residues , Wood pellets and other agglomerates, Sawlogs and veneer logs, Sawnwood, Total fibre furnish , Graphic papers, Paper and paperboard, excluding newsprint , Packaging paper and paperboard

OECD - Agri-Environmental indicators: Nutrients

General information

Description: This tool dataset analyze nutrients, fertilisers used and manure.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: fertiliser, Soil, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Europe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 25, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2014

Keywords: soil, fertiliser, nutrients

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS#	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS#	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Phosphorus	January, 2000 - December, 2014		100	
Nitrogen	January, 2000 - December, 2014		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total forage	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

Total harvested fodder crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total pasture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient removal by crop residues removed from the field	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient removal by crop residues burned on the field	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Balance (inputs minus outputs)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Balance per hectare	Socioeconomic variable	Kilograms	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient inputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total inorganic fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total organic fertilisers (excluding livestock manure)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Net input of manure	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

Livestock manure production	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total cattle	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total poultry	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total other livestock	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total manure withdrawals	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Manure imports	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Other nutrient inputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Atmospheric deposition	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Biological fixation	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total seeds and planting materials	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient outputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total harvested crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

Total cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total oil crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total dried pulses and beans	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Other crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

OECD - Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume

General information

Description: The objective of this dataset is to trace net changes in terms of volume in the growing stock of standing wood on forest land.

Producer: OECD

Link: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOREST>

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: forest, natural resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: ENV.Stat@oecd.org

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Chile, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 29, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2019

Keywords: environment, forest

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOREST	Excel XLS	False
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOREST	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOREST	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOREST	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Intensity of use of forest resources	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Fellings	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Volumes salvaged	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Net fellings	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Natural losses	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Gross Increment	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Net increment	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume
Net change	Socioeconomic variable	ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Countries' Depletion and growth of forest resources in terms of volume

OECD - Air Emission Accounts

General information

Description: The System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) Central Framework is an accounting system developed around two objectives: "understanding the interactions between the economy and the environment" and describing "stocks and changes in stocks of environmental assets".

Data refer to total emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, PFCs, SF₆ +NF₃, SO_x, NO_x, CO, NMVOC, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and NH₃.

Producer: OECD

Link: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEA#>

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: greenhouse gas, air safety, atmospheric pollution, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment, Atmospheric conditions

Useful for the analysis of: Pollutant Gases, Greenhouse gas emissions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Switzerland, Colombia, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Indonesia, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, Ukraine

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:
Last update: May 10, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEA#	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEA#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEA#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEA#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	
B: Mining and quarrying	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
CO: Carbon monoxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
CO2: Carbon dioxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
CH4: Methane	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
N2O: Nitrous oxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
HFC: Hydrofluorocarbons	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
PFC: Perfluorocarbons	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
SF6: Sulphur hexafluoride	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
PM2_5: Particulates (less than 2.5µm)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
NMVOC: Non-methane volatile organic compounds	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying

SOX: Sulphur oxides	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
NOX: Nitrogen oxides	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
ACG: Acidifying gases (SOX in SO2 equivalent, NOX in SO2 equivalent, NH3 in SO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
NH3: Ammonia	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
O3PR: Ozone precursors (NMVOC, NOX in NMVOC equivalent, CO in NMVOC equivalent, CH4 in NMVOC equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying
PM10: Particulates (less than 10µm)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes of pollutant	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B: Mining and quarrying

OECD - Wastewater treatment (% population connected)

General information

Description:

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_TREAT

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: water, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Czechia, East Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords: wastewater

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_TREAT	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_TREAT	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_TREAT	Excel XLS	False
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_TREAT	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Wastewater treatment (% population connected)	January, 1970 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total public sewerage (% of resident)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)

population connected to urban wastewater collecting system = PUBTOTTR + PUBNOTR)						
Population connected to independent treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Not connected to public sewerage or independent treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Connected to a wastewater treatment plant without treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Public total treatment (connected to a wastewater treatment plant 0 PUBMECTR + PUBIOTR + PUBADVTR + OTHERTR)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Unspecified (other) treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)

Tertiary treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Secondary treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Primary treatment	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)
Total treatment (= PUBTOTTR + INDEPDTR)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Wastewater treatment (% population connected)

EUROSTAT - Number of sheep

General information

Description: Number of sheep (over 500,000) from the November/December survey

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: September 22, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of sheep	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Eurostat - Environmental taxes by economic activity (NACE Rev. 2)

General information

Description: Statistics on environmental taxes by economic activity characterise amount of paid environmental taxes in breakdown by economic activity (NACE Rev. 2).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link:

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Environment and energy

Subjects: tax, environmental policy, Environment, Transport, Energy resources

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage:

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 24, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 21, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1995 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV format (unzipped)	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_taxind2/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_taxind2/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV format	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_taxind2/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-ML format	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_taxind2/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
[ENV] Total environmental taxes	Socioeconomic variable	Million euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NRG] Energy taxes	Socioeconomic variable	[MIO_EUR] Million euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[POL] Pollution taxes	Socioeconomic variable	Million euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[RES] Resource taxes	Socioeconomic variable	Million euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[TRA] Transport taxes	Socioeconomic variable	Million euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)

Eurostat - Generation and discharge of wastewater by pollutant

General information

Description: Wastewater generation, treatment and discharge: Generation of wastewater - point sources.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ww_genp/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Environment and energy

Subjects: water, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, France, Greece, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 23, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2018

Keywords: water, wastewater

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ww_genp/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ww_genp/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ww_genp/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture, forestry, fishing	January, 2009 - December, 2018	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Generation of wastewater	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of O2 per day	January, 2009 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry, fishing

[UINPR] Selling of Prices of Crop Products (Absolute Prices)

General information

Description:

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=apri_ap_crpouta&lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: price of agricultural produce

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: June 15, 2021

Characterization created at: March 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: December, 2000 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SPSS	SPSS	Public		SPSS	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public		PC-AXIS	False
PDF	PDF	Public		PDF	False
TSV	TSV	Public		TSV	False
HTML	HTML	Public		HTML	False
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Excel XLS	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
National	December, 2000 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Barley	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg, National Currency per 100 kg	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Soft wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg; National Currency per 100 kg	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National

Durum wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg, National Currency per 100 kg	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Vin de pays/Vinho regional/Vino de la tierra	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Other table wine	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Quality wine	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Other wine	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Extra vergine	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Sopraffino - fine	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National

[UINPR] Purchase Prices of the Means of Agricultural Production (Absolute Prices)

General information

Description:

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=apri_ap_ina&lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: raw material, price of energy

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: June 15, 2021

Characterization created at: April 6, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: December, 2000 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SPSS	SPSS	Public		SPSS	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public		PC-AXIS	False
PDF	PDF	Public		PDF	False
TSV	TSV	Public		TSV	False
HTML	HTML	Public		HTML	False
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Excel XLS	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
National	December, 2000 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Ammonium nitrate (26% N) (in bulk)	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg of nutritive substance, National Currency per	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National

		100 kg of nutritive substance				
Binary fertilizers: 1 - 1 - 0	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg merchandise, National Currency per 100 kg merchandise	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Ternary fertilizers: 1 - 1 - 1 (in sacks)	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg merchandise, National Currency per 100 kg merchandise	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Electricity	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kwh, National Currency per 100 kwh	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Heating gas oil	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Residual fuel oil	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg, National Currency per 100 kg	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Motor spirit	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National

Diesel oil	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 litres, National Currency per 100 litres	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Sulphate of ammonia	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg of nutritive substance, National Currency per 100 kg of nutritive substance	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National
Ammonium nitrate (26% N) (in sacks)	Socioeconomic variable	€ per 100 kg of nutritive substance, National Currency per 100 kg of nutritive substance	December, 2000 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	National

[UNIPR] EU-Wide FADN (after 2017)

General information

Description:

Producer: DG Agriculture and Rural Development

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/farming/facts-and-figures/farms-farming-and-innovation/structures-and-economics/economics/fadn_en

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural market, means of agricultural production, agricultural policy, common agricultural policy, agricultural product, price of agricultural produce, agricultural statistics, accounting, agricultural expenditure, agri-foodstuffs, agricultural equipment, agricultural economics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Income and distributional policies, Environmental policy, Technical efficiency analysis, Greenhouse gas emissions, Climate change, Energy use in agriculture, Insurance policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Europe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: June 15, 2021

Characterization created at: March 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2018 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Restricted		CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm	January, 2018 - December, 2018		9900000	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Location of the holding - Latitude	Socioeconomic variable	Degrees; Minutes	January, 2018 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Farm
Location of the holding - Longitude	Socioeconomic variable	Degrees; Minutes	January, 2018 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Farm

(IDENER dry run) Farm Labour Force 2010

General information

Description: Farm labour force includes all persons having completed their compulsory education who carried out farm work on the holding during the 12 months ending on the reference day of the survey.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural statistics, labour force, gender equality, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Population and society, Population distribution — demography

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: September 27, 2021

Characterization created at: September 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2010

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2010 - December, 2010		100	1

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Family Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country

Labour force - members of the sole holder's family	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
Regular non family labour force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
Regular female labour force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of female persons (females)	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
Regular Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands FTE	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country

Agricultural holdings by agricultural area 2010

General information

Description: Agricultural holding: a single unit both technically and economically, which has single management and which produces agricultural products. The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Land use, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: September 29, 2021

Characterization created at: September 28, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2010

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural area, number of holdings

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public		Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public		TSV	False
SDMX-CVS	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2010 - December, 2010		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
100 ha or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
Zero ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
Less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 5 to 19.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country

From 20 to 49.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 50 to 99.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2010 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Country

OECD - Freshwater abstractions (million m3)

General information

Description: This dataset shows the state and changes over time in the abstractions of freshwater resources.

This dataset shows water abstractions by source (surface and ground water) and by major uses. Water abstractions refer to water taken from ground or surface water sources and conveyed to the place of use. If the water is returned to a surface water source, abstraction of the same water by the downstream user is counted again in compiling total withdrawal.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_ABSTRACT#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: water, water policy, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Freshwater abstractions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: agricultural and other relevant ministries of participating countries, national statistical offices, various national and international databases, including other OECD databases, Detailed information on sources of data for each participating country is available in the Definitions and Sources files by country

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_ABSTRACT#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_ABSTRACT#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_ABSTRACT#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_ABSTRACT#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	100	
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross abstractions as percentage of total renewable resources	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Total gross abstraction	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Agriculture, forestry, fishing	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Aquaculture	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Construction	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Production of electricity (cooling only)	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Private households	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Manufacturing industry	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Manufacturing cooling	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)

Mining and quarrying	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Public water supply	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Services	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Public water supply per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Net abstraction	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Gross abstractions per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Gross abstractions as percentage of internal resources	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)
Water returned without use	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres per capita	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	TOTAL FRESHWATER (GROUND AND SURFACE)

FAO - Country Investment Statistics Profile

General information

Description: The Country Investment Statistics Profile domain provides an overall view of the information about investment in agriculture at country level.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CISP>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Investment

Subjects: investment, economic statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Business, statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT - Investment and Macro Indicators

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 19, 2018

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2001 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CISP	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CISP	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Share of total US\$	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Country	95	
Value US\$	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Country	95	
Annual growth US\$	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Country	95	
Ratio	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Value added (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$, Ratio

Gross Fixed Capital Formation (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$
Agriculture, forestry, fishing (Central Government)	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$
Credit to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$
DFA Commitment to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$
FDI inflows to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	Millions/Percentage	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Share of total US\$, Value US\$, Annual growth US\$
Gross Fixed Capital Formation to GDP	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Ratio
Gross Fixed Capital Formation as a share of Value Added (Agriculture,	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 2001 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Ratio

Forestry and Fishing)						
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OECD - Water made available for use

General information

Description: Environment Database Water made available for use

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_USE

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: water, water policy, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Use of water

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: national statistical offices , various national and international databases, including other OECD databases, Detailed information on sources of data for each participating country is avail, agricultural and other relevant ministries of participating countries

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1980 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_USE#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_USE#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_USE#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_USE#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Countries' Water made available for use	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Generation of hydroelectricity. Desalinated water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total gross abstraction non-freshwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Abstractions for agriculture, forestry, fishing. Non-freshwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Abstractions for manufacturing. Non-freshwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Abstractions for electricity production. Non-freshwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total desalinated water. Non-freshwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total abstractions of reused water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Imported water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Exported water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use

Total non-renewable groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total water made available for use	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total losses during transport	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Abstractions from artificial reservoirs	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Abstractions for hydro-electricity	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Public water supply	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Self- and other supply	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use
Total gross abstraction. Desalinated water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' Water made available for use

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of sugar beet (unit value)

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00064/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 19, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00064/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00064/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00064/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sugar beet (unit value)	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Sugar beet (unit value)

EUROSTAT - Number of dairy cows

General information

Description: Number of animals from the November/December survey.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00014/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 18, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00014/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00014/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00014/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural holdings by agricultural area 2007

General information

Description: Agricultural holding: a single unit both technically and economically, which has single management and which produces agricultural products. The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Land use, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: September 29, 2021

Characterization created at: September 28, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2007 - December, 2007

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural area, number of holdings

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public		TSV	False
SDMX-CVS	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public		Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2007 - December, 2007		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Zero ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country
Less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 5 to 19.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 20 to 49.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country

100 ha or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 50 to 99.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2007 - December, 2007	Instant value	Annual	Country

Agricultural holdings by agricultural area 2013

General information

Description: Agricultural holding: a single unit both technically and economically, which has single management and which produces agricultural products. The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Land use, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: September 29, 2021

Characterization created at: September 28, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2013 - December, 2013

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural area, number of holdings

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TVS	TSV	Public		TSV	False
SDMX-CVS	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public		Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2013 - December, 2013		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
From 50 to 99.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country
100 ha or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country
Zero ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country
Less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country

From 5 to 19.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 20 to 49.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Country

Agricultural holdings by agricultural area 2005

General information

Description: Agricultural holding: a single unit both technically and economically, which has single management and which produces agricultural products. The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Land use, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: September 29, 2021

Characterization created at: September 28, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2005

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural area, number of holdings

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public		TSV	False
SDMX-CVS	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public		Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2005 - December, 2005		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Zero ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country
Less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 5 to 19.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country
From 20 to 49.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country

From 50 to 99.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country
100 ha or over	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand	January, 2005 - December, 2005	Instant value	Annual	Country

(IDENER dry run) Farm Labour Force 2013

General information

Description: Farm labour force includes all persons having completed their compulsory education who carried out farm work on the holding during the 12 months ending on the reference day of the survey.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural statistics, labour force, gender equality, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Population and society, Population distribution — demography

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: October 14, 2021

Characterization created at: September 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2013 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser-backend/api/query/1.0/LIVE/xlsx/en/download/c4a9ce80-0770-47d4-89f6-0fad4f85e497	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2013 - January, 2013	Country	100	1
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Regular Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Family Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Labour force - members of the sole holder's family	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Regular non family labour force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons (pers)	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Regular female labour force	Socioeconomic variable	Number of female persons (females)	January, 2013 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings by crops

General information

Description: The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land (unutilised agricultural land, wooded land and other land).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00007/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00007/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00007/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00007/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	98	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
hold: Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

hold: Pulses - total	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Root crops	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Industrial crops - total	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Fresh vegetables, melons, strawberries	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Flowers and ornamental plants	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Fodder crops - total	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Seeds, seedlings and other crops on arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Employment in the EU environmental economy by NACE Rev. 2 activity

General information

Description: This table presents employment in the European Union's (EU's) environmental economy, as it is defined in the European environmental goods and services sector (EGSS) accounts. The environmental economy encompasses activities and products that serve either of two purposes: 'environmental protection' — that is, preventing, reducing and eliminating pollution or any other degradation of the environment, or 'resource management' — that is, preserving and maintaining the stock of natural resources, hence safeguarding it against depletion.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00133/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Environment and energy

Subjects: labour force, employment service, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment, Energy

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics, Farm structure, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: EUROSTAT regular operations

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: November 24, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2008

Last update: March 31, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2007 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00133/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV format (unzipped)	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00133/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
TSV format	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00133/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-ML format	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00133/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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European Union - 27 countries	January, 2007 - December, 2018		100	
Agricultural, Forestry and Fishing Sector of the EU	January, 2007 - December, 2018		100	
Mining and quarrying; manufacturing of the EU	January, 2007 - December, 2018		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Employment in the Agricultural, Forestry and Fishing Sector	Socioeconomic variable	Full Time Equivalentents	January, 2007 - January, 2018		Annual	European Union - 27 countries
Employment	Socioeconomic variable	Full Time Equivalentents (FTE)	January, 2007 - December, 2018		Annual	Agricultural, Forestry and Fishing Sector, Mining and quarrying; manufacturing

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings by agricultural area

General information

Description: Agricultural holding: a single unit both technically and economically, which has single management and which produces agricultural products. The total area of the holding consists of the agricultural area utilized by the holding (arable land, kitchen gardens, permanent grassland and permanent crops) and other land.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Farm size, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00001/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
zero ha	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 5 to 19.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
100 ha or over	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 20 to 49.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 50 to 99.9 ha	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings by age of holder

General information

Description: The farm holder is the natural person, on whose account and in whose name the holding is operated and who is legally and economically responsible for the holding. If the holder is a group holding, the data relates to the person considered holder.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00029/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Farm structure, Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00029/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00029/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00029/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
From 45 to 54 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

From 55 to 64 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
65 years or over	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Not applicable	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Less than 35 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
From 35 to 44 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings by economic size of the farm (Standard Output in Euro)

General information

Description: The monetary economic size of the farm is expressed in Standard Output (SO). The SO is the average monetary value of the agricultural output at farm-gate price, in euro per hectare or per head of livestock.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00123/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural economics, economic indicator, agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Technical efficiency analysis, Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:
Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00123/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00123/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00123/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
------	------	---------------------	-----------------	-----------------------------	----------------	------------------

from 4000 to 14000 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
less than 4000 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 15000 to 49000 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 50000 to 99999 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 100000 to 249999 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
from 250000 to 499999 euros	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
500000 euros or over	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Farm Labour Force

General information

Description: Farm labour force includes all persons having completed their compulsory education who carried out farm work on the holding during the 12 months ending on the reference day of the survey.

Producer: Eurostat

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural statistics, labour force, gender equality, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Population and society, Population distribution — demography

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser-backend/api/query/1.0/LIVE/xlsx/en/download/c4a9ce80-0770-47d4-89f6-0fad4f85e497	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00020/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holding	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Family Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of people	January, 2005 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding
Labour force - members of the sole holder's family	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of people	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding
Regular non family labour force	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of people	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding
Regular female labour force	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of people (females)	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding
Regular Labour Force	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of people	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings by age of manager

General information

Description: The farm manager is the natural person responsible for the normal daily financial and production routines of running the holding.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00125/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Farm structure, Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00125/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00125/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00125/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Not applicable	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

Total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
From 45 to 54 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
From 55 to 64 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
65 years or over	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Less than 35 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
From 35 to 44 years	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Crop output - basic and producer prices

General information

Description: Crop output is valued at basic prices. The basic price is defined as the price received by the producer, after deduction of all taxes on products but including all subsidies on products. The concept of output comprises sales, changes in stocks, and crop products used as animal feedingstuffs, for processing and own final use by the producers.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00054/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Price policy, Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00054/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00054/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00054/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Production value at producer price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production value at basic price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

EUROSTAT -Animal output - basic and producer prices

General information

Description: Animal output is valued at basic prices. The basic price is defined as the price received by the producer, after deduction of all taxes on products but including all subsidies on products. The concept of output comprises sales, changes in stocks, and products used for processing and own final use by the producers.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00055/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, livestock farming value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00055/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00055/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00055/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
------	------	---------------------	-----------------	-----------------------------	----------------	------------------

Production value at producer price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production value at basic price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

EUROSTAT - Output of the agricultural industry - basic and producer prices

General information

Description: Output is valued at basic prices. The basic price is defined as the price received by the producer, after deduction of all taxes on products but including all subsidies on products. Output of the agricultural industry is made up of the sum of the output of agricultural products, agricultural services and of the goods and services produced in inseparable non-agricultural secondary activities.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00102/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agro-industry, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance, Production and industrial facilities

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, production value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00102/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00102/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00102/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production value at producer price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production value at basic price	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of pigs (light)

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00066/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Bulgaria, Czechia, Denmark, Spain, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 19, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00066/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00066/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00066/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Pigs (light)	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Pigs (light)

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of fresh eggs

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00071/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00071/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00071/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00071/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Fresh eggs	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Fresh eggs

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of raw cow's milk

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00070/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00070/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00070/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00070/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Row cow's milk	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Row cow's milk

EUROSTAT - Agricultural holdings with livestock

General information

Description: Livestock are the production animals that are in direct possession or management of the holding on the reference day of the survey.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00124/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agricultural holdings, livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Livestock farming, Farm structure

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: October 15, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00124/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00124/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00124/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
hold: Equidae	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

hold: Cattle - total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Sheep - total	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Goats	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Laying hens	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
hold: Number of holdings with livestock	Socioeconomic variable	thousands of holdings	January, 2005 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

EUROSTAT - Indicator A of the income from agricultural activity

General information

Description: Indicator A corresponds to the deflated (real) net value added at factor cost of agriculture, per total annual work unit. The implicit price index of GDP is used as deflator.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00057/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: agro-industry, cost analysis, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00057/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00057/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00057/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Indicator A	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2010=100	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of oats

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00061/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00061/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00061/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00061/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Oats	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	oats

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of barley

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00060/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00060/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00060/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00060/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Barley	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Barley

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of soft wheat

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00059/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00059/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00059/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00059/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Soft wheat	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Soft wheat

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of maize

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00062/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00062/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00062/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00062/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Maize	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Maize

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of main crop potatoes

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00063/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 18, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00063/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00063/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00063/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
main crop potatoes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	main crop potatoes

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of calves

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00065/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 19, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00065/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00065/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00065/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Calves	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Calves

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of piglets

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00067/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 19, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00067/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00067/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00067/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Piglets	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Piglets

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of sheep

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00069/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 19, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00069/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00069/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00069/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sheep	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Sheep

EUROSTAT - Selling prices of chickens (live 1st choice)

General information

Description: The absolute prices in this table give information on the levels of the producer prices of the product. Prices are net of VAT.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00068/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy, Income and distributional policies

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00068/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00068/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00068/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Chickens (live 1 st choice)	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Selling prices	Price variable	Euro	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Chickens (live 1 st choice)

EUROSTAT - Producer price indices, total agricultural production

General information

Description: The indices in this table give information on the trends in the producer prices of agricultural production as a whole. The sub-indices were weighted by the values of sales in 2000.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00046/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: economic indicator, agricultural product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, production value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2008

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00046/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00046/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00046/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural goods output	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Nominal price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural goods output

Real price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural goods output
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EUROSTAT - Producer price indices, crop products

General information

Description: The indices in this table give information on the trends in the producer prices of agricultural production as a whole. The sub-indices were weighted by the values of sales in 2000.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00048/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: economic indicator, agricultural product, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, production value, Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2008

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00048/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00048/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00048/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Crop output	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Nominal price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Crop output

Real price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Crop output
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EUROSTAT - Producer price indices, animals and animal products

General information

Description: The indices in this table give information on the trends in the producer prices of agricultural production as a whole. The sub-indices were weighted by the values of sales in 2000.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00050/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: economic indicator, animal product, livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, production value, livestock farming value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2008

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00050/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00050/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00050/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Animal output	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Nominal price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Animal output

Real price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Animal output
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EUROSTAT - Purchase price indices, total means of agricultural production

General information

Description: The indices in this table give information on the trends in the producer prices of agricultural production as a whole. The sub-indices were weighted by the values of sales in 2000.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00052/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: economic indicator, input-output analysis, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, production value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 20, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2008

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00052/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00052/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00052/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Input total	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Nominal price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Input total

Real price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1997 - December, 2008	Instant value	Annual	Input total
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EUROSTAT - Production of meat: pigs

General information

Description: This indicator expresses the total carcass weight of pigs slaughtered in slaughterhouses and on the farm, whose meat is declared fit for human consumption.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00042/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00042/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00042/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00042/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of meat: pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of meat: sheep and goats

General information

Description: This indicator expresses the total carcass weight of pigs slaughtered in slaughterhouses and on the farm, whose meat is declared fit for human consumption.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00045/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00045/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00045/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00045/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Production of meat: sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
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EUROSTAT - Cereals for the production of grain (including seed) by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of cereals for the production of grain: wheat (common wheat and spelt and durum wheat), rye, maslin, barley, oats, mixed grain other than maslin, grain maize, sorghum, triticale, and other cereal crops such as buckwheat, millet, canary seed and rice. Cereal grains harvested just before maturity are also included in this table.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area

EUROSTAT - Barley by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of barley: winter barley sown before or during winter and spring barley sown in the spring. Cereal grains harvested just before maturity are also included in this table. Cereals harvested green or yellow as whole plant for fodder or renewable energy use are not included in this table. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00051/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:
Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00051/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00051/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00051/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Oats and spring cereal mixtures by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of oats and spring cereal mixtures: oats and other cereals sown in the spring and grown as mixtures and harvested as dry grain, including seed. Cereal grains harvested just before maturity are also included in this table. Cereals harvested green or yellow as whole plant for fodder or renewable energy use are not included in this table. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00053/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00053/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00053/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00053/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Production of butter

General information

Description: Data concern the total production of butter and other yellow fat dairy products.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00038/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: milk product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Products

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00038/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00038/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00038/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of butter	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of milk powder

General information

Description: Milk powder is one of two products (with butter) whose marketing can be sustained by public authorities. Since the implementation of milk quotas milk powder stocks have considerably decreased. EU15: Eurostat estimation including confidential data.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00039/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: milk product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Products

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00039/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00039/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00039/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of milk powder	Socioeconomic variable	1000	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of cheese

General information

Description: Several cheese categories belong to the denomination "cheese". They differ mainly from their moisture content. Data presented in this table relate to all cheeses but European statistics also provide information on the production of seven cheese categories with different moisture contents and compositions. EU15: Eurostat estimation including confidential data.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cheese, milk product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Products

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of cheese	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of milk on farms

General information

Description: Milk production on the farm covers milk from cows, ewes, goats and buffaloes. Attention should be paid to the fact that some Member States produce only cow's milk.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00041/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: milk, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Production, production value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00040/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of milk on farms	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of meat: cattle

General information

Description: This indicator expresses the total carcass weight of pigs slaughtered in slaughterhouses and on the farm, whose meat is declared fit for human consumption.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00044/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00044/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00044/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00044/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of meat: cattle	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Production of meat: poultry

General information

Description: This indicator expresses the total carcass weight of pigs slaughtered in slaughterhouses and on the farm, whose meat is declared fit for human consumption.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00043/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00043/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00043/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00043/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production of meat: poultry	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

EUROSTAT - Number of pigs

General information

Description: Number of animals from the November/December survey

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 18, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00017/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

EUROSTAT - Organic crop area (fully converted area)

General information

Description: The area which fulfills all the conditions of production established in Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 can be considered to be organic. The detailed rules for the implementation of this Regulation are laid down in Commission Regulation (EC) No 889/2008.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00098/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: organic farming, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Organic Crop, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: August 4, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area	January, 1997 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Organic crop area	Socioeconomic variable	Hectare	January, 1997 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area

EUROSTAT - Area under organic farming

General information

Description: The indicator measures the share of total utilised agricultural area (UAA) occupied by organic farming (existing organically-farmed areas and areas in process of conversion). Farming is recognised to be organic if it complies with Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007, which has set up a comprehensive framework for the organic production of crops and livestock and for the labelling, processing and marketing of organic products, as well as for governing imports of organic products into the EU. The detailed rules for the implementation of this Regulation are laid down in Commission Regulation (EC) No 889/2008.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: economic indicator, organic farming, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: land use, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: August 4, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_02_40/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area under organic farming	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area

OECD - Monitoring and evaluation : Single commodity indicators

General information

Description: This dataset and predefined summary tables are a complement to the report Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation 2021, which monitors agricultural policy developments in 37 OECD member countries, 5 non-OECD European Union member states and 12 emerging and developing economies: Argentina, Brazil, China, Costa Rica, India, Indonesia, Kazakhstan, the Philippines, the Russian Federation, South Africa, Ukraine and Viet Nam. Costa Rica became the 38th Member of the OECD in May 2021, but in this dataset, it is not included in the OECD total.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_SINGLE_COMMODITY_INDICATORS

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: agricultural policy, environmental policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: collected from agricultural and other relevant ministries of participating countries

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, European Union, United Kingdom, Indonesia, India, Iceland, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, South Korea, Mexico, Norway, New Zealand, Philippines, Russia, Turkey, Ukraine, United States, Vietnam, South Africa

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued: June 1, 2021

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1986 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX (XML)	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_SINGLE_COMMODITY_INDICATORS	XML	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_SINGLE_COMMODITY_INDICATORS	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_SINGLE_COMMODITY_INDICATORS	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MON_SINGLE_COMMODITY_INDICATORS	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Tea	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Coffee	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Pineapples	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Plantains	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Plants and flowers	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Potatoes	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Red peppers	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Rubber	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Spinach	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Strawberries	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
wheat	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
maize	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
rye	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Barley	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Sorghum	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	

Cotton	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Oats	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Rice	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Sugar	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Rapeseed	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Sunflower	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Soybeans	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
milk	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Beef and Veal	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Sheep meat	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Wool	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Pig meat	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Poultry meat	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Eggs	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Alfalfa	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	

Apples	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Avocados	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Bananas	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Dried Beans	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Blueberries	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Cashes nuts	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Cassava	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Cherries	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Chick peas	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Chinese cabbage	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Cocoa beans	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Coconuts	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Cucumbers	January, 1990 - December, 2020		100	
Dried peas	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Flax	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	

Fruit and vegetables	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Garlic	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Tobacco	January, 1990 - December, 2020		100	
Tomatoes	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Welsh onions	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Wine	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Other Commodities	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Grapefruits	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Grapes	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Groundnuts	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Lentils	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Mandarins	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Mangoes	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Onions	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Oranges	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	

Other pulses	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Palm oil	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Peaches	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Pears	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	
Peppers	January, 1986 - December, 2020		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Market Price Support	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs
Value of production (at farm gate)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Bananas, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Cucumbers, Dried peas, Flax, Garlic, Grapes, Lentils, Mandarins, Pears, Potatoes, Spinach, Strawberries, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Welsh onions, Wine, Avocados, Cherries, Grapefruits, Groundnuts, Oranges, Palm oil, Peaches, Peppers, Plantains, Other Commodities, Apples, Blueberries, Plants and flowers, Red peppers

Value of consumption (at farm gate)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Bananas, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Cucumbers, Dried peas, Flax, Garlic, Grapes, Lentils, Mandarins, Pears, Potatoes, Spinach, Strawberries, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Welsh onions, Wine, Avocados, Cherries, Grapefruits, Groundnuts, Oranges, Palm oil, Peaches, Peppers, Plantains, Other Commodities, Apples, Blueberries, Plants and flowers, Red peppers
Transfers to producers from consumers (-)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Garlic, Grapes, Mandarins, Pears, Potatoes, Spinach, Strawberries, Welsh onions, Palm oil, Other Commodities, Plants and flowers, Red peppers, wheat, maize, Barley, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Bananas, Chinese cabbage, Cotton, Cucumbers, Flax
Level of production	Socioeconomic variable	thousand of Tonnes	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Strawberries, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Welsh onions, Wine, wheat, maize, rye, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Apples, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Cucumbers, Dried peas, Flax, Garlic, Grapes, Lentils, Mandarins, Pears, Potatoes, Red peppers, Spinach

Level of consumption (at farm gate)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of tonnes	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, rye, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Bananas, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Cucumbers, Dried peas, Flax, Garlic, Grapes, Lentils, Mandarins, Pears, Potatoes, Red peppers, Spinach, Strawberries, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Welsh onions, Wine, Avocados, Blueberries, Cherries, Grapefruits, Groundnuts, Oranges, Palm oil, Peaches, Peppers, Plantains
Other transfers from consumers (-)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Alfalfa, Bananas, Chinese cabbage, Flax, Garlic, Grapes, Mandarins, Potatoes, Strawberries, Welsh onions, Palm oil, Other Commodities, Plants and flowers, Red peppers
Budgetary transfers	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, rye, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Apples, Bananas, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Garlic, Grapes, Mandarins, Palm oil, Pears, Plants and flowers, Potatoes, Red peppers, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Wine
Excess feed cost (crops)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, million	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	wheat, rye, Rice, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Soybeans
Excess feed cost (Livestock)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, million	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs

Transfer to producer from taxpayers	Socioeconomic variable	USD, million	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, rye, maize, Barley, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Apples, Bananas, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Coffee, Cotton, Garlic, Grapes, Mandarins, Palm oil, Pears, Plants and flowers, Potatoes, Tobacco, Tomatoes, Wine
Price levies (-)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, million	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Rice, Sugar, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Poultry meat, Pig meat, Eggs
Payments based on output	Socioeconomic variable	USD, million	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Strawberries, Other Commodities, wheat, maize, rye, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs, Apples, Dried Beans, Chinese cabbage, Cotton, Cucumbers, Grapes, Mandarins, Pears, Spinach
Percentage single commodity transfers	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs
Producer nominal protection coefficient	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs
Consumer nominal protection coefficient	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 1986 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	wheat, maize, Barley, Sorghum, Oats, Rice, Sugar, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Soybeans, milk, Beef and Veal, Sheep meat, Wool, Pig meat, Poultry meat, Eggs

OECD - Patents - Technology development

General information

Description: Environment Database Technology development

This dataset presents patent statistics and indicators that are suitable for tracking innovation in environment-related technologies. They allow the assessment of countries' and firms' innovation performance as well as the design of governments' environmental and innovation policies

Producer: OECD

Link:

https://www.google.com/url?q=https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode%3DPAT_DEV&sa=D&source=editors&ust=1641816754899777&usg=AOvVaw1dkxjineEN2ONJZVlgLjWe

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: new technology, patent, environmental policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment, Science and technology

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: The patent statistics presented here are constructed using algorithms developed by the OECD Environment Directorate drawing on data extracted from the OECD STI Micro-data Lab: Intellectual Property Database, <http://oe.cd/ipstats>

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: January 4, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=PAT_DEV#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=PAT_DEV#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=PAT_DEV#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=PAT_DEV#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
All countries' inventions	January, 1990 - December, 2018	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Environment-related technologies	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
All technologies (total patents)	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Environmental management	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Air pollution abatement	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Water pollution abatement	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Waste management	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Soil remediation	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Environmental monitoring	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Climate change mitigation	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Climate change adaptation technologies	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions
Sustainable ocean economy	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 1990 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	All countries' inventions

EUROSTAT - Wheat and spelt by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of common wheat and spelt: wheat, spelt, einkorn wheat and durum wheat. Cereal grains harvested just before maturity are also included in this table. Cereals harvested green or yellow as whole plant for fodder or renewable energy use are not included in this table. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00047/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:
Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00047/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00047/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00047/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Grain maize and corn-cob-mix by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of maize harvested for grain, as seed or as corn-cob-mix. In particular, grain maize harvested by hand, corn-picker, corn-sheller or combine harvester, regardless of the use, including grain for silage. Also grain harvested together with parts of the cob, but with humidity higher than 20% and used for silage (so called corn-cob-mix, CCM – humidity 30-35%) is included here. Maize harvested green for fodder or for energy use and sweet maize are not included in this table. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00093/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00093/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00093/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00093/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Rye and winter cereal mixtures by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of rye and winter cereal mixtures: rye, mixtures of "rye and other cereals" and "other cereal mixtures" sown before or during the winter (maslin). Cereal grains harvested just before maturity are also included in this table. Cereals harvested green or yellow as whole plant for fodder or renewable energy use are not included in this table. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00049/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00049/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00049/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00049/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Eu standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain (including seed and mixtures of cereals and pulses) by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the areas, productions and humidity of field peas, broad and field beans, sweet lupins, dry beans, other dry peas, lentils, chickling vetch, chick peas, vetches and other protein crops sown in pure crops or as mixtures with cereals harvested dry for grain. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00094/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00094/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00094/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00094/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area
Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area

EUROSTAT - Grapes by production

General information

Description: This table includes the productions of all grapes; in particular, for wine, for table use and for raisins. This indicator uses the concept of "harvested production" which corresponds to the production for which harvesting started in year N, even though harvesting may finish in year N+1. So N is the reference year for data published by Eurostat.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00121/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Agriculture policy, Grapes production, Wine production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00121/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00121/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00121/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Grapes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Grapes

Grapes for wines	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Grapes
Grapes for table use	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Grapes
Grapes for raisins	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Grapes

EUROSTAT - Olives by production

General information

Description: This table includes the productions of olives for olive oil and for table use. This indicator uses the concept of "harvested production" which corresponds to the production for which harvesting started in year N, even though harvesting may finish in year N+1. So N is the reference year for data published by Eurostat.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00122/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: olive oil, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00027/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Olives	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Olives production for olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Olives
Olives production for table use	Socioeconomic variable	100 tonnes	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Olives

EUROSTAT - Number of bovine animals

General information

Description: Number of animals from the November/December survey.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00016/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Technical efficiency analysis

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 21, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 18, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00016/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00016/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00016/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of bovine animals	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holding

OECD - Treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5

General information

Description: This dataset shows the Treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5 (biochemical oxygen demand).

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_BOD#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: water policy, water, environmental protection, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Use of water, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Data for European countries comes directly from the E.U. statistical agency (EUROSTAT) , Data is expressed in tons of O2/day

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Chile, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: August 1, 2019

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2014

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_BOD#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_BOD#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_BOD#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_BOD#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis

Design capacity BOD5 (primary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Design capacity BOD5 (secondary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Design capacity BOD5 (tertiary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (primary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (secondary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5

Effluent BOD5 (tertiary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (secondary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Incoming load BOD5 (primary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Incoming load BOD5 (secondary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Incoming load BOD5 (tertiary treatment, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Primary treatment (other	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5

treatment plants)						
Secondary treatment (other treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Tertiary treatment (other treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Total wastewater treatment (other treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Total urban wastewater treatment (plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Design capacity BOD ₅ (total)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Incoming load BOD ₅ (total)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Effluent BOD ₅ (total)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅

Primary treatment (plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Design capacity BOD ₅ (primary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Incoming load BOD ₅ (primary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Effluent BOD ₅ (primary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Secondary treatment (plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Design capacity BOD ₅ (secondary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Incoming load BOD ₅ (secondary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Tertiary treatment	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Design capacity BOD ₅ (tertiary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅
Incoming load BOD ₅ (tertiary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O ₂ /day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD ₅

Effluent BOD5 (tertiary treatment)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Nitrogen removal (plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Design capacity BOD5 (Nitrogen removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Incoming load BOD5 (Nitrogen removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (Nitrogen removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Phosphorus removal (plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Design capacity BOD5 (Phosphorus removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Incoming load BOD5 (Phosphorus removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (Phosphorus removal)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Effluent BOD5 (total, other wastewater)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5

treatment plants)						
Incoming load BOD5 (total, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5
Design capacity BOD5 (total, other wastewater treatment plants)	Socioeconomic variable	tons of O2/day	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Countries' treatment capacity of wastewater treatment plants, in terms of BOD5

OECD - Land cover in countries and regions

General information

Description: Loss of biodiversity and pressures on ecosystem services are among the most pressing global environmental challenges. Changes in land cover and land use are the leading contributors to terrestrial biodiversity loss. Land cover 'snapshots' for a given year provide context against which the conversions detailed above can be evaluated. This multi-class dataset allows for analysis of changes in land cover consistently at the global scale. It builds on decades of Earth observation missions by different national and supranational space organisations.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: geographical information system, Land cover

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 29, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1992 - December, 2019

Keywords: land cover

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Tree cover	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Grassland	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Wetland	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Shrubland	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Cropland	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Artificial surfaces	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Bare area	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	
Inland water	January, 1992 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land cover km ²	Socioeconomic variable	Km ²	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Tree cover, Grassland, Wetland, Shrubland, Cropland, Artificial surfaces, Bare area, Inland water
Land cover Percent of total country area	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Tree cover, Grassland, Wetland, Shrubland, Cropland, Artificial surfaces, Bare area, Inland water

EUROSTAT - Rape, turnip rape, sunflower seeds and soya by area

General information

Description: This table includes the areas of rape, turnip rape, sunflower seeds and soya, harvested as dry grains. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation". The "area under cultivation" corresponds: • before the harvest, to the sown area; • after the harvest, to the sown area excluding the non-harvested area (e.g. area ruined by natural disasters, area not harvested for economic reasons, etc.)

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00100/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00100/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00100/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00100/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Land with rape and turnip rape seeds	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with sunflower seeds	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with soya	Socioeconomic variable	1000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area

EUROSTAT - Green maize by area, production and humidity

General information

Description: This table includes the area, production and humidity of all forms of maize harvested green grown mainly for silage. This includes green maize directly consumed by animals (without silage) and whole cobs (grain, rachis, husk) harvested for feedstuff or silage, as well as for renewable energy production. Maize harvested as grain and corn-cob-mix is excluded. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation", "harvested production" and "humidity".

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00101/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: cereals, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:
Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00101/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00101/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00101/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Area (cultivation/harvested/production)	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 hectares	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
Harvested production in EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	1 000 tonnes.	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop
EU standard humidity	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Parcel cultivated for the production of a crop

EUROSTAT - Root crops and plants harvested green from arable land by area

General information

Description: This table includes the areas where are sown potatoes (including seed), sugar beet (excluding seed), temporary grasses for grazing, hay or silage (in the crop rotation cycle), leguminous plants grown and harvested green (as the whole plant, mainly for fodder, energy or green manuring use), other cereals harvested green (excluding green maize): rye, wheat, triticale, annual sorghum, buckwheat, etc. This indicator uses the concepts of "area under cultivation" which corresponds: • before the harvest, to the sown area; • after the harvest, to the sown area excluding the non-harvested area (e.g. area ruined by natural disasters, area not harvested for economic reasons, etc.)

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00103/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: crop production, root crop, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00103/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00103/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00103/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land with potatoes (including seed potatoes)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with sugar beet (excluding seed)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with temporary grasses and grazings	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Leguminous plants harvested green	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area
Land with other cereals harvested green (excluding green maize)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Area

EUROSTAT - Permanent crops for human consumption by area

General information

Description: This table includes the areas of all fruit trees (in particular apples, pears and cherries) all nut trees, all berry plantations (except strawberries), all citrus fruit trees, all vineyards, all olive trees and all other permanent crops used for human consumption. This indicator uses the concepts of "production area". The "production area" corresponds to the area that can be harvested in the reference harvest year. All of the non-producing areas, such as new plantations that have not yet started to produce, are not excluded, as well as the abandoned areas. In addition, only the areas planted with permanent crops that are entirely or mainly intended to produce for the market are included.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00120/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00120/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00120/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00120/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Area	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land with pear trees	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Production Area
Land with cherry trees	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Production Area
Land with orange trees	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Production Area
Land with permanent crops for human consumption	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Production Area
Land with apple trees	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Production Area

EUROSTAT - Gross value added of the forestry industry, at basic prices

General information

Description: The economic accounts for forestry and logging are based on national accounts, but are collected with greater detail. Current prices means prices of that particular year. Annual inflation must yet be taken into account if one wishes to compare the values of different years. Basic prices means the price received by the producer after deduction of all taxes on products, but including all subsidies on products. Gross value added is the value of the output less the value of intermediate consumption. Fixed capital relates to longer-lived assets (e.g. equipment or buildings) that are either acquired (this is gross fixed capital formation) or consumed (this is fixed capital consumption, the annual reduction in the value of fixed assets). The definition of the activity of forestry and logging is based on Division 02 of NACE Rev. 2.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00058/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: forestry economics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy, Forestry output

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00058/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00058/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00058/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
forestry industry	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross value added	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	forestry industry
Consumption of fixed capital	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	forestry industry
Gross fixed capital formation (excluding deductible VAT)	Price variable	Million euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	forestry industry

FAO - Detailed trade matrix

General information

Description: The trade database includes the following variables: export quantity, export value, import quantity, and import value. The trade database includes all food and agricultural products imported/exported annually by all the countries in the world.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TM>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Trade

Subjects: export policy, import policy, Economy and finance, Imports of goods, Exports of goods

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: UNSD, Eurostat

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 20, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1986 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TM	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TM	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Legumes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Rice	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Flour	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Vegetables	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Coffew	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Fruits	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Sugar	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Geonames	75	
Dried fruits	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	

Oil	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	
Cotton	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	75	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Flour , Vegetables, Fruits, Sugar, Dried fruits, Legumes, Cotton , Rice, Oil, Coffew
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Flour , Vegetables, Fruits, Sugar, Dried fruits, Legumes, Cotton , Rice, Oil, Coffew
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Flour , Vegetables, Fruits, Sugar, Dried fruits, Legumes, Cotton , Rice, Oil, Coffew
Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Flour , Vegetables, Fruits, Sugar, Dried fruits, Legumes, Cotton , Rice, Oil, Coffew

FAO - Crops and livestock products

General information

Description: Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Primary, Cereals, Coarse Grain, Citrus Fruit, Fruit, Jute Jute-like Fibres, Oilcakes Equivalent, Oil crops Primary, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts and Vegetables and Melons. Data are expressed in terms of area harvested, production quantity and yield. The objective is to comprehensively cover production of all primary crops for all countries and regions in the world. Cereals: Area and production data on cereals relate to crops harvested for dry grain only. Cereal crops harvested for hay or harvested green for food, feed or silage or used for grazing are therefore excluded. Area data relate to harvested area. Some countries report sown or cultivated area only

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Production

Subjects: livestock, agricultural product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Livestock farming

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: November 11, 2021

Issued:
Last update: September 15, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Crops primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Crops processed	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Live animals	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Livestock processed	January, 1961 - December, 2021	Country	95	
Livestock primary	January, 1961 - December, 2021	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area havrvested	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Crops primary
Crops primary Yeld	Socioeconomic variable	Hg/ha	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Crops primary
Stock	Socioeconomic variable	Head	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Live animals
Livestock primary Yeld	Socioeconomic variable	Hg/animal	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Livestock primary
Production quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Crops primary, Livestock primary
Producing Animals/Slaughtered	Socioeconomic variable	Head	January, 1961 - December, 2021		Annual	Livestock primary

Labour force by sex, type of the farm and size of the farm

General information

Description: Labour force by sex, type of the farm and size of the farm

Producer: Eurostat

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ef_lf_size/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: employment policy

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2013 - January, 2016

Keywords: employment, awu

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Labour force by sex, type of the farm and size of the farm	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Labour force by sex, type of the farm and size of the farm	Socioeconomic variable	Persons	January, 2013 - January, 2016	Instant value	Annual	

OECD - Food Waste

General information

Description: The OECD food waste dataset is a compilation of available data related to food loss and food waste for 32 countries. The period covered may vary across different countries depending on data availability (globally ranging from 1993 to 2013).

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOOD_WASTE

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: food waste, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by: Several types of sources have been used: international organisations, government and national statistic institutes, OECD delegations, academic studies and private sector or >>/overnmental analytical reports

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 14, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1993 - December, 2013

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOOD_WASTE#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOOD_WASTE#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOOD_WASTE#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=FOOD_WASTE#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural production	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Manufacturing	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Storage	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Transportation	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Wholesale & Retail	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Food Services	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Households	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Combined	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Municipal Waste	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Total	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	
Contextual data	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Unavoidable food Loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Agricultural production remaining in the fields	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data

Animal and mixed food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Animal and mixed food waste; vegetal waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Animal and vegetal waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Animal food refuse	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Animal food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Animal waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Avoidable and possibly	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households,

avoidable food and drink waste						Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Avoidable cost of food & drinks waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Avoidable food and drink waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Discarded food	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food Loss & Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food & Loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food and drink waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data

Food production	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food purchased	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food Supply	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food thrown away without being eaten in total food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Food Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Harvest Losses	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
household food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households,

						Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Ingredient waste after storage	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Kitchen Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Liquid food waste in total food and drink waste collected	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Maximum percentage food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Minimum estimate percentage of food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Mixed food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data

Organics in total diversion	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Other food loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Possibly avoidable food and drink waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Residual waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Share animal and vegetal waste in total household waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Solid food considered food Loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Solid waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households,

						Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Total Food Loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Total food supply	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Total food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Total waste diversion	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Unavoidable food and drink waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Unnesserary food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data, Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households

Vegetable waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Vegetal food waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data
Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, kg/capita, %	January, 1993 - December, 2013	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural production, Manufacturing, Storage, Transportation, Wholesale & Retail, Food Services, Households, Combined, Municipal Waste, Total, Contextual data

OECD - Mineral and Energy Resources

General information

Description: Mineral and energy resources are one of the seven environmental assets considered in the System of Environmental Economic Accounting (SEEA, 2012). They are non-renewable resources which cannot be regenerated over a human timescale in spite of their prominent role in sustaining economic activities. From an economic, environmental and supply security perspective, it is therefore important to gather harmonised data on their rate of extraction and current availability.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=NAT_RES

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: mineral resources, natural resources, Energy resources, Mineral resources

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Canada, Colombia, Denmark, United Kingdom, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: May 26, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=NAT_RES#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=NAT_RES#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=NAT_RES#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=NAT_RES#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
countries' Stock and flows	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Crude oil	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Natural gas	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Coal	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Hard coal	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Brown coal	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Iron-Ore	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Bauxite	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Copper	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Tin	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Zinc	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Lead	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Nickel	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Gold	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Silver	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows
Phosphate	Socioeconomic variable	Barrels, Billions	January, 2000 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' Stock and flows

EUROSTAT - Animal populations by NUTS 2 regions

General information

Description: Livestock numbers are derived from surveys of farms or from administrative sources in November or December for each Member State.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tgs00045/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: livestock farming, livestock, meat, animal product, dairy production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, livestock farming value

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage:

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: September 3, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tgs00045/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tgs00045/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tgs00045/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2009 - December, 2020	NUTS2	98	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Live bovine animals	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Live swine, domestic species	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Live sheeps	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Live goats	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand heads	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

EUROSTAT - Roundwood production

General information

Description: Roundwood production (the term is used as a synonymous term for "removals") comprise all quantities of wood removed from the forest and other wooded land or other felling site during a certain period of time. It is reported in cubic metres underbark (i.e. excluding bark).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00072/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: wood industry, wood product, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Wood Products , Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00072/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00072/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00072/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Roundwood	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand cubic metres	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood

Production by Coniferous	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand cubic metres	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood
Production by non-coniferous	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand cubic metres	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Roundwood

EUROSTAT - Total sawnwood production

General information

Description: Sawnwood: Wood that has been produced either by sawing lengthways or by a profile-chipping process and that exceeds 6 mm in thickness. It includes planks, beams, joists, boards, rafters, scantlings, laths, boxboards and "lumber", etc., in the following forms: unplaned, planed, end-jointed, etc. It is reported in cubic metres solid volume (m³).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00073/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: wood product, wood industry, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Wood Products , Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00073/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00073/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00073/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sawnwood	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand cubic metres	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	sawnwood

EUROSTAT - Total paper and paperboard production

General information

Description: "Paper and paper board" comprises the sum of graphic papers; sanitary and household papers; packaging materials and other paper and paperboard. It excludes manufactured paper products such as boxes, cartons, books and magazines.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00074/default/table?lang=en>

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: forest, forestry economics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Wood Products

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: October 22, 2021

Issued:

Last update: February 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00074/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00074/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tag00074/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Forest Area	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Paper production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2008 - December, 2021	Instant value		

Paperboard production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tonnes	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value		
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EUROSTAT - Air emissions accounts by NACE Rev. 2 activity

General information

Description: This data set reports the emissions of greenhouse gases and air pollutants broken down by 64 industries (classified by NACE Rev. 2) plus households. Concepts and principles are the same as in national accounts. Complete data starts from reference year 2008.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link:

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Environment and energy

Subjects: atmospheric pollution, air quality policy, Environment, Atmospheric conditions

Useful for the analysis of: Climate change, Environmental policy, Air emissions intensities

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: energy statistics/balances., national emission inventories

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 23, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 10, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1995 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	TSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_ainah_r2/default/table?lang=en	TSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_ainah_r2/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_ainah_r2/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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[GHG] Greenhouse gases (CO ₂ , N ₂ O in CO ₂ equivalent, CH ₄ in CO ₂ equivalent, HFC in CO ₂ equivalent, PFC in CO ₂ equivalent, SF ₆ in CO ₂ equivalent, NF ₃ in CO ₂ equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CO ₂] Carbon dioxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CO] Carbon monoxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NF ₃ _SF ₆ _CO ₂ E] Nitrogen trifluoride and sulphur hexafluoride (CO ₂ equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CO ₂ _BIO] Carbon dioxide from biomass used as a fuel	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[ACG] Acidifying gases (SO _x in SO ₂ equivalent, NO _x in SO ₂ equivalent, NH ₃ in SO ₂ equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[SO _x _SO ₂ E] Sulphur oxides (SO ₂ equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)

[NOX_SO2E] Nitrogen oxides (SO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CO_NMVOCE] Carbon monoxide (NMVOC equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CH4_NMVOCE] Methane (NMVOC equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CH4] Methane	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[CH4_CO2E] Methane (CO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[N2O] Nitrous oxide	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NOX] Nitrogen oxides	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[HFC_CO2E] Hydrofluorocarbones (CO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[PFC_CO2E] Perfluorocarbones (CO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NH3_SO2E] Ammonia (SO2 equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)

[O3PR] Ozone precursors (NMVOC, NOX in NMVOC equivalent, CO in NMVOC equivalent, CH4 in NMVOC equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NOX_NMVOCE] Nitrogen oxides (NMVOC equivalent)	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NH3] Ammonia	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[PM2_5] Particulates < 2.5µm	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[PM10] Particulates < 10µm	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)
[NMVOC] Non-methane volatile organic compounds	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry (NACE: A)

EUROSTAT - Air emissions intensities by NACE Rev. 2 activity

General information

Description: This data set presents intensity-ratios relating AEA emissions to economic parameters (value added, production output) for 64 industries (classified by NACE Rev. 2).

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_aeint_r2/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Environment and energy

Subjects: atmospheric pollution, Environment, Atmospheric conditions

Useful for the analysis of: Air emissions intensities, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: energy statistics/balances., national emission inventories

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 23, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 3, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1995 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
TSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_aeint_r2/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
SDMX-CSV	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_aeint_r2/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_aeint_r2/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis

Greenhouse gases	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Carbon dioxide [CO2]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Methane [CH4]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Methane (CO2 equivalent) [CH4_CO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrous oxide [N2O]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrous oxide (CO2 equivalent) [N2O_CO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Hydrofluorocarbones (CO2 equivalent) [HFC_CO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Perfluorocarbones (CO2 equivalent) [PFC_CO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrogen trifluoride and sulphur hexafluoride (CO2 equivalent) [NF3_SF6_CO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Carbon dioxide from biomass used as a fuel [CO2_BIO]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)

Acidifying gases (SOX in SO2 equivalent, NOX in SO2 equivalent, NH3 in SO2 equivalent) [ACG]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Sulphur oxides (SO2 equivalent) [SOX_SO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrogen oxides (SO2 equivalent) [NOX_SO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Ammonia (SO2 equivalent) [NH3_SO2E]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Ozone precursors (NMVOC, NOX in NMVOC equivalent, CO in NMVOC equivalent, CH4 in NMVOC equivalent) [O3PR]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrogen oxides (NMVOC equivalent) [NOX_NMVOCE]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Carbon monoxide [CO]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Carbon monoxide (NMVOC equivalent) [CO_NMVOCE]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)

Methane (NMVOC equivalent) [CH4_NMVOCE]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Nitrogen oxides [NOX]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Ammonia [NH3]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Particulates < 2.5µm [PM2_5]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Particulates < 10µm [PM10]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)
Non-methane volatile organic compounds [NMVOC]	Socioeconomic variable	Gram per Euro	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (NACE Rev.2: A01)

FAO - Temperature change

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT Temperature Change domain disseminates statistics of mean surface temperature change by country, with annual updates. The current dissemination covers the period 1961–2020. Statistics are available for monthly, seasonal and annual mean temperature anomalies, i.e., temperature change with respect to a baseline climatology, corresponding to the period 1951–1980. The standard deviation of the temperature change of the baseline methodology is also available.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/ET>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: environmental impact, environmental monitoring, climate change, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Temperature change

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: GISTEMP

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 27, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/ET	Excel XLS	False
csv	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/ET	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
March	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
February	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
August	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
May	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
April	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
June	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
January	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	

July	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
September	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
October	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
November	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
December	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
Dec-Jan-Feb	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
Mar-Apr-May	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
Jun-Jul-Aug	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
Sep-Oct-Nov	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	
Meteorological year	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Standard Deviation	Socioeconomic variable	Celsius degrees °C	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November, December, Dec-Jan-Feb, Mar-Apr-May, Jun-Jul-Aug, Sep-Oct-Nov, Meteorological year

Temperature change	Socioeconomic variable	Celsius degrees °C	January, 1961 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November, December, Dec-Jan-Feb, Mar-Apr-May, Jun-Jul-Aug, Sep-Oct-Nov, Meteorological year
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FAO - Burning - Crop Residues

General information

Description: Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions from burning crop residues consist of methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) gases produced by the combustion of a percentage of crop residues burnt on-site.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GB>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Climate Change

Subjects: biomass, methane, nitrous oxide, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Greenhouse gas emissions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: data are sourced from the most recently available GHG National Inventories (NGHGI) or from National Communications.

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GB	CSV	False
Excel (xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GB	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Maize	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Rice, paddy	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Wheat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Sugar cane	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Biomass burned (dry matter)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Maize, Rice, paddy, Sugar cane, Wheat
Emissions (N2O)	Socioeconomic variable	kiloTonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Maize, Rice, paddy, Sugar cane, Wheat

Emissions (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	kiloTonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Maize, Rice, paddy, Sugar cane, Wheat
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OECD - Land cover in Functional Urban Areas

General information

Description: Land cover 'snapshots' for a given year provide context against which the conversions detailed above can be evaluated. This multi-class dataset allows for analysis of changes in land cover consistently at the global scale. It builds on decades of Earth observation missions by different national and supranational space organisations.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_FUA

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: land use, Environment, Regions and cities

Useful for the analysis of: land use, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Japan, South Korea

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1992 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_FUA#	XML	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_FUA#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_FUA#	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_FUA#	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Land cover in Functional Urban Areas	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Geonames	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Tree cover	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Grassland	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Wetland	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Shrubland	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Sparse vegetation	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Cropland	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Artificial surfaces	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Bare area	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas
Inland water	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total Area	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Irregular	Land cover in Functional Urban Areas

FAO - Rice Cultivation

General information

Description: Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from rice cultivation consist of methane gas from the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter in paddy fields. The FAOSTAT emissions database is computed following Tier 1 IPCC 2006 Guidelines for National GHG Inventories.

The FAOSTAT domain Rice Cultivation disseminates information on: area harvested of paddy rice (1000 ha) and methane emissions (kilotonnes CH₄). Data are available for most countries and territories, for standard FAOSTAT regional aggregations, and for Annex I and non-Annex I groups.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GR>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Climate Change

Subjects: atmospheric pollution, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area, Rice production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: ctivity data are sourced from the most recently available GHG National Inventories (NGHGI) or from National Communications.

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GR	CSV	False
Excel (xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GR	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Rice, paddy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area harvested	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Rice, paddy
Emissions (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Rice, paddy

FAO - Capital Stock

General information

Description: As part of the FAO Agriculture Capital Stock (ACS) database, ESS-FAO publishes country-by-country data on physical investment in agriculture, forestry and fishing as measured by the System of National Accounts (SNA) concept of Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF). Additional variables included in the ACS are Net and Gross Capital Stock, Consumption of Fixed Capital, the Agriculture Investment ratio, and the Gross Fixed Capital Formation Agriculture Orientation Index. The FAO Agriculture Capital Stock Database is an analytical database: whenever available, the database integrates official National Accounts data harvested from the UNSD National Accounts Main Aggregates Database (UNSD AMA) and the OECD Annual National Accounts Database (OECD ANA).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CS>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Macrostatistics

Subjects: economy, financial policy, economic policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Capital Stock

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: UNSD Official Country Data, OECD Annual National Accounts, OECD Structural Analysis Database., <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/snaama/Introduction.asp>; <http://stats.oecd.org/>.

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 10, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1995 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CS	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CS	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Consumption of Fixed Capital (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1995 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
Gross Fixed Capital	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1995 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	

Formation (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)						
Net Capital Stocks (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1995 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
Gross Capital Stocks (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1995 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	

OECD - Environmentally related tax revenue accounts

General information

Description: This dataset presents the data collected from OECD and partner economies on environmentally related tax revenue accounts with a breakdown by tax-base category and industrial activity.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ERTR_ACC

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: tax, environmental policy, Environment, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: September 1, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ERTR_ACC#	XML	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ERTR_ACC#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ERTR_ACC#	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ERTR_ACC#	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Total industry ISIC rev. 4	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Country	100	
Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Country	100	
Mining and quarrying industry	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total Tax revenue	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Total industry ISIC rev. 4, Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry, Mining and quarrying industry
Energy Tax revenue	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Total industry ISIC rev. 4, Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry, Mining and quarrying industry
Energy related GHG emissions Tax revenue	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Total industry ISIC rev. 4, Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry, Mining and quarrying industry
Transport Tax revenue	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Total industry ISIC rev. 4, Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry, Mining and quarrying industry
Pollution Tax revenue	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Total industry ISIC rev. 4, Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry, Mining and quarrying industry

FAO - Trade Indices

General information

Description: The food and agricultural trade dataset is collected, processed and disseminated by FAO according to the standard International Merchandise Trade Statistics (IMTS) Methodology. The data is mainly provided by UNSD, Eurostat, and other national authorities as needed. This source data is checked for outliers, trade partner data is used for non-reporting countries or missing cells, and data on food aid is added to take into account total cross-border trade flows. The trade database includes the following variables: export quantity, export value, import quantity, and import value. The trade database includes all food and agricultural products imported/exported annually by all the countries in the world.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TI>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Trade

Subjects: trade policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: The main source is official country statistics compiled by UNSD and Eurostat

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:
Last update: February 22, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Csv	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TI	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/TI	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Products	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Food Excluding Fish	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals and Preparations	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Fats and Oils (excluding Butter)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Vegetable Oil and Fat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Meat and Meat Preparations	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Bovine Meat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Poultry Meat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Natural Rubber	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Fodder and feeding stuff	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Non-edible Crude materials	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Flowers	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Textile	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Hides and skins	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Crude materials nes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Non-edible fats and oils	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Tobacco	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Fruit	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Vegetables	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Pulses	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Roots and Tubers	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Nuts	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Sugar Crops Primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Dairy Products and eggs	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Dairy products	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Eggs	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Beverages	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Alcoholic beverages	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Non-alcoholic beverages	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Other food	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Live Animals	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Oilseeds	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Other food nes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Non-food	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Other Meat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Pigmeat	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Sugar and Honey	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Fruit and Vegetables	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Import Value Base Period Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	usd	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Import Value Base Period Price	Socioeconomic variable	usd	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter),

						Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Export Value Base Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	usd	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Export Value Base Price	Socioeconomic variable	usd	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter),

						Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Import Value Index (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Import Unit/Value	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter),

Index (2014-2016 = 100)						Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Import Quantity Index (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco

Export Value Index (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmear , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco
Export Unit/Value Index (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	index	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmear , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco

<p>Export Quantity Index (2014-2016 = 100)</p>	<p>Socioeconomic variable</p>	<p>index</p>	<p>January, 1961 - December, 2019</p>	<p>Instant value</p>	<p>Annual</p>	<p>Agricultural Products, Cereals and Preparations , Food Excluding Fish, Cereals, Fats and Oils (excluding Butter), Animal Fats and Oils (excl. Butter) , Vegetable Oil and Fat , Meat and Meat Preparations , Bovine Meat , Poultry Meat , Pigmeat , Other Meat , Sugar and Honey , Fruit and Vegetables, Fruit , Vegetables, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Nuts, Sugar Crops Primary, Dairy Products and eggs, Dairy products, Eggs, Beverages, Alcoholic beverages, Non-alcoholic beverages, Other food, Live Animals, Oilseeds, Other food nes , Non-food, Fodder and feeding stuff, Non-edible Crude materials, Flowers, Natural Rubber, Textile, Hides and skins, Crude materials nes , Non-edible fats and oils, Tobacco</p>
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OECD - Generation and discharge of wastewater

General information

Description:

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: waste management

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type:**Was generated by:****Is referenced by:**

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Chile, Czechia, Denmark, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 25, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1999 - December, 2019

Keywords: water, wastewater, discharge

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#	Excel XLS	False
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WATER_DISCHARGE#	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge	January, 1999 - December, 2019		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis

Biochemical oxygen demand	Socioeconomic variable	1000 kg O ₂ /day	January, 2000 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge
Chemical oxygen demand	Socioeconomic variable	1000 kg O ₂ /day	January, 2000 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge
Total nitrogen	Socioeconomic variable	1000 kg/day	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge
Total phosphorus	Socioeconomic variable	1000 kg/day	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge
Suspended solids	Socioeconomic variable	1000 kg/day	January, 2000 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge
Volume	Socioeconomic variable	Million m ³ /year	January, 1999 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural (incl. forestry + fisheries) wastewater, all sources, direct discharge

FAO - Land use indicators

General information

Description: The Agri-environmental Indicators—Land Use domain provides information on the distribution of agricultural and forest land, and their sub-components, including irrigated areas and areas under organic agriculture, at national, regional and global levels.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EL>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: land use, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: land use, Use of agricultural area, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EL	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EL	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Share in Agricultural land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Share in Cropland	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Share in Forest land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Share in Land area	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agricultural Land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Land area
Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land

Land under permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land
Cropland	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land, Share in Land area
Land under perm. meadows and pastures	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land, Share in Land area
Agriculture area actually irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land
Land area equipped for irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land, Share in Cropland
Forest land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Land area
Planted forest	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Forest land
Naturally regenerating forest	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Forest land
Agriculture area under organic agric.	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Share in Agricultural land

FAO - Food Balances (2014-)

General information

Description: Food Balance Sheet presents a comprehensive picture of the pattern of a country's food supply during a specified reference period. The food balance sheet shows for each food item - i.e. each primary commodity and a number of processed commodities potentially available for human consumption - the sources of supply and its utilization.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FBS>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Food Balance

Subjects: agri-foodstuffs, food industry, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Food Balance

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: The main source is official statistics from FAO member countries

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 11, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2014 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FBS	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FBS	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sugar Crops	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Sugar & Sweeteners	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Pulses	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Treenuts	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Oilcrops	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Vegetable Oils	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Vegetables	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Fruits - Excluding Wine	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	

Stimulants	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Spices	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Vegetal products	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Animal products	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Cereals	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Starchy Roots	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Alcoholic Beverages	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Meat	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Offals	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Animal fats	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Eggs	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Milk - Excluding Butter	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Fish, Seafood	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Aquatic Products, Other	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Miscellaneous	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	

Acquatic products	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products, Miscellaneous, Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops
Stock Variation	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products, Miscellaneous
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal

						fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products, Miscellaneous
Domestic supply quantity	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products, Miscellaneous
Feed	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood
Seed	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Pulses, Oilcrops, Vegetables, Eggs, Fish, Seafood
Losses	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter
Processed	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Milk - Excluding Butter
Other uses (non-food)	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal

						fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products
Tourist consumption	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Miscellaneous
Residuals	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Miscellaneous
Food	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Cereals, Starchy Roots, Sugar Crops, Sugar & Sweeteners , Pulses, Treenuts, Oilcrops, Vegetable Oils , Vegetables, Fruits - Excluding Wine , Stimulants, Spices, Alcoholic Beverages , Meat, Offals, Animal fats , Eggs, Milk - Excluding Butter , Fish, Seafood , Acquatic products, Miscellaneous

OECD - Land cover change in countries and regions

General information

Description: These data refer to the percentage of tree cover, grassland, wetland, shrubland and sparse vegetation converted to any other land cover type.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_CHANGE

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: land use, Land cover, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Continuous

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Copernicus/European Space Agency and Université catholique de Louvain Geomatics Climate Change Initiative, OECD Territorial grid, FAO Global Administrative Unit Layers (GAUL 2014), OECD-EU Functional Urban Area

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Afghanistan, Angola, Anguilla, Albania, Andorra, Netherlands Antilles, United Arab Emirates, Argentina, Armenia, American Samoa, Antarctica, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Burundi, Belgium, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Bulgaria, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belize, Bermuda, Bolivia, Brazil, Barbados, Brunei, Bhutan, Bouvet Island, Botswana, Belarus, Central African Republic, Canada, Cocos (Keeling) Islands, Switzerland, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Congo, Cook Islands, Colombia, Comoros, Cabo Verde, Costa Rica, Cuba, Christmas Island, Cayman Islands, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Djibouti, Dominica, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Ecuador, Egypt, Eritrea, Western Sahara, Spain, Estonia, Ethiopia, Finland, Fiji, Falkland Islands, French Southern and Antarctic Lands, France, Faroes, Micronesia, Gabon, United Kingdom, Georgia, Guernsey, Ghana, Gibraltar, Guinea, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Equatorial Guinea, Greece, Grenada, Greenland, Guatemala, Guam, Guyana, Hong Kong, Heard Island and McDonald Islands, Honduras, Croatia, Haiti, Hungary, Indonesia, Isle of Man, India, British Indian Ocean Territory, Ireland, Iran, Iraq, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Jersey, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Cambodia, Kiribati, Saint Kitts and Nevis, South Korea, Kuwait,

Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Libya, Saint Lucia, Liechtenstein, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Macau, Morocco, Moldova, Madagascar, Maldives, Mexico, Marshall Islands, North Macedonia, Mali, Malta, Myanmar/Burma, Montenegro, Mongolia, Northern Mariana Islands, Mozambique, Mauritania, Montserrat, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Namibia, New Caledonia, Niger, Norfolk Island, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Niue, Netherlands, Norway, Nepal, Nauru, New Zealand, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Pitcairn Islands, Peru, Philippines, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Poland, Puerto Rico, North Korea, Portugal, Paraguay, Palestine, French Polynesia, Qatar, Romania, Russia, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Senegal, Singapore, South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha, Svalbard and Jan Mayen, Solomon Islands, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, San Marino, Somalia, Saint Pierre and Miquelon, Serbia, South Sudan, São Tomé and Príncipe, Suriname, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Eswatini, Seychelles, Syria, Turks and Caicos Islands, Chad, Togo, Thailand, Tajikistan, Tokelau, Turkmenistan, Timor-Leste, Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Tuvalu, Taiwan, Tanzania, Uganda, Ukraine, Uruguay, United States, Uzbekistan, Vatican City State, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Venezuela, British Virgin Islands, US Virgin Islands, Vietnam, Vanuatu, Wallis and Futuna, Samoa, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Continuous

Temporal extent: January, 1992 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_CHANGE	XML	False
PC-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_CHANGE	PC-AXIS	False

Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_CHANGE	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER_CHANGE	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Land cover change	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
To natural and semi natural vegetated land total	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Continuous	Land cover change
From natural and semi natural vegetated land total	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1992 - December, 2019	Instant value	Continuous	Land cover change

OECD - Tariffs on Environmental Goods

General information

Description: This indicator reports the import-weighted applied tariffs on environmentally related goods as defined in the Combined List of Environmental Goods (CLEG) in percentage points for all countries between 2003 and 2016.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND9

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: environmental monitoring, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 2, 2021

Issued:

Last update: May 1, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2003 - December, 2016

Keywords: environment

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND9	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND9	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND9	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND9	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Tariffs on Environmental Goods	January, 2003 - December, 2016		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Air pollution control	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods

Cleaner or more resource efficient technologies and products	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Environmentally preferable products based on end use or disposal characteristics	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Heat and energy management	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Environmental monitoring, analysis and assessment equipment	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Natural resources protection	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Noise and vibration abatement	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
[DUPLICATED] Air pollution control	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Renewable energy plant	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Management of solid and hazardous	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods

waste and recycling systems						
Clean up or remediation of soil and water	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods
Waste water management and potable water treatment	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2003 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Tariffs on Environmental Goods

OECD - Embodied Materials in Trade

General information

Description: This indicator estimates the total raw materials embedded in the final consumption for all countries between 1990 and 2010. Estimates of this consumption-based material extraction are called material footprint (MF) or raw material consumption (RMC). The different categories of raw materials considered are biomass, fossil fuels, metal ores, and non-metallic minerals.((

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND4

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: trade policy, raw material, ecological footprint, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Database provided by UNEP International Resource Panel

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: May 1, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2010

Keywords: materials, economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND4	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND4	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND4	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND4	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
countries' embodied materials in trade	January, 1990 - December, 2010	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Biomass	Socioeconomic variable	Material Footprint, Material	January, 1990 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	countries' embodied materials in trade

		Footprint of Exports, Material Footprint of Imports				
fossil fuels	Socioeconomic variable	Material Footprint, Material Footprint of Exports, Material Footprint of Imports	January, 1990 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	countries' embodied materials in trade
metal ores	Socioeconomic variable	Material Footprint, Material Footprint of Exports, Material Footprint of Imports	January, 1990 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	countries' embodied materials in trade
non-metallic minerals	Socioeconomic variable	Material Footprint, Material Footprint of Exports, Material Footprint of Imports	January, 1990 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	countries' embodied materials in trade

FAO - Land Use

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT Land Use domain contains data on forty-four categories of land use, irrigation and agricultural practices, relevant to monitor agriculture, forestry and fisheries activities at national, regional and global level.

Areas values are in 1000 ha (hectares); Carbon stocks values (for forest category only) are in million tonnes.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RL>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Inputs

Subjects: land use, Land use, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAO Land Use, Irrigation and Agricultural Practices questionnaires

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/RL	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/RL	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Perm. meadows & pastures area actually irrig.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area under conservation tillage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Farm buildings & farmyards	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land used for aquaculture	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Inland waters used for aquac. or holding facilities	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Inland waters used for capture fisheries	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
EEZ used for aquac. or holding facilities	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area under zero or no tillage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Coastal waters used for aquac. or holding facilities	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Aquaculture and Fisheries	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Primary Forest	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Coastal waters used for capture fisheries	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
EEZ used for capture fisheries	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land use	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Country area	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land area	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Agriculture	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Agricultural land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Arable land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land under temporary crops	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land under temp. meadows and pastures	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land with temporary fallow	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Land under permanent crops	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land under perm. meadows and pastures	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Perm. meadows & pastures - Cultivated	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Perm. meadows & pastures - Nat. growing	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land under protective cover	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Forest land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Naturally regenerating forest	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Planted Forest	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Other land	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Water	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Inland waters	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Coastal waters	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land area equipped for irrigation	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Land area actually irrigated	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Agriculture area actually irrigated	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area actually irrigated	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Forestry area actually irrigated	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Agricultural practices	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Agriculture area under organic agric.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Agriculture area certified organic	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area under organic agric.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area certified organic	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Perm. meadows & pastures area under organic agric.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Perm. meadows & pastures area certified organic	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cropland area under conventional tillage	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha (hectares)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Cropland area under conservation tillage, Farm buildings & farmyards, Land used for aquaculture, Inland waters used for aquac. or holding facilities, Inland waters used for capture fisheries, EEZ used for aquac. or

						holding facilities, Cropland area under zero or no tillage, Coastal waters used for aquac. or holding facilities, Aquaculture and Fisheries, Primary Forest, Coastal waters used for capture fisheries, EEZ used for capture fisheries, Land use, Country area, Land area, Agriculture, Agricultural land, Cropland, Arable land, Land under temporary crops, Land under temp. meadows and pastures, Land with temporary fallow, Land under permanent crops, Land under perm. meadows and pastures, Perm. meadows & pastures - Cultivated, Perm. meadows & pastures - Nat. growing, Land under protective cover, Forest land, Naturally regenerating forest, Planted Forest, Other land, Water, Inland waters, Coastal waters, Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), Land area equipped for irrigation, Land area actually irrigated, Agriculture area actually irrigated, Cropland area actually irrigated, Perm. meadows & pastures area actually irrig., Forestry area actually irrigated, Agricultural practices, Agriculture area under organic agric., Agriculture area certified organic, Cropland area under organic agric., Cropland area certified organic, Perm. meadows & pastures area under organic agric., Perm. meadows & pastures area certified organic, Cropland area under conventional tillage
Carbon stock in living biomass	Socioeconomic variable	million tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Cropland area under conservation tillage, Farm buildings & farmyards, Land used for aquaculture, Inland waters used for aquac. or holding facilities, Inland waters used for

						<p>capture fisheries, EEZ used for aquac. or holding facilities, Cropland area under zero or no tillage, Coastal waters used for aquac. or holding facilities, Aquaculture and Fisheries, Primary Forest, Coastal waters used for capture fisheries, EEZ used for capture fisheries, Land use, Country area, Land area, Agriculture, Agricultural land, Cropland, Arable land, Land under temporary crops, Land under temp. meadows and pastures, Land with temporary fallow, Land under permanent crops, Land under perm. meadows and pastures, Perm. meadows & pastures - Cultivated, Perm. meadows & pastures - Nat. growing, Land under protective cover, Forest land, Naturally regenerating forest, Planted Forest, Other land, Water, Inland waters, Coastal waters, Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), Land area equipped for irrigation, Land area actually irrigated, Agriculture area actually irrigated, Cropland area actually irrigated, Perm. meadows & pastures area actually irrig., Forestry area actually irrigated, Agricultural practices, Agriculture area under organic agric., Agriculture area certified organic, Cropland area under organic agric., Cropland area certified organic, Perm. meadows & pastures area under organic agric., Perm. meadows & pastures area certified organic, Cropland area under conventional tillage</p>
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FAO - Synthetic Fertilizers

General information

Description: Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from synthetic fertilizers consist of nitrous oxide gas from synthetic nitrogen additions to managed soils. Specifically, N₂O is produced by microbial processes of nitrification and de-nitrification taking place on the addition site (direct emissions), and after volatilization/re-deposition and leaching processes (indirect emissions).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GY>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Climate Change

Subjects: fertiliser, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Fertilizers indicators

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: May 31, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords: nutrients, environment, emissions

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GY/metadata	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GY/metadata	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nutrient nitrogen N (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agricultural use in nutrients	Socioeconomic variable	kg of nutrients	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Nitrogen fertilizer content applied that leaches	Socioeconomic variable	kg of nutrients	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Nitrogen fertilizer	Socioeconomic variable	kg of nutrients	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)

content applied that volatilises						
Direct emissions (N ₂ O) (Synthetic fertilizers)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Direct emissions (N ₂ O that leaches) (Synthetic fertilizers)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Direct emissions (N ₂ O that volatilises) (Synthetic fertilizers)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Indirect emissions (N ₂ O that volatilises) (Synthetic fertilizers)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)
Emissions (N ₂ O that volatilises) (Synthetic fertilizers)	Socioeconomic variable	kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N (total)

FAO - Fertilizers by Nutrient

General information

Description: The Fertilizers by Nutrient dataset contains information on the totals in nutrients for Production, Trade and Agriculture Use of inorganic (chemical or mineral) fertilizers, over the time series 1961-present.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFN>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Land, Inputs and Sustainability

Subjects: fertiliser, Environment, Exports of goods, Imports of goods

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, production indices

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: http://fenixservices.fao.org/faostat/static/documents/RFN/RFN_EN_README.pdf

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFN	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFN	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nutrient nitrogen N	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Nutrient phosphate P205	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Nutrient potash K20 (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N , Nutrient phosphate P205, Nutrient potash K20 (total)
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N , Nutrient phosphate P205, Nutrient potash K20 (total)
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N , Nutrient phosphate P205, Nutrient potash K20 (total)

Agricultural Use	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient nitrogen N , Nutrient phosphate P205, Nutrient potash K20 (total)
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FAO - Supply Utilization Accounts

General information

Description: The food balance sheet shows for each food item - i.e. each primary commodity and a number of processed commodities potentially available for human consumption - the sources of supply and its utilization.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/SCL>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Food Balance

Subjects: agricultural statistics, export policy, import policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Imports of goods, Exports of goods

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2014 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/SCL	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/SCL	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Crops primary	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Crops processed	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Grand total	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Livestock primary	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	
Livestock processed	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Import quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Stock variation	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Export quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Feed	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Seed	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Loss	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Processed	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Tourist consumption	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Other uses (non-food)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed

Residuals	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Food	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Food supply	Socioeconomic variable	kcal/capita/day	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed
Food supply quantity	Socioeconomic variable	g/capita/day	January, 2014 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops primary, Crops processed, Grand total, Livestock primary, Livestock processed

OECD - Surface water and surface water change

General information

Description: Surface water and surface water change.

Surface water changes impact in different ways on biodiversity and climate. Both surface water gains and losses have biodiversity costs and impacts on ecosystem service provision.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SURFACE_WATER

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: water, water policy, environmental policy, Environment, Oceanographic geographical features

Useful for the analysis of: Water change

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Surface water: Joint Research Centre & Pekel et al. (2016) High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes supporting data, Political and administrative boundaries: FAO (2015) Global Administrative Unit Layers (GAUL)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2018

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1984 - December, 2015

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SURFACE_WATER#	SDMX	False
PC-AXIS	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SURFACE_WATER#	PC-AXIS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SURFACE_WATER#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SURFACE_WATER#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Countries' surface water and surface water change	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Maximum water extent since 1984	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total country area and Square kilometers	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	
Permanent water	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total country area and Square kilometers	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	
Seasonal water	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total country area and Square kilometers	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	
Always seasonal water since 1984	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total country area and Square kilometers	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	
Always permanent water since 1984	Socioeconomic variable	Percent of total country area and Square kilometers	January, 1984 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	

OECD - Agri-Environmental indicators: Nutrients

General information

Description: This dataset shows nutrients as agri-environmental indicators.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: environmental impact, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Europe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 30, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2014

Keywords: nutrients, environment

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_NUTRIENTS	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nitrogen	January, 2000 - December, 2014		100	
Phosphorus	January, 2000 - December, 2014		100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Nutrient inputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

Total fertilizers	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total inorganic fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total organic fertilizers (excluding livestock manure)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Net input of manure	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Livestock manure production	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total cattle	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total poultry	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total other livestock	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total manure withdrawals	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Manure imports	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Other nutrient inputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

Atmospheric deposition	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Biological fixation	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total seeds and planting materials	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient outputs	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total harvested crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total oil crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total dried pulses and beans	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Other crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total forage	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total harvested fodder crops	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Total pasture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient removal by crop	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

residues removed from the field						
Balance (inputs minus outputs)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Nutrient removal by crop residues burned from the field	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Instant value	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus
Balance per hectare	Socioeconomic variable	Kilograms	January, 2000 - December, 2014	Average	Annual	Nitrogen, Phosphorus

OECD - Nutrient Balance of Exports

General information

Description: The indicator reports the nutrient balance of nitrogen and phosphorus – the difference between the quantity of nutrient inputs entering an agricultural system and the quantity of nutrient outputs leaving this system – for exports of nine cereal and oilseed (hence excluding pasture) as a share of the total nutrient balance for 21 countries in years 2006, 2007, 2010 and 2014. Grains covered by this indicator are wheat, maize, barley, sorghum, oats, rice soybeans, sunflower seed and rapeseed.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND6

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: export monitoring, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Cyprus, Czechia, East Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:
Last update: May 1, 2019

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2006 - December, 2014

Keywords: nutrients, exports

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND6	SDMX	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND6	PC-AXIS	False
Text file (CSV)	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND6	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TRADEENV_IND6	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nitrogen nutrient balance	January, 2006 - December, 2014	Country	100	
Phosphorus nutrient balance	January, 2006 - December, 2014	Country	100	
Share of exported grains	January, 2006 - December, 2014	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Exports	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2006 - December, 2014	Instant value	Irregular	Nitrogen nutrient balance, Phosphorus nutrient balance, Share of exported grains

EUROSTAT - Production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions

General information

Description: This dataset shows the production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions.

Producer: EUROSTAT

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_milkpr/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: animal product, milk product, milk, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Milk Production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Kosovo, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Luxembourg, Latvia, North Macedonia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 5, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
sdmx	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_milkpr/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False
csv	CSV	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_milkpr/default/table?lang=en	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_milkpr/default/table?lang=en	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
countries' production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Products obtained	Socioeconomic variable	1000t	January, 2016 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	countries' production of cow's milk on farms by NUTS 2 regions
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FAO - Fertilizers by Product

General information

Description: The Fertilizers by Product dataset contains information on the Production, Trade and Agriculture Use of inorganic (chemical or mineral) fertilizers products, over the time series 2002-present. The fertilizer statistics data are for a set of 23 product categories. Both straight and compound fertilizers are included.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFB>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Inputs

Subjects: fertiliser, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2002 - December, 2019

Keywords: fertiliser

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFB/metadata	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RFB/metadata	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Phosphate rock	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Ammonia, anhydrous	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Ammonium nitrate (AN)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Ammonium sulphate	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Diammonium phosphate (DAP)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			

Fertilizers n.e.c.	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Other NK compounds	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Monoammonium phosphate (MAP)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
NPK fertilizers	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c.	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Other NP compounds	January, 2002 - December, 2019		100	
Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c.	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c.	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
PK compounds	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Potassium nitrate	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Sodium nitrate	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Superphosphates above 35%	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Urea	January, 2002 - December, 2019			

Superphosphates, other	January, 2002 - December, 2019			
Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN)	January, 2002 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP), Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP),

						Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP), Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP),

						Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%
Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP), Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%
Agricultural use	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 2002 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Ammonium sulphate, Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and other mixtures with calcium carbonate , Fertilizers n.e.c., Other phosphatic fertilizers, n.e.c., Phosphate rock, PK compounds, Potassium chloride (muriate of potash) (MOP), Potassium nitrate, Potassium sulphate (sulphate of potash) (SOP),

						<p>Superphosphates, other, Urea, Ammonia, anhydrous, NPK fertilizers, Other NP compounds , Urea and ammonium nitrate solutions (UAN), Ammonium nitrate (AN), Diammonium phosphate (DAP), Monoammonium phosphate (MAP), Other nitrogenous fertilizers, n.e.c., Other NK compounds, Other potassic fertilizers, n.e.c., Sodium nitrate, Superphosphates above 35%</p>
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FAO - Energy Use

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT emissions database is with global coverage, relative to the period 1970 - 2019, by motor gasoline and by aggregates.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GN>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Emissions

Subjects: energy statistics, reduction of gas emissions, emission trading, Energy, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions, Energy use in agriculture

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT emissions database

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GN	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GN	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Emissions (CH4)	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (N20)	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Use in agriculture	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (CO2)	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gas-Diesel oil	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Motor Gasoline	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)

Natural gas (including LNG)	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG)	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Fuel oil	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Coal	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Electricity	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Gas-diesel oils used in fisheries	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)
Fuel oil used in fisheries	Socioeconomic variable	Terajoule/kilotonnes	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Use in agriculture, Emissions (CO2)

FAO - Fertilizers indicators

General information

Description: The data provides the ratio between the totals by nutrient of agricultural use of chemical or mineral fertilizers, reported in the FAOSTAT domain “Inputs/Fertilizers by Nutrient” for nitrogen (N), phosphorus (expressed as P2O5) and potassium (expressed as K2O), and the area of cropland (sum of arable land and permanent crops) reported in the FAOSTAT domain “Inputs/Land Use”. Data are provided at national, regional, and global level over the time series 1961-present.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EF>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: fertiliser, environmental indicator, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: land use, Fertilizers indicators

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT Inputs / Fertilizers by Nutrient, FAOSTAT Inputs / Land Use

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 8, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/EF	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/EF	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nutrient potash K2O (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Nutrient phosphate P2O5 (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Nutrient nitrogen N (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Use per area of cropland	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ha	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nutrient potash K2O (total), Nutrient phosphate P2O5 (total) , Nutrient nitrogen N (total)

FAO - Credit to Agriculture

General information

Description: The Credit to Agriculture dataset provides national data for over 120 countries on the amount of loans provided by the private/commercial banking sector to producers in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, including household producers, cooperatives, and agro-businesses.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/IC>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Investment

Subjects: credit, agricultural economics

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural credits

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 18, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1991 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/IC	CSV	False
Excel (Xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/IC	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Credit to Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Credit to Agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Credit to Agriculture and Fishery	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry

Credit to Agriculture and Forestry	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Credit to Fishery	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Credit to Forestry	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Credit to Forestry and Fishery	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry
Total Credit	Socioeconomic variable	USD, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	National agriculture, forestry and fisheries industry

FAO - Pesticides Trade

General information

Description: This domain contains data on pesticides and covers two different categories: pesticides traded in form or packaging for retail sale or as preparations or articles, and pesticides traded as separate chemically defined compounds.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RT>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Land, Inputs and Sustainability

Subjects: pesticide, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Pesticides use, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RT	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RT	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Herbicides (excl. Haz. pest.)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Azinphos-methyl	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Fluoroacetamide, monocrotophos & phosphamidon	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Disinfectants, etc (excl. Haz. pest.)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Binapacryl	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Hazardous pesticides	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Rotterdam Convention	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chlordimeform	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Fungicides	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Compounds of mercury chemically defined, excluding amalgams	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Dinoseb and its salts	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Ethylene dichloride	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
DDT (clofenotane (INN))	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Pesticides (total)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Ethylene dibromide (1,2-dibromoethane)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
HCH (mixed isomers)/Lindane	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Mercury compounds etc. excl. amalgams	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Antimalarial insecticides	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Aldrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Insecticides	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Fungicides (excl. Haz. pest.)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Dieldrin	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

2,4,5-T and its salts and esters	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Herbicides	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
DNOC and its salts	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Oxirane (ethylene oxide)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Parathion & parathion-methyl	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Alachlor	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Disinfectants, etc	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Tributyltin compounds	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Aldicarb, captafol & methamidophos	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Insecticides (excl. Haz. pest.)	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Chlorobenzilate	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Dinoseb acetate	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Endosulfan	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
DDT, Hexachlorobenzene	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Pentachlorophenol	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Salts of Pentachlorophenol	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019		Annual	Herbicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Azinphos-methyl, Disinfectants, etc (excl. Haz. pest.), Binapacryl, Hazardous pesticides, Rotterdam Convention , Chlordimeform, Fungicides, Compounds of mercury chemically defined, excluding amalgams, DDT (clofenotane (INN)), Pesticides (total), Antimalarial insecticides, Aldrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor, Insecticides, Fungicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Dieldrin, 2,4,5-T and its salts and esters, Herbicides, Alachlor, Disinfectants, etc, Aldicarb, captafol & methamidophos, Insecticides (excl. Haz. pest.), Chlorobenzilate, Dinoseb acetate, DDT, Hexachlorobenzene, Dinoseb and its salts, DNOC and its salts, Endosulfan, Ethylene dibromide (1,2-dibromoethane), Ethylene dichloride, Fluoroacetamide, monocrotophos & phosphamidon, HCH (mixed isomers)/Lindane, Mercury compounds etc. excl. amalgams, Oxirane (ethylene oxide), Parathion & parathion-methyl, Pentachlorophenol, Salts of Pentachlorophenol, Tributyltin compounds
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019		Annual	Herbicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Azinphos-methyl, Disinfectants, etc (excl. Haz. pest.), Binapacryl, Hazardous pesticides, Rotterdam Convention , Chlordimeform,

						<p>Fungicides, Compounds of mercury chemically defined, excluding amalgams, DDT (clofenotane (INN)), Pesticides (total), Antimalarial insecticides, Aldrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor, Insecticides, Fungicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Dieldrin, 2,4,5-T and its salts and esters, Herbicides, Alachlor, Disinfectants, etc, Aldicarb, captafol & methamidophos, Insecticides (excl. Haz. pest.), Chlorobenzilate, Dinoseb acetate, DDT, Hexachlorobenzene, Dinoseb and its salts, DNOC and its salts, Endosulfan, Ethylene dibromide (1,2-dibromoethane), Ethylene dichloride, Fluoroacetamide, monocrotophos & phosphamidon, HCH (mixed isomers)/Lindane, Mercury compounds etc. excl. amalgams, Oxirane (ethylene oxide), Parathion & parathion-methyl, Pentachlorophenol, Salts of Pentachlorophenol, Tributyltin compounds</p>
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 1961 - December, 2019		Annual	<p>Herbicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Azinphos-methyl, Disinfectants, etc (excl. Haz. pest.), Binapacryl, Hazardous pesticides, Rotterdam Convention , Chlordimeform, Fungicides, Compounds of mercury chemically defined, excluding amalgams, DDT (clofenotane (INN)), Pesticides (total), Antimalarial insecticides, Aldrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor, Insecticides, Fungicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Dieldrin, 2,4,5-T and its salts and esters, Herbicides, Alachlor, Disinfectants, etc, Aldicarb, captafol & methamidophos, Insecticides (excl. Haz. pest.), Chlorobenzilate, Dinoseb acetate, DDT, Hexachlorobenzene, Dinoseb</p>

						and its salts, DNOC and its salts, Endosulfan, Ethylene dibromide (1,2-dibromoethane), Ethylene dichloride, Fluoroacetamide, monocrotophos & phosphamidon, HCH (mixed isomers)/Lindane, Mercury compounds etc. excl. amalgams, Oxirane (ethylene oxide), Parathion & parathion-methyl, Pentachlorophenol, Salts of Pentachlorophenol, Tributyltin compounds
Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	1000 US\$	January, 1961 - December, 2019		Annual	Herbicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Azinphos-methyl, Disinfectants, etc (excl. Haz. pest.), Binapacryl, Hazardous pesticides, Rotterdam Convention , Chlordimeform, Fungicides, Compounds of mercury chemically defined, excluding amalgams, DDT (clofenotane (INN)), Pesticides (total), Antimalarial insecticides, Aldrin, Chlordane, Heptachlor, Insecticides, Fungicides (excl. Haz. pest.), Dieldrin, 2,4,5-T and its salts and esters, Herbicides, Alachlor, Disinfectants, etc, Aldicarb, captafol & methamidophos, Insecticides (excl. Haz. pest.), Chlorobenzilate, Dinoseb acetate, DDT, Hexachlorobenzene, Dinoseb and its salts, DNOC and its salts, Endosulfan, Ethylene dibromide (1,2-dibromoethane), Ethylene dichloride, Fluoroacetamide, monocrotophos & phosphamidon, HCH (mixed isomers)/Lindane, Mercury compounds etc. excl. amalgams, Oxirane (ethylene oxide), Parathion & parathion-methyl, Pentachlorophenol, Salts of Pentachlorophenol, Tributyltin compounds

FAO - Enteric Fermentation

General information

Description: This FAOSTAT domain also disseminates the activity data and emissions reported by countries to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), under the category 'Enteric fermentation'.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GE/metadata>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Emissions

Subjects: emission trading, greenhouse gas, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Greenhouse gas emissions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT domains Production/Live animals, GHG National Inventories (NGHGI), UNFCCC

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GE	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GE	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Asses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Camels	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, breeding	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Swine, market	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Cattle, non-dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Llamas	January, 1961 - December, 2019			
Mules	January, 1961 - December, 2019			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Head/Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			Asses, Buffaloes, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Swine, market
Emissions (CH ₄)	Socioeconomic variable	Head/Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019			Asses, Buffaloes, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Swine, market

FAO - Suite of Food Security Indicators

General information

Description: Suite of Food Security Indicators presents the core set of food security indicators. Following the recommendation of experts gathered in the Committee on World Food Security (CFS) Round Table on hunger measurement, hosted at FAO headquarters in September 2011, an initial set of indicators aiming to capture various aspects of food insecurity is presented here.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Food security

Subjects: food security, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: August 20, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1999 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
csv	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS	CSV	False
excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Food Security Indicators' values	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Rail lines density (total route in km per 100 square km of land area)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Gross domestic product per capita, PPP, dissemination (constant 2011 international \$)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

Prevalence of undernourishment (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of people undernourished (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Availability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Featured Indicators	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of undernourishment (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of people undernourished (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of severely food insecure people (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of moderately or severely food	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

insecure people (million)						
Percentage of children under 5 years affected by wasting (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
[DUPLICATED] Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of children under 5 years affected by wasting (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of children under 5 years of age who are stunted (modelled estimates) (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of children under 5 years of age who are stunted (modeled estimates) (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of children under 5 years of age who are overweight	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

(modelled estimates) (percent)						
Number of children under 5 years of age who are overweight (modeled estimates) (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of obesity in the adult population (18 years and older)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of obese adults (18 years and older) (million) Prevalence of anemia among women of reproductive age (15-49 years)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of women of reproductive age (15-49 years) affected by anemia (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding among infants 0-5 months of age	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

Prevalence of low birthweight (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of newborns with low birthweight (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Average dietary energy supply adequacy (percent) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Average value of food production (constant 2004-2006 I\$/cap) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Dietary energy supply used in the estimation of prevalence of undernourishment (kcal/cap/day) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Share of dietary energy supply derived from cereals, roots and tubers (kcal/cap/day) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Share of dietary energy supply derived from cereals, roots and	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

tubers (kcal/cap/day) (3-year average)						
Average protein supply (g/cap/day) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Average supply of protein of animal origin (g/cap/day) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Access	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of severely food insecure people (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of moderately or severely food insecure people (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Stability	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Rail lines density (total route in km per 100 square km of land area)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Gross domestic product per capita, PPP, dissemination	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

(constant 2011 international \$)						
Prevalence of undernourishment (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Number of people undernourished (million)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Cereal import dependency ratio (percent) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percent of arable land equipped for irrigation (percent) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Value of food imports in total merchandise exports (percent) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

Political stability and absence of violence/terrorism (index)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Per capita food production variability (constant 2004-2006 thousand int\$ per capita)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Per capita food supply variability (kcal/cap/day)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Utilization	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of population using safely managed drinking water services (Percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of population using at least basic drinking water services (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of population using safely managed sanitation services (Percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

Percentage of population using at least basic sanitation services (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of children under 5 years affected by wasting (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of children under 5 years of age who are stunted (modelled estimates) (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Percentage of children under 5 years of age who are overweight (modelled estimates) (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of obesity in the adult population (18 years and older)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of anemia among women of reproductive age (15-49 years)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

Prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding among infants 0-5 months of age	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Other	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Prevalence of low birthweight (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Minimum dietary energy requirement (kcal/cap/day)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Average dietary energy requirement (kcal/cap/day)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Coefficient of variation of habitual caloric consumption distribution (real number)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Incidence of caloric losses at retail distribution level (percent)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values
Average fat supply (g/cap/day) (3-year average)	Socioeconomic variable	usd, %, kcal/capita/day, number	January, 1999 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Food Security Indicators' values

FAO - Employment Indicators

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT Employment indicators module contains data on:- Agriculture value added per worker;- Employment in agriculture (absolute numbers and shares, by sex);- Share of Employees in agriculture (by sex);- Labour force participation in rural areas (by sex);- Employment-to-population ratio in rural areas (by sex).The series consist of data taken from Labour Force Surveys as available from the original sources, namely the International Labour Organization (ILO).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OE>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Population

Subjects: employment policy, employability, Business, statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics, Employment indicators

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: Labour force survey

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: April 2, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1947 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OE	Excel XLS	False
Excel (Xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OE	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agriculture value added per worker (US\$, 2010 prices)	Socioeconomic variable	USD	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Employment in agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Persons	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Employment in agriculture, female	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Persons	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country

Employment in agriculture, male	Socioeconomic variable	1000 Persons	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Employment-to-population ratio, rural areas	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Employment-to-population ratio, rural areas, female	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Employment-to-population ratio, rural areas, male	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Labour force participation rate, rural areas	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Labour force participation rate, rural areas, female	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Labour force participation rate, rural areas, male	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of employees in agriculture (% of total employees)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of employees in agriculture,	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country

male (% of total male employees)						
Share of employment in agriculture (% of total employment)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of employment in agriculture, female (% of total female employment)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of employment in agriculture, male (% of total male employment)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of female employees in agriculture (% of employees in agriculture)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country
Share of female employment in agriculture (% of employment in agriculture)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1945 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Country

OECD-Land use

General information

Description: The data presented here give information concerning land use state and changes (e.g. agricultural land, forest land).

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_USE

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: land use, Land use, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: land use, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAO

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Aruba, Afghanistan, Angola, Anguilla, Andorra, United Arab Emirates, Argentina, Armenia, American Samoa, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Burundi, Belgium, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Bulgaria, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belize, Bermuda, Bolivia, Brazil, Barbados, Brunei, Bhutan, Botswana, Belarus, Central African Republic, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Congo, Cook Islands, Colombia, Comoros, Cabo Verde, Costa Rica, Cuba, Cayman Islands, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Djibouti, Dominica, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Ecuador, Egypt, Eritrea, Spain, Estonia, Ethiopia, Finland, Fiji, Falkland Islands, France, Faroes, Micronesia, Gabon, United Kingdom, Georgia, Ghana, Gibraltar, Guinea, Guadeloupe, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Equatorial Guinea, Greece, Grenada, Greenland, Guatemala, Guam, Guyana, Hong Kong, Honduras, Croatia, Haiti, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iran, Iraq, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Cambodia, Kiribati, Saint Kitts and Nevis, South Korea, Kuwait, Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Libya, Saint Lucia, Liechtenstein, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Macau, Morocco, Monaco, Moldova, Madagascar, Maldives, Mexico, Marshall Islands, North Macedonia, Mali, Malta, Myanmar/Burma, Mongolia, Northern Mariana Islands, Mozambique, Mauritania, Montserrat, Martinique, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Mayotte, Namibia, New Caledonia, Niger, Norfolk Island, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Niue, Netherlands, Norway, Nepal, Nauru, New Zealand,

Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Pitcairn Islands, Peru, Philippines, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Poland, Puerto Rico, North Korea, Portugal, Paraguay, French Polynesia, Qatar, Romania, Russia, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Senegal, Singapore, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha, Solomon Islands, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, San Marino, Somalia, Saint Pierre and Miquelon, São Tomé and Príncipe, Suriname, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Eswatini, Seychelles, Syria, Turks and Caicos Islands, Chad, Togo, Thailand, Tajikistan, Tokelau, Turkmenistan, Timor-Leste, Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Tuvalu, Taiwan, Tanzania, Uganda, Ukraine, Uruguay, United States, Uzbekistan, Vatican City State, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Venezuela, British Virgin Islands, US Virgin Islands, Vietnam, Vanuatu, Wallis and Futuna, Samoa, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_USE	XML	False
PC-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_USE	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_USE	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_USE	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Land use	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land area	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometres	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Arable land and permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometres	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Permanent meadows and pastures	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometres	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Forest	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometers	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Other areas	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometres	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Arable and cropland % land area	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Meadows and pastures % land area	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Forest % land area	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use
Other % land area	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Land use

OECD - Threatened species

General information

Description: The data presented here show numbers of known species (or assessed) and threatened species with the aim of indicating the state of mammals, birds, freshwater fish, reptiles, amphibians, vascular plants, mosses, lichens and invertebrates.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: protected species, animal welfare, Environment, Species distribution

Useful for the analysis of: Threatened species

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2020 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX (XML)	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE	XML	False
Developer API	JSON	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE	JSON	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WILD_LIFE	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Mammals	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Birds	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Reptiles	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Amphibians	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Fish	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Marine Fish	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Freshwater fish	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Vascular plants	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Mosses	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Lichens	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Invertebrates	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Threatened species as % of known species	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Mammals, Birds, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Marine Fish, Freshwater fish, Vascular plants, Mosses, Lichens, Invertebrates
Number of critically endangered species	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Mammals, Birds, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Marine Fish, Freshwater fish, Vascular plants, Mosses, Lichens, Invertebrates

Number of endangered species	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Mammals, Birds, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Marine Fish, Freshwater fish, Vascular plants, Mosses, Lichens, Invertebrates
Number of vulnerable species	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Mammals, Birds, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Marine Fish, Freshwater fish, Vascular plants, Mosses, Lichens, Invertebrates
Total number of threatened species	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Mammals, Birds, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Marine Fish, Freshwater fish, Vascular plants, Mosses, Lichens, Invertebrates

FAO - Pesticides indicators

General information

Description: Agri-environmental indicator on the Use of pesticides per area of cropland (which is the sum of arable land and land under permanent crops) at national level for the period 1990 to 2016.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EP>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: pesticide, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Pesticides use, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 27, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EP	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EP	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Use per area of cropland	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Pesticides (total)	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ha	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Use per area of cropland

FAO - Pesticides Use

General information

Description: The Pesticides Use database includes data on the use of major pesticide groups (Insecticides, Herbicides, Fungicides, Plant growth regulators and Rodenticides) and of relevant chemical families. Data report the quantities (in tonnes of active ingredients) of pesticides used in or sold to the agricultural sector for crops and seeds.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RP>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Inputs

Subjects: pesticide, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Pesticides use, Use of agricultural area, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: July 19, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
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Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Pesticides (total)	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Mineral Oils	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Country		
Insecticides	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Country		
Herbicides	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Country		
Fungicides and Bactericides	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Fungicides – Seed treatments	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Insecticides – Seed Treatments	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Plant Growth Regulators	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Rodenticides	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		
Disinfectants	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Agricultural Use	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Pesticides (total), Mineral Oils , Insecticides , Herbicides, Fungicides and Bactericides , Fungicides – Seed treatments , Insecticides – Seed Treatments , Plant Growth Regulators , Rodenticides, Disinfectants

OECD - Employment by activities and status (ALFS)

General information

Description: The “Employment by activities and status (ALFS)” dataset is a subset of the Annual Labour Force Statistics (ALFS) database which contains annual labour force statistics for the 38 OECD member countries plus Brazil and Russian Federation.

This dataset contains employment and the number of employees

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ALFS_EMP#

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Labour

Subjects: employment policy, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Transport, Economy and finance, Environment, Production and industrial facilities, Transport networks, Utility and governmental services

Useful for the analysis of: Social Sustainability - Work force characteristics

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: <http://www.oecd.org/sdd>

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, United States

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:
Last update: November 25, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
sdmx	SDMX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ALFS_EMP#	SDMX	False
pc-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ALFS_EMP#	PC-AXIS	False
text file csv	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ALFS_EMP#	CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLSX	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=ALFS_EMP#	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Country	100	
FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Country	100	

ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Country	100	
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Employment in all activities	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employment in Agriculture, hunting and forestry	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employment in Industry	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employment in Services	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)

Employment in Industry, Index	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employment in Services, Index	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employees in all activities	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employees in Agriculture, hunting and forestry	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employees in Industry	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
Employees in Services	Socioeconomic variable	persons, thousands	January, 2008 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	MALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), FEMALES - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS), ALL PERSONS - Countries' Employment by activities and status (ALFS)

						Employment by activities and status (ALFS)
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OECD - Material resources

General information

Description: These data refer to material resources, i.e. materials originating from natural resources that form the material basis of the economy: metals (ferrous, non-ferrous) non-metallic minerals (construction minerals, industrial minerals), biomass (wood, food) and fossil energy carriers.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MATERIAL_RESOURCES

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: raw material, mineral resources, natural resources, soil resources, Mineral resources, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: UNEP "Environment Live" database, Eurostat's "Material Flow and Productivity" database

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Afghanistan, Angola, Albania, Argentina, Armenia, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Burundi, Belgium, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Bulgaria, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, Belize, Bolivia, Brazil, Barbados, Brunei, Bhutan, Botswana, Central African Republic, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Congo, Colombia, Comoros, Cabo Verde, Cuba, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Djibouti, Dominica, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Ecuador, Egypt, Eritrea, Spain, Estonia, Ethiopia, Finland, Fiji, France, Micronesia, Gabon, United Kingdom, Georgia, Ghana, Guinea, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Equatorial Guinea, Greece, Grenada, Guatemala, Guyana, Honduras, Croatia, Haiti, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iran, Iraq, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Cambodia, Kiribati, South Korea, Kuwait, Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Libya, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Morocco, Moldova, Madagascar, Maldives, Mexico, Marshall Islands, North Macedonia, Mali, Malta, Myanmar/Burma, Mongolia, Mozambique, Mauritania, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Nicaragua, Netherlands, Norway, Nepal, New Zealand, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Palau, Papua New

Guinea, Poland, North Korea, Portugal, Paraguay, Qatar, Romania, Russia, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Senegal, Singapore, Solomon Islands, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, Somalia, Serbia, South Sudan, São Tomé and Príncipe, Suriname, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Eswatini, Seychelles, Syria, Chad, Tajikistan, Turkey, Tanzania, United States, Samoa, South Africa

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 11, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MATERIAL_RESOURCES	XML	False
PC-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MATERIAL_RESOURCES	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MATERIAL_RESOURCES	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MATERIAL_RESOURCES	Excel XLS	False

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Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Material resources	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross domestic product per domestic material consumption (2010 PPP)	Socioeconomic variable	US dollars per kilogram	January, 1980 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources
Imports	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources
Domestic extraction used	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources
Exports	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1970 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources
Direct Material Input	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources
Material footprint	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Material resources

OECD - Agri-Environmental other indicators

General information

Description: The OECD database of Agri-environmental Indicators provides the latest and most comprehensive set of agri-environmental indicators (AEIs) across 35 OECD countries and UE countries (plus Norway and Switzerland) from 1990 to 2015.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_OTHER

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Agriculture and Fisheries

Subjects: environmental statistics, pesticide, Environment, Agricultural and aquaculture facilities

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy, Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Eurostat, OECD Agri-environmental Indicators Questionnaire

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, Ukraine, United States, Vietnam, South Africa

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_OTHER	XML	False
PC-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_OTHER	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_OTHER	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=AEI_OTHER	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agri-Environmental indicators	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Irrigable area	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 1990 - December, 2019			Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sales of herbicides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural ammonia (NH3)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Nitrogen oxides (Nox)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sulfur oxides (Sox)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total greenhouse gas emissions by gas (without LULUCF)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Carbon dioxide (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sulphur hexafluoride (SF6)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Harvest wood product (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1994 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total Nitrous oxide (N2O)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Forest land (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Cropland (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Grassland (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Wetlands (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Settlements (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Other land (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Others (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Farmland Birds Index	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having tolerable water erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having low water erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Agricultural land classified as having moderate water erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having low wind erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1991 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Harvest wood product (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Others (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1994 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Total methane (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Forest land (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Cropland (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Grassland (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Settlements (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Other land (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators

Total greenhouse gas emissions by source (without LULUCF)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Energy	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Energy industries	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Industrial processes and product use	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Field burning of agricultural residues (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Others N20	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total greenhouse gas from LULUCF	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total carbone dioxide (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Forest land (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Cropland (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Grassland (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Wetlands (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Settlements (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Other land (CO2)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Transgenic crops	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Organic farming	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sales of insecticides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total sales of agricultural pesticides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Total freshwater abstraction	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agriculture freshwater abstraction	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Biodiesel production	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Other	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total Carbone diocide (CO2) from agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Liming	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Urea application	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Other carbon-containing fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Wetlands (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Total methane (CH4) from agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Enteric fermentation (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Manure management (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Rice cultivation (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Prescribed burning of savannas (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Field burning of agricultural residues (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Others CH4	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators
Total Nitrous oxide (N2O) from agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Environmental indicators

Manure managment (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural soil (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1985 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Prescribed bruning of savannas (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Irrigation area	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Methane (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Nitrous oxide (N20)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Perfluorocarbons (PFCs)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Others CO2	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Manufacturing industries and costruction	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Transports	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Other sectors	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1988 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agriculture surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sales of fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Sales of other pesticides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total Molluscicides	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Direct on-farm energy consumption	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total final energy consumption	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Ethanol production	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total agriculture land area	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

Arable and premanent crop land	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Permanent Pasture	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agriculture groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Cubic metres, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Ammonia (NH3)	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having high water erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having severe water erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total agriculture land area affected by warer erosion	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1991 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

tolerable wind erosion risk						
Agricultural land classified as having moderate wind erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1991 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Agricultural land classified as having high wind erosion risk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1991 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total agriculture land area affected by wind erosion	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1992 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of nitrate in surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of phosphate in surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of nitrate in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of phosphate in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

nitrate in coastal water						
Share of agriculture in total emissions of phosphate in coastal water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of agriculture in total emissions of nitrate in surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas where one or more pesticide are present in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended drinking water limits for nitrate in surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended drinking water limits for nitrate in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1992 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

drinking water limits for phosphorus in surface water						
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended drinking water limits for phosphorus in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2012 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended drinking water limits for pesticides in surface water	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Share of monitoring sites in agricultural areas that exceed recommended drinking water limits for pesticides in groundwater	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1995 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators
Total greenhouse gas emissions with LULUCF	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent, Thousands	January, 1990 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agri-Enviromental indicators

OECD - Non-Medical Determinants of Health

General information

Description: This dataset on health risks examines the non-medical determinants of health by comparing food, alcohol, tobacco consumption (smoking) and body weight (incidence of obesity or overweight) among countries.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/data/oecd-health-statistics/oecd-health-data-non-medical-determinants-of-health_data-00546-en

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Health

Subjects: consumption, nutrition, Population and society, Health

Useful for the analysis of: Population health

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: health.contact@oecd.org

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Luxembourg, Latvia, Mexico, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey, South Africa

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public		XML	False
PC-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://ardit-agricore.idener.es/datasets/edit/354	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://ardit-agricore.idener.es/datasets/edit/354	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://ardit-agricore.idener.es/datasets/edit/354	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Non-Medical Determinants	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Vegetables supply	Socioeconomic variable	Kilos per capita per year	January, 2005 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Non-Medical Determinants

Fruits supply	Socioeconomic variable	Kilos per capita per year	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Non-Medical Determinants
Sugar supply	Socioeconomic variable	Kilos per capita per year	January, 2005 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Non-Medical Determinants

FAO - Manure Management

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT domain Manure Management consists of methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from aerobic and anaerobic processes of manure decomposition. Estimates are computed following the Tier 1 method of the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National greenhouse gas Inventories (IPCC, 2006).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GM>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Climate Change

Subjects: climate change, natural gas, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Manure management

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT domains Production/Live animals (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QA>), Production/Livestock Primary (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QL>)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GM	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GM	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Chickens, broilers	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Ducks	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Goats	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cattle, dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Chickens, layers	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Buffaloes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Horses	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Camels	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Llamas	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Mules	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Swine, breeding	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Turkeys	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Asses	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Cattle, non-dairy	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH ₄) [kt] Direct emissions (N ₂ O) [kt] Indirect emissions (N ₂ O) [kt] Emissions (N ₂ O) [kt] Stocks [heads]	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys

Manure (N content)	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH4) [kt] Direct emissions (N2O) [kt] Indirect emissions (N2O) [kt] Emissions (N2O) [kt] Stocks [heads]	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys
Emissions (CH4)	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH4) [kt] Direct emissions (N2O) [kt] Indirect emissions (N2O) [kt] Emissions (N2O) [kt] Stocks [heads]	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys
Direct emissions (N2O)	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH4) [kt] Direct emissions (N2O) [kt] Indirect emissions (N2O) [kt] Emissions (N2O) [kt] Stocks [heads]	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys
Indirect emissions (N2O)	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH4) [kt] Direct emissions (N2O)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys

		[kt] Indirect emissions (N2O) [kt] Emissions (N2O) [kt] Stocks [heads]				
Emissions (N2O)	Socioeconomic variable	Manure (N content) [kg] Emissions (CH4) [kt] Direct emissions (N2O) [kt] Indirect emissions (N2O) [kt] Emissions (N2O) [kt] Stocks [heads]	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Buffaloes, Asses, Camels, Cattle, dairy, Cattle, non-dairy, Chickens, broilers, Chickens, layers, Ducks, Goats, Horses, Llamas, Mules, Sheep, Swine, breeding, Turkeys

FAO - Emissions Totals

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT domain Emissions Totals summarizes the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions disseminated in the FAOSTAT Climate Change Emissions domains, generated from agriculture and forest land.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Emissions

Subjects: reduction of gas emissions, emission trading, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Air emissions intensities, Greenhouse gas emissions, Climate change

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: FAOSTAT, FAO TIER 1, UNFCCC

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: October 20, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Direct emissions (N2O)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (CH4)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (N2O)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Indirect emissions (N2O)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Emissions (CO2)	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Manure management	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Rice cultivation	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Synthetic Fertilizers	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5)
Manure applied to Soils	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5)
Manure left on Pasture	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Crop residues	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5)
Burning - Crop residues	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4

						(AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Drained organic soils	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5)
New forest conversion	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Forestland	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Savanna fire	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Forest fires	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Fires in organic soils	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Direct emissions (N20)
On-farm energy use	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions

						(N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)
Enteric Fermentation	Socioeconomic variable	Kilotonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Direct emissions (N20), Emissions (CH4), Emissions (N20), Indirect emissions (N20), Emissions (CO2eq) from CH4 (AR5), Emissions (CO2eq) (AR5), Emissions (CO2)

FAO - Production Indices

General information

Description: Production indices of Agriculture, Cereals, Crops, Food , Livestock, Meat indigenous, Milk, Non Food, Oilcrops, Oil Equivalent, Roots and Tubers, Sugar Crops Primary, Vegetables and Fruit Primary.

Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Primary, Cereals, Coarse Grain, Citrus Fruit, Fruit, Jute Jute-like Fibres, Oilcakes Equivalent, Oil crops Primary, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts and Vegetables and Melons. Data are expressed in terms of area harvested, production quantity and yield. The objective is to comprehensively cover production of all primary crops for all countries and regions in the world.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Production

Subjects: production statistics, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Production and industrial facilities

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: The main data source is official statistics from FAO member countries, collected either through annual production questionnaires

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 18, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords: production, production indices

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Crops	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Food	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Livestock	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Meat Indigenous	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Milk	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Non food	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Oilcrops, oil equivalent	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Roots and tubers	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Sugar crops primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Vegetables and fruit primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross Production Index Number (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	Production Quantity and Seed: tonnes; Area harvested: hectares; Yield: tonnes per hectare.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops, Cereals, Food, Livestock, Meat Indigenous, Milk, Non food, Oilcrops, oil equivalent, Roots and tubers, Sugar crops primary, Vegetables and fruit primary
Gross per capita Production Index Number (2014-2016 = 100)	Socioeconomic variable	Production Quantity and Seed: tonnes; Area harvested: hectares; Yield: tonnes per hectare.	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Crops, Cereals, Food, Livestock, Meat Indigenous, Milk, Non food, Oilcrops, oil equivalent, Roots and tubers, Sugar crops primary, Vegetables and fruit primary

FAO - Macro Indicators

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT Macro Indicators database provides a selection of country-level macroeconomic indicators relating to total economy (GDP, GFCF); agriculture (Ag); agriculture, forestry and fishing (AFF); manufacturing (MAN); manufacturing of food products and beverages (FB); manufacturing of tobacco products (Tob); and manufacturing of food, beverage and tobacco products (FBT).

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/MK>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Macrostatistics

Subjects: macroeconomics, economic statistics, economic indicator, Business, statistics, Economy and finance, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Macroeconomic indices

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update:

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1970 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/MK	Excel XLS	False
Excel (Xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/MK	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross Domestic Product	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Gross Fixed Capital Formation	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

Value Added (Total Manufacturing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added (Manufacture of food, beverages and tobacco products)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added (Manufacture of food and beverages)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added (Manufacture of tobacco products)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Gross National Income	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Value Added (Agriculture)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Gross Output (Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country
Gross Output (Agriculture)	Socioeconomic variable	USD, Millions	January, 1970 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Country

FAO - Producer Prices

General information

Description: This sub-domain contains data on Agriculture Producer Prices and Producer Price Index. Agriculture Producer Prices are prices received by farmers for primary crops, live animals and livestock primary products as collected at the point of initial sale (prices paid at the farm-gate)

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PP>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Prices

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Montly

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 21, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1991 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Text file	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/PP	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Citrus Fruit	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Coarse Grain	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Crops Primary	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Agriculture	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals (Rice Milled Eqv)	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Eggs Primary	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Fibre Crops Primary	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		

Fruit excl Melons	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Fruit Incl Melons	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Fruit Primary	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Jute & Jute-like Fibres	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Livestock	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Meat Liveweight	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Meat	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Milk	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Oilcrops, Oil Equivalent	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Pulses	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Roots and Tubers	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Country		
Treenuts	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Vegetables Primary	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		
Vegetables & Melons	January, 1991 - December, 2018	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Producer Price	Price variable	USD / tonne	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Agriculture , Cereals (Rice Milled Eqv), Cereals, Citrus Fruit, Coarse Grain, Crops Primary , Eggs Primary , Fibre Crops Primary , Fruit excl Melons, Fruit Incl Melons , Fruit Primary , Jute & Jute-like Fibres , Livestock, Meat Liveweight, Meat, Milk, Oilcrops, Oil Equivalent , Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts, Vegetables Primary , Vegetables&Melons
Producer price index	Socioeconomic variable	Index (2014-2016) = 100	January, 1991 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture , Cereals (Rice Milled Eqv), Cereals, Citrus Fruit, Coarse Grain, Crops Primary , Eggs Primary , Fibre Crops Primary , Fruit excl Melons, Fruit Incl Melons , Fruit Primary , Jute & Jute-like Fibres , Livestock, Meat Liveweight, Meat, Milk, Oilcrops, Oil Equivalent , Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts, Vegetables Primary , Vegetables&Melons

OECD - Green Growth Indicators

General information

Description: The OECD Green Growth database contains selected indicators for monitoring progress towards green growth to support policy making and inform the public at large. The database synthesises data and indicators across a wide range of domains including a range of OECD databases as well as external data sources.

Producer: OECD

Link: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: environmental indicator, green economy, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy, Pollutant Gases, Air emissions intensities

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1990 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH	Excel XLS	False
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH	XML	False
Developer API	JSON	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH	JSON	False
PC-Axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH	PC-AXIS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Green growth indicators	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Production-based CO2 intensity, energy-related CO2 per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Demand-based CO2 productivity, GDP per unit of energy-related CO2 emissions	Socioeconomic variable	US dollars per kilogram, 2015	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Demand-based CO2 intensity, energy-related CO2 per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Demand-based CO2 emissions	Socioeconomic variable	Index 2000 = 100	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Demand-based CO2 emissions	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Production-based CO2 productivity, GDP per unit of energy-related CO2 emissions	Socioeconomic variable	US dollars per kilogram, 2015	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Production-based CO2 emissions, index 2000=100	Socioeconomic variable	Index 2000 = 100	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Production-based CO2 emissions	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators

CO2 intensity of GDP, CO2	Socioeconomic variable	emissions per unit of GDP	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Energy productivity, GDP per unit of TPES	Socioeconomic variable	US Dollar, 2015	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Energy intensity, TPES per capita	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Total primary energy supply, index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Total primary energy supply	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), Millions	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Renewable energy supply, % total energy supply	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Renewable electricity, % total electricity generation	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Energy consumption in agriculture, % total energy consumption	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Energy consumption in services, % total	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators

energy consumption						
Renewable energy supply (excluding solid biofuels), % total energy supply	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Population with access to improved drinking water sources	Socioeconomic variable	% total population	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Population with access to improved sanitation	Socioeconomic variable	% total population	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Permanent surface water	Socioeconomic variable	% total surface	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Seasonal surface water	Socioeconomic variable	% total surface	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Intact forest landscape	Socioeconomic variable	Square kilometres	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Intact forest landscape loss	Socioeconomic variable	% since 2000	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Development of environment-related technologies	Socioeconomic variable	% all technologies	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Relative advantage in environment-	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators

related technology						
Development of environment-related technologies	Socioeconomic variable	% inventions worldwide	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Development of environment-related technologies	Socioeconomic variable	Pure number	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Real GDP, Index	Socioeconomic variable	Index, 2000=100	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators
Population	Socioeconomic variable	Per 1 000 inhabitants	January, 1990 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Green growth indicators

FADN - Public Database (SO)

General information

Description: The farm accountancy data network (FADN) monitors farms' income and business activities. It is also an important informative source for understanding the impact of the measures taken under the common agricultural policy.

Producer: EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Link: <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FADNPublicDatabase/FADNPublicDatabase.html>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FADN Public database (SO)

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance, Business, statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Income and business activities, Farm structure, Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: national surveys

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 6, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 30, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2004 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel (xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FA-DNPublicDatabase/FA-DNPublicDatabase.html	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
(SE027)Permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE028)Permanent grassland	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE035)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE041)Other field crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE042)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE046)Vegetables and flowers	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE050)Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE055)Orchards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE060)Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE065)Other permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE054)Permanent crops other than vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE071)Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE072)Agricultural fallows without any subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE073)Set aside	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE074)Total agricultural area out of production	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE075)Woodland area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE080)Total livestock units	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE085)Dairy cows (incl. buffaloes)	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE086)Cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE087)Buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE090)Other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE095)Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE100)Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE10)Poultry	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE110)Yield of wheat	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE115)Yield of maize	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE120)Stocking density	Socioeconomic variable	q / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE125)Milk yield (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE126)Milk yield cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE127)Milk yield buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE131)Total output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE132)Total output /Total input	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE135)Total output crops and crop production	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE136)Total crop output/ha production	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE140)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE145)Protein crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE146)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE150)Potatoes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE155)Sugar beet	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE160)Oil-seed crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE165)Industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE170 Vegetables & flowers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE175 Fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE180	Citrus fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE185	Wine and grapes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE190	Olives & olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE195	Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE200	Other crop output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE206	Total output livestock and livestock products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE207	Total livestock output / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE211	Change in value of livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE216	Cows' milk and milk products (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE220	Beef and veal	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE225 Pigmeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE230 Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE235 Poultrymeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE240 Eggs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE618 Subsidies sheep & goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE619 Other livestock subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE624 Total support for rural development	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE415M Farm Net Value Added - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Farm Holding
SE245 Ewes' and goats' milk	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE251 Other livestock & products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE256 Other output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE700 Total OGA output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE715 Forestry and wood processing	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE720 Contractual work (services)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE725 Agritourism	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE260 Farmhouse consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE265 Farm use	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE270 Total Inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE275 Total intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE281 Total specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE284	Specific crop costs / ha	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE420	Farm Net Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE285	Seeds and plants	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE290	Seeds and plants home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE295	Fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE296	Fertiliser N	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE297	Fertiliser P	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE298	Fertiliser K	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE300	Crop protection	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE305	Other crop specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE309 Specific livestock costs / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE310 Feed for grazing livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE320 Feed for pigs and poultry	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE325 Feed for pigs and poultry home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE330 Other livestock specific costs, incl. veterinary expenses	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE750 All specific costs for other gainful activities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE331 Forestry specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE336 Total farming overheads	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE340 Machinery & building current costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE345 Energy	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE350 Contract work	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE356 Other direct inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE360 Depreciation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE365 Total external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE370 Wages paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE375 Rent paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SYS02)Farms represented	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SYS03)Sample farms	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE005)Economic size	Socioeconomic variable	Total standard output in € / 1000	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE010)Total labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE015)Unpaid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE020)Paid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE011)Labour input	Socioeconomic variable	Hours	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE022)Share of OGA work in total work	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE025)Total Utilised Agricultural Area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Sum	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE030)Rented U.A.A.	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE026)Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE380 Interest paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE381 Balance of interest paid and received	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE605 Total subsidies - excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE606 Total Direct Payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE610 Total subsidies on crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE611 Compensatory payments/area payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE612 Set aside premiums	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE613 Other crops subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE615 Total subsidies on livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE616 Subsidies dairying	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE617 Subsidies other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE621 Environmental subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE622 LFA subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE623 Other rural development payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE625 Subsidies on intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE626 Subsidies on external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE630 Decoupled payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE631 Single Farm Payment and Basic Payment Scheme	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE632 Single Area payment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE640 Additional aid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE650 Total aid for Article 68	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE699 Other subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE600 Balance current subsidies and taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE390 Taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE395 VAT balance excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE405 Balance subsidies and taxes on investment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE406 Subsidies on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE409 Subsidies on agricultural investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE407 Payments to dairy outgoers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE408 Balance of VAT on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE410 Gross Farm Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE415 Farm Net Value Added	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE425 Farm Net Value Added / AWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE425M Farm Net Value Added / AWU - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Farm Holding
SE430 Family Farm Income / FWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE436 Total assets closing valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE437 Total assets, opening valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE441 Total fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE446 Land, permanent crops and quotas	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE450 Farm buildings	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE455 Machinery and equipment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE460 Breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE465 Total current assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE470 Non-breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE475 Stock of agricultural products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE476 Inventories	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE480 Other circulating capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE485 Total liabilities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE490 Long & medium-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE495 Short-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE501 Net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE506 Change in net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE510 Average farm capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE516	Gross Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE521	Net Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE526	Cash Flow (1)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE530	Cash Flow (2)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE532	Cash flow / farm total capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

FAO - Consumer Price Indices

General information

Description: These indices measure the price change between the current and reference periods of the average basket of goods and services purchased by households.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CP>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Prices

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Month

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: ECCB, UNCTAD, International Monetary Fund (IMF), UN Statistics Division(UNSD), OECD, BCEAO

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: September 20, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CP	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/CP	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Country	January, 2000 - December, 2021	Country	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Consumer Prices, Food Indices (2015=100)	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2000 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Country
Consumer Prices, General Indices (2015=100)	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2000 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Country
Food price inflation	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2000 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Country

FAO - Value of Agricultural Production

General information

Description: Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Primary, Cereals, Coarse Grain, Citrus Fruit, Fruit, Jute Jute-like Fibres, Oilcakes Equivalent, Oil crops Primary, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts and Vegetables and Melons.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QV>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Production

Subjects: production statistics, crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, production value, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Afghanistan, Angola, Albania, Argentina, Armenia, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Azerbaijan, Burundi, Belgium, Benin, Burkina Faso, Bangladesh, Bulgaria, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, Belize, Bolivia, Brazil, Barbados, Brunei, Bhutan, Botswana, Central African Republic, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Congo, Cook Islands, Colombia, Cabo Verde, Costa Rica, Czechoslovakia, Cuba, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Djibouti, Dominica, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Algeria, Ecuador, Egypt, Eritrea, Spain, Estonia, Ethiopia, Finland, Fiji, France, Faroes, Micronesia, Gabon, United Kingdom, Georgia, Guernsey, Ghana, Guinea, Guadeloupe, The Gambia, Equatorial Guinea, Greece, Grenada, Guatemala, French Guiana, Hong Kong, Honduras, Croatia, Haiti, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iran, Iraq, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Cambodia, Kiribati, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Kuwait, Laos, Lebanon, Liberia, Libya, Saint Lucia, Sri Lanka, Lesotho, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Macau, Morocco, Monaco, Moldova, Madagascar, Maldives, Mexico, Marshall Islands, North Macedonia, Mali, Malta, Myanmar/Burma, Mongolia, Mauritania, Martinique, Mauritius, Malawi, Malaysia, Namibia, New Caledonia, Niger, Nigeria,

Nicaragua, Niue, Netherlands, Norway, Nepal, Nauru, New Zealand, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Papua New Guinea, Poland, Puerto Rico, North Korea, Portugal, Paraguay, Palestine, French Polynesia, Qatar, Réunion, Romania, Russia, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Serbia and Montenegro, Sudan, Senegal, Singapore, Svalbard and Jan Mayen, Solomon Islands, Sierra Leone, El Salvador, Somalia, Serbia, South Sudan, São Tomé and Príncipe, Suriname, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Eswatini, Seychelles, Syria, Chad, Togo, Thailand, Tajikistan, Tokelau, Turkmenistan, Timor-Leste, Tonga, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Tuvalu, Taiwan, Tanzania, Uganda, Ukraine, Uruguay, United States, Uzbekistan, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Democratic Republic of Vietnam, Venezuela, Vanuatu, Yemen, Yugoslavia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 18, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QV	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QV	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Cereals	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Sugar crops primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Food Total	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		
Vegetables and Fruit primary	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross Production Value	Socioeconomic variable	thousand US\$	January, 1961 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, Cereals, Sugar crops primary, Food Total, Vegetables and Fruit primary

FAO - Land Cover

General information

Description: The FAOSTAT domain Land Cover under the Agri-Environmental Indicators section contains land cover information organized by the land cover classes of the international standard system for Environmental and Economic Accounting Central Framework (SEEA CF). The land cover information is compiled from publicly available Global Land Cover (GLC) maps: a) MODIS land cover types based on the Land Cover Classification System, LCCS (2001–2018) and b) the European Spatial Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative (CCI) annual land cover maps (1992–2018) produced by the Université catholique de Louvain (UCL)-Geomatics and now under the European Copernicus Program.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/LC/>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: land use, Land cover

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters): 1.0

Temporal resolution: Years

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 26, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1992 - December, 2018

Keywords: land cover

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
XLS	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/LC	Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/LC	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Coastal water bodies and intertidal areas	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Woody crops	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Artificial surfaces (including urban and associated areas)	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Shrubs and/or herbaceous vegetation, aquatic or regularly flooded	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Herbaceous crops	January, 1992 - December, 2018			

Sparsely natural vegetated areas	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Multiple or layered crops	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Mangroves	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Terrestrial barren land	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Permanent snow and glaciers	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Inland water bodies	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Grassland	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Shrub-covered areas	January, 1992 - December, 2018			
Tree-covered areas	January, 1992 - December, 2018			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area from MODIS	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 1992 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Artificial surfaces (including urban and associated areas), Shrubs and/or herbaceous vegetation, aquatic or regularly flooded, Herbaceous crops, Sparsely natural vegetated areas, Woody crops, Multiple or layered crops, Mangroves, Terrestrial barren land, Permanent snow and glaciers, Inland water bodies, Grassland, Shrub-covered

						areas, Tree-covered areas, Coastal water bodies and intertidal areas
Area from CCI_LC	Socioeconomic variable	1000 ha	January, 1992 - December, 2018	Instant value	Annual	Artificial surfaces (including urban and associated areas), Shrubs and/or herbaceous vegetation, aquatic or regularly flooded, Herbaceous crops, Sparsely natural vegetated areas, Woody crops, Multiple or layered crops, Mangroves, Terrestrial barren land, Permanent snow and glaciers, Inland water bodies, Grassland, Shrub-covered areas, Tree-covered areas, Coastal water bodies and intertidal areas

FAO - Emissions intensities

General information

Description: Intensities of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by unit of product for a selection of agricultural commodities.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EI>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Agri-Environmental Indicators

Subjects: atmospheric pollution, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Air emissions intensities

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 3, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1961 - December, 2017

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EI	CSV	False
Excel (Xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/EI	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Meat, cattle	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Rice, paddy	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Milk, whole fresh sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Cereals excluding rice	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Meat, buffalo	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Milk, whole fresh cow	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Meat, goat	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Milk, whole fresh camel	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		

Meat, pig	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Milk, whole fresh goat	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Eggs, hen, in shell	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Milk, whole fresh buffalo	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Meat, chicken	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		
Meat, sheep	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Production Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Cereals excluding rice, Meat, buffalo, Meat, cattle, Rice, paddy, Milk, whole fresh sheep, Milk, whole fresh cow, Meat, goat, Milk, whole fresh camel, Meat, pig, Milk, whole fresh goat, Eggs, hen, in shell, Milk, whole fresh buffalo, Meat, chicken, Meat, sheep
Emission intensity	Socioeconomic variable	kg CO ₂ eq/kg product	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Cereals excluding rice, Meat, buffalo, Meat, cattle, Rice, paddy, Milk, whole fresh sheep, Milk, whole fresh cow, Meat, goat, Milk, whole fresh camel, Meat, pig, Milk, whole fresh goat, Eggs, hen, in shell, Milk, whole fresh buffalo, Meat, chicken, Meat, sheep
Emissions (CO ₂ eq)	Socioeconomic variable	Gigagrams	January, 1961 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Cereals excluding rice, Meat, buffalo, Meat, cattle, Rice, paddy, Milk, whole fresh

						sheep, Milk, whole fresh cow, Meat, goat, Milk, whole fresh camel, Meat, pig, Milk, whole fresh goat, Eggs, hen, in shell, Milk, whole fresh buffalo, Meat, chicken, Meat, sheep
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FAO - Forestry Trade Flows

General information

Description: The database contains data on the bilateral trade flows in roundwood, primary wood and paper products for all countries and territories in the world. The main types of primary forest products included in are: roundwood, sawnwood, wood-based panels, pulp, and paper and paperboard. These products are detailed further. The definitions are available.

Producer: FAO

Link: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FT>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FAO - Forestry

Subjects: forestry policy, forestry economics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of:

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Electronic questionnaire

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: World

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: June 19, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1997 - December, 2017

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadheet	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/FT	Excel XLS	False
csv	CSV	Public	https://www.fao.org/aostat/en/#data/FT	CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Sawnwood, non-coniferous all	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
Veneer sheets	January, 1997 - December, 2019	Country	95	
Plywood	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
Industrial roundwood, coniferous (export/import)	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous non-tropical (export/import)	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
Wood chips and particles	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
Sawnwood, coniferous	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	

Newsprint	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Country	95	
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Export Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Export Quantity [m3] Export Quantity [t] Export Value [1000 USD] Import Quantity [m3] Import Quantity [t] Import Value [1000 USD]	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Sawnwood, non-coniferous all, Veneer sheets, Plywood, Industrial roundwood, coniferous (export/import), Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous non-tropical (export/import), Wood chips and particles, Sawnwood, coniferous, Newsprint
Export Value	Socioeconomic variable	Export Quantity [m3] Export Quantity [t] Export Value [1000 USD] Import Quantity [m3] Import Quantity [t] Import Value [1000 USD]	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Sawnwood, non-coniferous all, Veneer sheets, Plywood, Industrial roundwood, coniferous (export/import), Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous non-tropical (export/import), Wood chips and particles, Sawnwood, coniferous, Newsprint
Import Quantity	Socioeconomic variable	Export Quantity [m3] Export Quantity [t] Export Value [1000 USD] Import	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Sawnwood, non-coniferous all, Veneer sheets, Plywood, Industrial roundwood, coniferous (export/import), Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous non-tropical (export/import), Wood chips and particles, Sawnwood, coniferous, Newsprint

		Quantity [m3]Import Quantity [t]Import Value [1000 USD]				
Import Value	Socioeconomic variable	Export Quantity [m3]Export Quantity [t]Export Value [1000 USD]Import Quantity [m3]Import Quantity [t]Import Value [1000 USD]	January, 1997 - December, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Sawnwood, non-coniferous all, Veneer sheets, Plywood, Industrial roundwood, coniferous (export/import), Industrial roundwood, non-coniferous non-tropical (export/import), Wood chips and particles, Sawnwood, coniferous, Newsprint

OECD - Generation of waste by sector

General information

Description: This dataset presents waste produced by the various sectors of economic activity (agriculture, mining and quarrying, manufacturing industry, energy production, water purification and distribution, construction, etc.). The disaggregation of waste by sector follows the major divisions of International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) revision 4.

Producer: OECD

Link: <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR>

Languages: English

Catalogue: OECD - Environment

Subjects: waste, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Member countries' authorities through the questionnaire on the state of the environment (OECD/Eurostat)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, South Korea, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Turkey

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: November 30, 2021

Issued:

Last update: March 1, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2004 - December, 2018

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
SDMX	XML	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR	XML	False
Developer API	JSON	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR	JSON	False
Pc-axis	PC-AXIS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR	PC-AXIS	False
Text file	CSV	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR	CSV	False
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=WSECTOR	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry	January, 1990 - March, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Waste	Socioeconomic variable	Tonnes, thousands	January, 1990 - March, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Agriculture, forestry and fishing industry

Polski FADN - Standard Results of Polish FADN agricultural holdings [UTP]

General information

Description: The farm accountancy data network (FADN) monitors farms' income and business activities. It is also an important informative source for understanding the impact of the measures taken under the common agricultural policy.

Producer: EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Link: <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FADNPublicDatabase/FADNPublicDatabase.html>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FADN Public database (SO)

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance, Business, statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Income and business activities, Farm structure, Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: national surveys

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 13, 2021

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued:

Last update: November 30, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2004 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel (xls)	Excel XLS	Public	https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FA-DNPublicDatabase/FA-DNPublicDatabase.html	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
(SE027)Permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE028)Permanent grassland	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE035)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE041)Other field crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE042)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE046)Vegetables and flowers	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE050)Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE055)Orchards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE060)Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE065)Other permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE054)Permanent crops other than vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE071)Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE072)Agricultural fallows without any subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE073)Set aside	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE074)Total agricultural area out of production	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE075)Woodland area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE080)Total livestock units	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE085)Dairy cows (incl. buffaloes)	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE086)Cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE087)Buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE090)Other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE095)Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE100)Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE10)Poultry	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE110)Yield of wheat	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE115)Yield of maize	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE120)Stocking density	Socioeconomic variable	q / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE125)Milk yield (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE126)Milk yield cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE127)Milk yield buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE131)Total output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE132)Total output /Total input	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE135)Total output crops and crop production	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE136)Total crop output/ha production	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE140)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE145)Protein crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE146)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE150)Potatoes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE155)Sugar beet	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE160)Oil-seed crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE165)Industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE170 Vegetables & flowers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE175 Fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE180	Citrus fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE185	Wine and grapes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE190	Olives & olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE195	Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE200	Other crop output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE206	Total output livestock and livestock products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE207	Total livestock output / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE211	Change in value of livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE216	Cows' milk and milk products (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE220	Beef and veal	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE225 Pigmeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE230 Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE235 Poultrymeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE240 Eggs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE618 Subsidies sheep & goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE619 Other livestock subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE624 Total support for rural development	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE415M Farm Net Value Added - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Farm Holding
SE245 Ewes' and goats' milk	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE251 Other livestock & products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE256 Other output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE700 Total OGA output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE715 Forestry and wood processing	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE720 Contractual work (services)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE725 Agritourism	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE260 Farmhouse consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE265 Farm use	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE270 Total Inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE275 Total intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE281 Total specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE284	Specific crop costs / ha	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE420	Farm Net Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE285	Seeds and plants	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE290	Seeds and plants home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE295	Fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE296	Fertiliser N	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE297	Fertiliser P	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE298	Fertiliser K	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE300	Crop protection	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE305	Other crop specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE309 Specific livestock costs / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE310 Feed for grazing livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE320 Feed for pigs and poultry	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE325 Feed for pigs and poultry home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE330 Other livestock specific costs, incl. veterinary expenses	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE750 All specific costs for other gainful activities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE331 Forestry specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE336 Total farming overheads	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE340 Machinery & building current costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE345 Energy	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE350 Contract work	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE356 Other direct inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE360 Depreciation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE365 Total external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE370 Wages paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE375 Rent paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SYS02)Farms represented	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SYS03)Sample farms	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE005)Economic size	Socioeconomic variable	Total standard output in € / 1000	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE010)Total labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

(SE015)Unpaid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE020)Paid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE011)Labour input	Socioeconomic variable	Hours	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE022)Share of OGA work in total work	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE025)Total Utilised Agricultural Area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Sum	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE030)Rented U.A.A.	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
(SE026)Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE380 Interest paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE381 Balance of interest paid and received	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE605 Total subsidies - excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE606 Total Direct Payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE610 Total subsidies on crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE611 Compensatory payments/area payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE612 Set aside premiums	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE613 Other crops subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE615 Total subsidies on livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE616 Subsidies dairying	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE617 Subsidies other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE621 Environmental subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE622 LFA subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE623 Other rural development payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE625 Subsidies on intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE626 Subsidies on external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE630 Decoupled payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE631 Single Farm Payment and Basic Payment Scheme	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE632 Single Area payment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE640 Additional aid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE650 Total aid for Article 68	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE699 Other subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE600 Balance current subsidies and taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE390 Taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE395 VAT balance excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE405 Balance subsidies and taxes on investment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE406 Subsidies on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE409 Subsidies on agricultural investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE407 Payments to dairy outgoers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE408 Balance of VAT on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE410 Gross Farm Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE415 Farm Net Value Added	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE425 Farm Net Value Added / AWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE425M Farm Net Value Added / AWU - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Farm Holding
SE430 Family Farm Income / FWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE436 Total assets closing valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE437 Total assets, opening valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE441 Total fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE446 Land, permanent crops and quotas	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE450 Farm buildings	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE455 Machinery and equipment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE460 Breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE465 Total current assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE470 Non-breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE475 Stock of agricultural products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE476 Inventories	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE480 Other circulating capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE485 Total liabilities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE490 Long & medium-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE495 Short-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE501 Net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE506 Change in net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE510 Average farm capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

SE516	Gross Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE521	Net Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE526	Cash Flow (1)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE530	Cash Flow (2)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
SE532	Cash flow / farm total capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding